

Master of Science in Environmental Meteorology

Thesis

Avalanche Forecasting in the Pejo Ski Area: A Data-Driven Approach Using Support Vector Machines

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Abstract

Snow avalanches are fast-moving snow masses that can cause severe damage to infrastructure and loss of life, making them one of the most dangerous natural hazards in mountain regions.

The prediction of snow avalanches is a crucial issue in Alpine regions, significantly impacting public safety and the economic well-being of mountain communities. By accurately predicting avalanche occurrences, forecasters help protect lives, minimize damage to property, and guide outdoor enthusiasts in making informed decisions. This process involves analyzing a variety of factors, such as snowfall patterns, weather conditions, and terrain features, to assess the stability of snowpack and evaluate potential hazards. As mountainous areas attract skiers, climbers, and hikers, reliable avalanche forecasts are crucial for preventing accidents and promoting safer recreational activities in these breathtaking yet potentially dangerous environments. While traditional forecasting methods are often reliable, they mainly depend on expert judgment and empirical techniques, which can introduce subjectivity and limit their scalability. Recently, physically based models have been proposed to enhance objectivity and consistency in avalanche forecasting. However, their effectiveness at the local level is often limited by data quality and a lack of good spatial representation.

This thesis explores the potential of a data-driven approach to help local avalanche forecasters in their decision-making. A Support Vector Machine (SVM) model has been used to classify daily natural avalanche release probability for the Pejo Ski Area. The model uses traditional nivo-meteorological data as input, including well-known variables that significantly affect snow stability. Key challenges in predicting avalanches, such as imbalanced datasets and the non-linear interactions between the nivo-meteorological features affecting snow stability, are addressed to improve the model's reliability and practical usefulness.

The focus is on applying the model on a restricted area with limited data available, such the Pejo Ski area and evaluating its performance in real-world forecasting. The results indicate that Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are effective decision-support tools, demonstrating strong predictive capabilities in distinguishing between avalanche and non-avalanche events. The performance metrics for the test dataset indicate an F1-score of 0.827 and an ROC-AUC of 0.880, highlighting a strong ability to accurately classify avalanche events. Additionally, this thesis looks into incorporating model interpretability techniques, like SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) tools, to help bridge the gap between automated predictions and the trust needed from experts. These tools help forecasters understand the reasons behind the model's outputs, making the usually opaque "black-box" nature of machine learning clearer and increasing confidence in its practical use.

The findings suggest that machine learning can enhance avalanche forecasting by working alongside traditional methods, especially when combined with understandable insights. This research contributes to the development of data-driven tools in snow science, aiming to improve risk management and safety for the public in mountainous areas.

Keywords: Avalanche forecasting, local forecasting, risk management, data-driven approach, nivo-meteorological data, machine learning, Support Vector Machine, model interpretability.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

Avalanches as a Major Natural Hazard

Avalanches represent a major natural hazard in mountainous and alpine regions worldwide. Triggered by various natural and human-induced factors, such as heavy snowfall, rapid temperature changes, wind-loading, or skier activity, avalanches can occur suddenly and with devastating force. They pose serious threats to human life, often causing injuries or fatalities among residents, tourists, and outdoor enthusiasts. Beyond loss of life, avalanches can destroy infrastructure like roads, railways, power lines, and buildings, disrupting transportation and communication, and imposing long-term economic burdens on affected communities.

The impact of avalanches often goes beyond immediate damage, isolating remote areas and interrupting essential services. In regions that rely on tourism and winter sports, avalanches cause significant disturbances and substantial economic losses due to the closure of ski slopes and the resulting decline in visitor numbers. These events negatively affect tourist inflows, harming local businesses and the entire winter tourism industry.

Effective avalanche risk management is crucial for public safety and socioeconomic stability. Central to this is the development of accurate, timely, and cost-effective forecasting systems that integrate meteorological data, snowpack analysis, expert knowledge, and increasingly, machine learning techniques to assess avalanche likelihood and issue early warnings. Public education, real-time data sharing, and digital decision-support tools further enable informed preventive actions.

Traditional Forecasting Methods and Their Limitations

Traditionally, avalanche forecasting depends on empirical methods and rules from forecasters' experience, based on direct observations and local knowledge of terrain and climate. While often effective, this approach relies heavily on human intuition and site-specific memory, leading to limitations in consistency and scalability.

Forecasting mainly uses nivological data (snow surface features, snowpack evolution, temperature profiles) and meteorological data (wind, snowfall, air temperature, solar radiation). Snowpack stability is assessed through physical profiles where technicians dig snow pits to identify weak layers and perform empirical stability tests.

Despite standardized procedures, this approach has structural limitations:

- Subjectivity, as interpretations vary between forecasters
- Difficulty managing large, heterogeneous datasets
- Limited reproducibility due to the high spatial variability of snow properties, which can differ significantly even over short distances
- Limited scalability, complicating regional or national forecast coordination.+

Emergence of Data-Driven and Machine Learning Approaches

These issues highlight the need for more objective, data-driven, and technologically advanced systems. Modern IT and AI enable more consistent, evidence-based decisions. Automation improves accuracy, reduces human error, and increases transparency, vital in high-risk contexts.

Recently, avalanche forecasting benefited from greater availability of nivo-meteorological data from automatic stations and systematic field observations. Combined with digitization and access to comprehensive historical datasets, this enables advanced analyses.

New approaches are motivated by the limitations of traditional, empirical methods. Machine learning holds promise by modeling complex relationships between meteorology and avalanches, thus improving adaptability and decision automation.

However, challenges remain: avalanche phenomena are complex and nonlinear, data are imbalanced (rare avalanche events), and machine learning models can be hard to interpret (“black-box” issue), hindering operational use. Rigorous testing on real data and varying climate scenarios is essential for reliability.

1.2 Objectives and Novel Contributions

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the application of a machine learning model for avalanche forecasting, aimed at supporting local forecasters in operational avalanche risk assessments within a local context. The study focuses on developing and evaluating data-driven models to identify potential avalanche release scenarios using both historical and real-time meteorological and snowfall data from the Pejo Ski Area.

Research Objectives and Potential Advantages of a Data-Driven Approach

This research is guided by the following objectives:

- To explore the potential of supervised machine learning models for predicting avalanche occurrences in a specific alpine setting.
- To identify the most informative features, meteorological, topographical, and snowpack-related, that influence avalanche release.
- To compare different model configurations in terms of predictive accuracy and interpretability.
- To evaluate the operational applicability of these models in daily avalanche risk management.

This study explores three main potential advantages of using machine learning for avalanche forecasting. First, a data-driven approach can enhance the objectivity and consistency of avalanche forecasting compared to traditional methods that rely primarily on expert judgment, particularly in uncertain or borderline situations. Second, machine learning models are capable of capturing complex, non-linear interactions among variables that are often overlooked by classical statistical techniques. Third, the use of interpretability tools, such as feature importance rankings and SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values, can offer valuable insights into the physical drivers of avalanche activity, thereby contributing to scientific understanding and operational decision-making.

Methodology

The research adopts a quantitative and empirical approach. A dataset comprising meteorological data, snowpack measurements, and historical avalanche occurrences is collected and preprocessed. A Support Vector Machine (SVM) model is trained and validated using cross-validation. Multiple model setups are tested to handle class imbalance and perform feature selection to identify the most accurate configuration, ensuring simplicity and efficiency. Model performance is evaluated using standard classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC-ROC). Furthermore, model explainability techniques are applied to assess the contribution of each feature to the model’s predictions.

Novel Contributions

This work stands out for its dual contribution to both scientific research and practical forecasting. From a research perspective, it offers a targeted analysis of machine learning techniques, specifically Support Vector Machines (SVMs), applied to avalanche prediction at a local scale, where historical data are often limited compared to regional datasets, reducing the opportunities to develop robust predictive models. This approach contrasts with most existing studies, which generally rely on large-scale regional datasets. On the operational side, the study aims not only to enhance predictive accuracy but also to deliver interpretable results that enable forecasters to understand the interactions between input variables in individual cases. By providing a physically grounded explanation of the model's behavior, this method fosters greater transparency and supports more informed decision-making in avalanche risk management.

Summary of Results

The results of this study demonstrate that Support Vector Machines (SVMs) can effectively predict avalanche occurrences at a local scale, despite relying on relatively limited and partially incomplete datasets, especially in terms of snowpack structural information. The proposed approach provides an operational tool that could improve prediction compared to traditional human experience-based methods and provides interpretable outputs that reveal the relationships between key environmental variables in specific cases. These findings highlight the potential of machine learning to enhance local avalanche forecasting, supporting more transparent and informed decision-making for risk management in mountainous regions.

1.3 Motivations of the Thesis

The motivation behind this thesis arises from both personal and professional experiences, as well as a growing interest within the scientific community in the application of data-driven techniques to snow and avalanche forecasting.

Personal Interest

My passion for snow, backcountry skiing, and mountain safety has played a key role in the choice of this topic. Avalanches are among the most critical hazards to consider during winter excursions. This interest led me to attend professional training courses offered by AINEVA (Associazione Interregionale NEve e VALanghe), through which I obtained the necessary certifications to work in the field of avalanche safety.

Since 2019, I have been employed as an avalanche safety manager in the Pejo ski area. My responsibilities include daily data collection, artificial avalanche release, and decision-making regarding the opening and closure of ski slopes based on local avalanche conditions. This hands-on experience has revealed the aforementioned strengths and limitations of traditional avalanche forecasting methods, highlighting the need for more systematic, data-driven approaches.

Scientific and Practical Relevance

The use of machine learning models for avalanche forecasting is an emerging and increasingly relevant topic in snow and avalanche science. Recent studies reviewed in this thesis demonstrate that the integration of machine learning into operational practices is becoming more popular within the research community. These models provide a valuable connection between the physical characterization of snow and avalanche processes and their practical application in operational risk forecasting, potentially enhancing the effectiveness of operational forecasting processes.

Machine learning approaches are particularly well-suited for managing large, heterogeneous datasets and can provide insights in a domain characterized by high uncertainty. Such methods can help standardize decision-making, thereby reducing the influence of subjective human factors.

Potential Impact

The primary impact of this work lies in its operational applicability. Using data-driven methods has the potential to make avalanche forecasting more accurate, consistent, and responsive to real-time data. Furthermore, analyzing the interactions among various environmental characteristics through machine learning models can lead to new advances in snow science and deepen our understanding of the physical and meteorological processes involved in avalanche formation.

In summary, this thesis aims to contribute to both the scientific understanding and practical management of avalanche risk, promoting safer winter sports activities and more informed decision-making in mountain environments.

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is organized into seven chapters, each addressing a specific aspect of the research process, from context and motivation to methodological design, experimental validation, and final considerations.

Chapter 2 lays the theoretical foundation and defines the forecasting problem. It reviews the literature on traditional and modern forecasting techniques, describes the main meteorological and snowpack factors involved in avalanche formation, and highlights key limitations in current forecasting methods that motivate the use of machine learning approaches.

Chapter 3 describes the study area, providing environmental and socio-economic context, as well as justifying its selection. It details the available data sources, meteorological and snow conditions, and avalanche characteristics relevant to model development.

Chapter 4 presents the research methodology. It begins with a literature review on machine learning applications in avalanche prediction and then introduces Support Vector Machines (SVM) in detail. The chapter continues with the description of the modeling pipeline, including data preprocessing, feature engineering, hyperparameter tuning, model training, and interpretability considerations.

Chapter 5 focuses on the practical application of the methodology. It provides an in-depth analysis of the dataset, the process of feature engineering, handling class imbalance, and applying feature selection and extraction techniques.

Chapter 6 presents and discusses the results. It includes performance evaluation of the SVM models, analysis of uncertainty, and interpretation using tools like SHAP. The chapter also examines the robustness of the models on real-world data and provides critical reflections on strengths, limitations, and operational implications.

Chapter 7 concludes the thesis by summarizing the main findings and contributions. It outlines the practical implications for avalanche forecasting and suggests directions for future research to improve accuracy, transparency, and operational use of machine learning models in natural hazard prediction.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background and Problem Definition

2.1 Introduction to Avalanche Forecasting

2.1.1 Avalanche risk in Alpine areas

Avalanches are rapid and potentially destructive snow movements down a slope, typically occurring when destabilizing forces, such as gravity, snow accumulation, or external disturbances, overcome the internal strength of the snowpack. These events are especially frequent and hazardous in alpine regions, where steep terrain and significant snowfall converge. Avalanches may involve dry or wet snow and often entrain additional material such as rocks, ice, or vegetation, greatly increasing their destructive potential.

At the core of avalanche formation lies snowpack stability, a local property describing the snowpack's ability to resist collapse under stress. Instability arises when active forces (e.g., snowfall, wind loading, or warming) exceed the resisting forces (e.g., internal bonding, layer cohesion, friction with the slope). This balance is influenced by meteorological and nivological conditions, which modify both the load and structural integrity of the snowpack.

Several key weather-related variables affect this balance, such as snowfall rate, temperature gradients, wind, and radiation, but their detailed roles will be addressed in dedicated sections. It is the combined evolution of these parameters over time that determines snowpack layering and, consequently, its stability.

Avalanche risk represents a significant scientific and operational challenge, requiring the integration of disciplines such as meteorology, snow science, geophysics, and data-driven modeling. The impacts of avalanches are far-reaching, ranging from threats to human life and infrastructure to economic losses in key sectors such as tourism and transportation. In the context of a changing climate, marked by increasing variability in weather patterns and snow conditions, the need for reliable and timely forecasting tools is more urgent than ever. A deeper understanding of the physical and meteorological dynamics involved is essential for improving early warning systems and enhancing the safety of both recreational users and infrastructure in alpine regions.

The Pejo ski area, which serves as the focus of this study, is located in the Italian Alps and is particularly prone to avalanche activity due to its complex topography and meteorological exposure. Like much of the Alpine region, forecasting avalanches here is especially challenging, as it involves the interplay of diverse meteorological and topographic factors. This requires a detailed analysis of both weather and snowpack (nivological) variables to identify which local conditions most strongly influence avalanche release.

Moreover, despite the expertise of professional forecasters, the human factor continues to play a critical role in the accuracy of avalanche predictions. To support and enhance human decision-making, this study explores the use of machine learning models as complementary tools for local forecasting. Emphasis is placed on developing models that are not only accurate but also interpretable and operationally practical, so they can be trusted and effectively used by avalanche forecasters in real-time decision-making.

2.1.2 Operational goals in avalanche forecasting

Avalanche forecasting aims to anticipate snow avalanche occurrence in a specific region and time frame, providing timely and reliable information to reduce risk for people, infrastructure, and economic activities in mountainous areas. Operational avalanche forecasting, in particular, is practiced by national and regional authorities, and its outputs, such as daily bulletins, are used to inform decisions by mountaineers, ski resorts, transportation agencies, and civil protection services. Based on these general evaluations, ski resorts, transportation agencies, and civil protection authorities are responsible for translating regional forecasts into local-scale assessments. This involves taking context-specific safety measures and making timely operational decisions to protect people and infrastructure.

The main operational goals in regional avalanche forecasting include (European Avalanche Warning Services, 2018):

- **Integration of diverse data sources:** Combining meteorological forecasts, snowpack observations, remote sensing, and expert judgment to inform decision-making.
- **Risk classification:** Assigning a danger level (using the European Avalanche Danger Scale (European Avalanche Warning Services, 2018)) to a defined geographic area, typically based on snow stability, weather conditions, and snowpack evolution.
- **Interpretability and transparency:** Offering explanations and justifications for each forecasted danger level, including expected avalanche types, triggering conditions, and recommended precautions.
- **Spatial generalization:** Producing forecasts that cover entire regions (e.g., valleys or mountain chains), even though data are collected at a limited number of stations.
- **Timeliness and reliability:** Providing updated forecasts at daily intervals, even under conditions of limited data availability, while ensuring sufficient accuracy to support safety-related decisions.

While regional avalanche bulletins provide an essential overview, local-scale forecasting requires translating these assessments into actionable information for specific locations. The main operational goals at the local level include:

- **Use of site-specific data:** Integrating high-resolution meteorological and snowpack data from local weather stations, field observations, and avalanche control teams to improve forecast relevance and accuracy.
- **Localization of danger assessments:** Refining regional forecasts to account for local terrain features, microclimates, and snowpack variations, which can lead to significant deviations from the general danger level.
- **Operational simplicity and interpretability:** Delivering clear, concise, and practical outputs that can be quickly interpreted by non-experts, such as ski patrols or road operators, even under time pressure.
- **Real-time risk mitigation:** Supporting time-sensitive safety decisions, such as slope closures, traffic management, or controlled avalanche releases, particularly in high-risk areas like ski resorts, alpine roads, and inhabited zones.
- **Adaptability to evolving conditions:** Ensuring that the forecasting system can adapt to rapidly changing weather or snowpack situations and update recommendations accordingly.
- **Support for decision-making and communication:** Providing actionable, location-specific forecasts that inform the planning and communication of protective measures to the public and operational staff.

In this context, the adoption of machine learning (ML) models is emerging as a potential complement to traditional forecasting workflows. However, any ML model intended for operational use must meet several key requirements: high predictive performance (especially in the detection of avalanche events), robustness to

noisy or missing data, explainability for end users, and efficient deployment in real-time systems. This thesis explores whether a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model, trained on existing local nivo-meteorological data, can meet these operational standards.

2.2 Overview of Forecasting Approaches, a literature review

Avalanche forecasting methods have evolved significantly over the years, ranging from manual, heuristic-based techniques grounded in local expert knowledge and experience (Schweizer et al., 2003), to sophisticated data-driven models that leverage advances in computational power and statistical learning (McClung, 2023). Early forecasting relied heavily on empirical observations, field tests, and decision rules derived from expert intuition about snowpack behavior and weather patterns (Jamieson, 2006). As scientific understanding of snow mechanics and meteorology improved, physically-based models emerged to simulate the complex processes governing snowpack evolution (Lehning et al., 2002; Brun et al., 1992). More recently, the availability of large datasets and advances in machine learning have enabled the development of predictive algorithms, including support vector machines, random forests, and neural networks, which can capture nonlinear relationships and interactions among multiple variables (Bellaire et al., 2017; Mitterer and Schweizer, 2013; Viallon-Galinier, 2022; Pérez-Guillén et al., 2022). These data-driven models offer the potential to enhance forecast accuracy, automate predictions, and provide new insights, although challenges remain in terms of interpretability and operational integration (McClung, 2023). This section provides an overview of the main forecasting approaches, highlighting their historical development and key characteristics.

2.2.1 Traditional and Rule-Based Methods

Before the advent of data-driven and machine learning techniques, avalanche forecasting primarily relied on a combination of empirical methods, physically-based models, and local expert knowledge. These tools, grounded in scientific understanding and field experience, served as the foundational decision-support systems for managing avalanche risk in alpine environments.

In particular, local knowledge, derived from experience, topographic familiarity, and continuous monitoring of snowpack evolution, has historically played a crucial role. This knowledge is validated and structured through expert interpretation, often formalized in institutions such as local avalanche commissions. The organization and involvement of local experts, however, vary by region, with different systems in place to support municipal decision-making processes (Associazione Interregionale NEve e VALanghe, 2013).

Traditional methods include rule-based systems and decision-tree frameworks that rely on predefined thresholds of meteorological and snowpack variables (e.g., critical snowfall amounts, temperature gradients, or recent avalanche activity) to assess danger levels (Schweizer et al., 2003). These systems are appreciated for their transparency and interpretability, allowing forecasters to explain predictions and adapt their judgment based on evolving field conditions.

However, such methods can be rigid and difficult to scale across large or data-sparse regions. Their effectiveness is often tied to the forecaster’s expertise and consistency in applying rules, which introduces subjectivity and potential variability. As avalanche forecasting has grown in complexity, the limitations of purely rule-based approaches have led to the integration of more quantitative and automated systems.

2.2.2 Physically-Based Snowpack Models

Over the past two decades, physically-based models have become central to operational avalanche forecasting. These models simulate the thermodynamic and mechanical processes driving snowpack evolution, using meteorological inputs such as temperature, humidity, wind, solar radiation, and precipitation. Two of the most widely adopted models in this domain are:

- **SNOWPACK** (Lehning et al., 2002), developed by the WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF), which simulates snow stratigraphy with high vertical resolution and accounts for snow metamorphism and weak layer formation.
- **CROCUS** (Brun et al., 1992), developed by Météo France, which provides a similarly detailed vertical description of snowpack evolution and is used operationally in the French forecasting system.

SNOWPACK is integrated into the operational chain of the Swiss avalanche warning service (SLF), while CROCUS supports daily forecasts issued by Météo France. These models serve as powerful diagnostic tools for understanding internal snowpack structure and assessing stability under evolving weather conditions.

However, physically-based models typically operate at a point scale and struggle to capture lateral spatial variability due to terrain complexity and sparse input data (Lehning et al., 2002). Moreover, their reliance on high-quality meteorological and snowpack data, coupled with computational intensity, limits their applicability in real-time forecasting, especially in regions with limited observational infrastructure. These challenges have prompted growing interest in alternative modeling strategies, particularly empirical and machine learning approaches that can generalize across locations and operate with less domain-specific tuning.

Recent developments aim to overcome spatial limitations by coupling snowpack models with atmospheric weather prediction systems and integrating terrain-specific representations, thereby enhancing their regional applicability and resolution.

2.2.3 Empirical and Statistical Models

Empirical models offer an alternative to physically-based simulations by establishing statistical relationships between meteorological or snowpack variables and observed avalanche activity (McClung, 2023; Mitterer and Schweizer, 2013; Schweizer et al., 2003). Common techniques include linear regression, logistic regression, and binary or probabilistic classification methods, which aim to identify conditions under which avalanches are likely to occur based on historical patterns.

These models are valued for their simplicity, ease of implementation, and interpretability. These qualities make them especially suitable for operational avalanche forecasting, where decisions must be made quickly and transparently. In addition, empirical models often provide a reliable baseline or serve as a complementary tool within more complex forecasting systems, helping to highlight the most relevant predictive variables under specific climatic and topographic conditions (Van Herwijnen et al., 2023).

However, empirical models face important limitations. Their predictive power is highly dependent on the quality, quantity, and representativeness of the training data, which can hinder generalization across different regions or climate regimes. Additionally, they often struggle to capture the nonlinear and dynamic interactions that characterize avalanche formation, limiting their ability to model complex snowpack processes (McClung, 2023).

Despite these challenges, empirical models continue to play a valuable role in avalanche forecasting, particularly in regions with long-term datasets and operational needs that favor interpretability and responsiveness.

2.2.4 Machine Learning for Avalanche Prediction

Over the past two decades, machine learning (ML) has gained increasing attention in avalanche forecasting research, offering tools to capture the nonlinear and multi-scale relationships between snowpack conditions, meteorological variables, and avalanche occurrences. The literature demonstrates a growing range of ML methods applied to both national-scale and local-scale forecasting, each with specific strengths depending on data availability, geographic context, and operational needs.

Among the most widely used algorithms in avalanche studies are Random Forests (RF) and Decision Trees (DT), known for their ability to handle heterogeneous data and provide interpretable models. For example, Pérez-Guillén et al. (2022) employed RFs using snow and meteorological inputs from Météo-France’s forecasting system to predict danger levels in the French Alps, highlighting the role of wind and recent snowfall as primary predictors. Similarly, Hendrick et al. (2023) used tree-based models to support operational forecasting in Switzerland, emphasizing their value in exploring variable interactions and reducing forecast subjectivity.

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) have also proven effective, particularly for binary classification tasks such as distinguishing avalanche from non-avalanche days. Early applications include Pozdnoukhov et al. (2008), who applied SVMs to daily avalanche danger ratings in the Swiss Alps, achieving good results even with relatively limited training data. Součková et al. (2022) later demonstrated the use of Random Forest and Decision Trees for operational forecasting in the Czech mountains, underlining their robustness in small-sample regimes and their adaptability to local-scale prediction.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been applied to model more complex relationships, although their use is somewhat limited in the avalanche field due to interpretability challenges. Notably, Singh and Ganju (2008) developed an ANN-based system for forecasting avalanche probability in the Indian Himalayas, showing high classification accuracy but acknowledging the "black-box" nature of the model as a limiting factor for operational deployment.

Regarding data sources, most ML models in avalanche forecasting integrate meteorological data (e.g., snowfall, temperature, wind speed) with snowpack variables derived from physically based models like SNOWPACK and CROCUS, as in Kronholm (2006). More recently, reanalysis products like ERA5 have enabled larger-scale retrospective studies, often used as proxies when direct field measurements are sparse (Mayer et al., 2022). Some studies also incorporate manual observations from field experts, especially in localized applications where automatic station data are insufficient.

An important trend in recent literature is the move toward hybrid modeling approaches that combine physically based knowledge with ML algorithms. For instance, Viallon-Galinier (2022) proposes integrating model-derived snow stability indices with ML classification to improve reliability and consistency across spatial scales. This addresses a key operational requirement: balancing predictive accuracy with interpretability and transparency, especially important in decision-critical domains like avalanche warning.

Most existing work has focused on regional or national forecasting systems, such as those operated by France, Switzerland, or Canada. However, there is growing interest in local-scale applications, where ML is used to support expert decision-making in data-scarce environments. This study aligns with such efforts by applying SVMs to a localized, high-quality dataset in the Pejo ski area, demonstrating the potential of tailored models informed by site-specific meteorology and expert observations.

In summary, the literature supports the view that ML models, particularly SVMs and RFs, are valuable tools for avalanche forecasting. They are not replacements for expert judgment or physical models but act as complementary systems that can enhance understanding of key drivers, increase objectivity, and support reproducibility in forecasting workflows.

2.2.5 Gaps in the Literature and Research Motivation

While the literature on avalanche forecasting increasingly explores data-driven and machine learning methods, most existing studies focus on large-scale, national or regional implementations. These models benefit from extensive standardized datasets, but they often rely heavily on outputs from physically-based snowpack simulations and reanalysis products, which may not fully capture the variability and specificity of local snow conditions. Consequently, their generalizability and operational relevance in data-sparse or under-instrumented regions remain limited.

Another common challenge in avalanche-related ML applications is the interpretability of model predictions. Algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are often considered "black boxes," which hinders their practical adoption by forecasters who require transparent and explainable decision-support tools.

In response to these gaps, this thesis investigates the use of SVMs for binary avalanche prediction at a highly localized scale, focusing on the Val de la Mite within the Pejo ski area. Unlike most prior studies, this work uses a manually curated, high-certainty dataset collected over multiple winter seasons, emphasizing the value of local observational knowledge over model-derived estimates.

The study systematically evaluates the impact of different resampling techniques to address class imbalance, an inherent issue in avalanche datasets, and tests multiple feature configurations to identify the most relevant predictors. To further address the issue of model interpretability, SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values are employed to interpret SVM outputs, providing insights into the contribution of individual features to avalanche predictions.

By integrating a localized empirical dataset with interpretable machine learning methods and systematically evaluating class imbalance strategies, this thesis aims to advance the practical use of machine learning as an operational tool for local avalanche forecasting. These results fill an important gap in the literature by demonstrating that accurate and interpretable avalanche forecasts can be achieved even in highly localized areas with limited observational data.

2.3 Meteorological and Snowpack Drivers

2.3.1 Key Variables Influencing Avalanche Risk

Snow

Snow forms in the atmosphere through a physical process called nucleation, where water vapor transitions directly into ice by attaching to microscopic particles like dust or sea salt, known as ice nuclei (Pruppacher et al., 1998). This phase change occurs when the air is supersaturated with respect to ice and the temperature is sufficiently low. Due to the molecular polarity of water, the deposited molecules arrange themselves into a stable hexagonal crystalline structure (Libbrecht, 2005). Once the first ice crystal forms, it continues to grow through deposition, the direct accumulation of water vapor from the surrounding air. Growth is strongly influenced by temperature and humidity, which determine the final shape and size of the snow crystal.

The final shape of a snow crystal depends on both temperature and supersaturation, the latter being a measure of the moisture available for deposition. Differences in saturation vapor pressure between the tips and edges of the growing crystal promote branching (dendritic growth), leading to the classical six-armed snowflake shape.

Once it reaches the ground, snow becomes a porous material composed largely of air; freshly fallen snow can contain up to 90% air, and individual snow crystals (Fierz et al., 2009). By the end of the winter season, this air content typically decreases to around 40–50%. After deposition, snow crystals are referred to as snow grains, a term that reflects their transformation through physical processes on the ground (Fierz et al., 2009). This transformation is known as snow metamorphism and is primarily driven by temperature gradients within the snowpack. The classification of snow grains and their characteristics is detailed by Fierz et al. (2009) in the International Classification for Seasonal Snow on the Ground. Grains are grouped into the following macro-categories: precipitation particles (PP), decomposed and fragmented particles (DF), rounded grains (RG), faceted crystals (FC), surface hoar (SH), depth hoar (DH), and melt forms (MF). In the remainder of this text, we refer to this classification when naming grain types and relating their evolution to meteorological conditions.

Its behavior and evolution are governed by the principles of thermodynamics and mass conservation. The structural evolution of the snowpack over time depends primarily on its energy budget, the net balance between energy inputs (e.g., solar radiation, sensible and latent heat fluxes) and energy losses (e.g., longwave emission, conduction), and its mass balance, which reflects snow accumulation (from snowfall and wind transport) versus mass loss (due to sublimation, melting, or runoff).

Although seemingly simple, snowpack dynamics involves numerous complex and highly non-linear processes (Male and Granger, 1981). SNOWPACK (Lehning et al., 2002) and CROCUS (Brun et al., 1992) attempt to simulate the energy and mass balance of the snowpack to reproduce its physical behavior. However, these models still require some degree of parameterization due to the inherent complexity of the processes involved.

Snowfall has a direct and significant impact on avalanche activity (Schweizer et al., 2003; McClung, 2023). The additional load introduced by new snow can increase the overall stress on an existing snowpack, potentially triggering avalanches. The type and size of snow crystals also play a key role, as certain combinations may lead to weak bonding either at the interface between the fresh snow and the existing snowpack or within the new snow layer itself. A notable example is graupel (PPgp) (McClung, 2023), which often forms during intense precipitation events such as winter thunderstorms. These small, rounded snow pellets behave like spheres, easily rolling over one another and thereby creating sliding surfaces with low cohesion.

Both high total snowfall and high precipitation intensity (Schweizer et al., 2003) can contribute to snowpack instability, albeit through different mechanisms. In the first case, the additional mass increases gravitational loading, thereby elevating shear stress within the snowpack. In the second case, a high precipitation rate can destabilize the snowpack because the structure cannot adjust quickly enough to the rapid accumulation of weight. When this happens, existing bonds between snow grains may break under the stress, while new bonds in the fresh snow layer have not yet had time to form. This mismatch increases the risk of slab formation and potential avalanche release.

Another critical issue related to precipitation is rain-on-snow events McClung (2023). Rainfall introduces both mass and heat to the snowpack. The thermal input accelerates melting, and the resulting percolation of liquid water into the snowpack reduces cohesion and promotes the release of wet avalanches. Moreover,

the additional water mass further increases the load on the snowpack, compounding the risk.

Air temperature

Air temperature influences snow and, consequently, avalanche activity in several critical ways. It is one of the primary mechanisms through which energy is transferred to or from the snowpack. The temperature difference between the air and the snow surface drives sensible heat exchange, resulting in either warming or cooling of the snow, depending on the direction of the gradient. Temperature is therefore a key factor in both the metamorphism of snow and the initiation of avalanches (Colbeck, 1973; Schweizer et al., 2003).

A fundamental concept for understanding the internal dynamics of the snowpack is the thermal gradient (Colbeck, 1973; Schweizer et al., 2003), defined as the temperature difference between two vertical layers (typically from top to bottom) divided by the distance between them. Warm conditions promote rounding of snow grains, while cold conditions with strong gradients can promote faceting. When temperatures rise significantly, especially under strong solar radiation, the snowpack tends to undergo melting.

Diurnal temperature cycles, as well as the advection of warm or cold air masses, continuously modify the physical properties of the snow. These temperature-related processes influence grain structure, layer cohesion, and overall snow stability.

During the initial stages of seasonal melting, repeated cycles of melting and refreezing often lead to the formation of melt–freeze crusts. These crusts, which are dense ice layers within the snowpack, are particularly hazardous because they often form or overlay weak layers. Due to the difference in thermal conductivity between crust and surrounding snow, they can induce strong local thermal gradients, encouraging the development of weak layers such as depth hoar (McClung, 2023) both above and below the crust.

Temperature also plays a central role in the formation of wet avalanches. When parts of the snowpack begin to melt, a rapid increase in temperature can lead to a loss of cohesion in wet snow layers, triggering avalanches. These types of events are typically associated with late winter and spring (Mitterer and Schweizer, 2013; McClung, 2023), although they may become more common in winter (?), and are primarily driven by the presence and movement of liquid water within the snowpack.

The altitudinal temperature gradient, i.e., the decrease in temperature with increasing elevation, also affects the spatial distribution of avalanches. On average, temperature decreases by approximately 6.5°C per 1000 meters of elevation gain. However, this lapse rate can vary considerably depending on weather conditions. For instance, during overcast or precipitation events, the gradient is often small, while under Foehn wind conditions, it can exceed 10°C per 1000 meters. Orographic effects, boundary layer processes and latent heat release from moist air masses further modulate temperature profiles. From an avalanche forecasting perspective, this means that different types of avalanche problems may occur at different elevation bands, even under the same synoptic conditions, due to temperature alone (Schweizer et al., 2003).

Wind

Wind is another critical factor influencing avalanche formation and activity. It plays a dominant role in redistributing snow across the landscape, depending on both wind intensity and terrain topography. Snow is eroded from exposed areas, known as erosion zones, and deposited in deposition zones, typically on the lee sides of ridges and slopes (McClung, 2023).

The amount of snow transported by wind depends on several factors, particularly the wind speed and the type and cohesion of snow grains. Freshly fallen snow, characterized by weak intergranular bonds, is more susceptible to wind erosion, while older, well-settled snow tends to exhibit greater resistance due to sintering and increased mechanical stability (Pomeroy and Male, 1992; Lehning and Fierz, 2008). As snow undergoes metamorphism and bonding between grains strengthens over time, its threshold friction velocity increases, reducing its likelihood of being mobilized by wind.

Wind intensity directly controls the mode and extent of snow transport. Light winds generally cause minimal movement, primarily inducing rolling or creeping of snow grains on the surface. As wind speed increases, snow grains begin to saltate and become suspended in the air, enabling transport over larger distances. At very high wind speeds, typically above 80–100 km/h depending on environmental conditions, sublimation may occur, where suspended snow grains are converted directly into water vapor due to frictional heating and thermodynamic interactions with the surrounding air (Pomeroy and Male, 1992). These threshold values can vary with factors such as temperature, humidity, and snow properties.

A key effect of wind transport is a reduction in snow grain size. Precipitation particles, such as dendrites or stellar crystals, are broken down through mechanical abrasion into decomposed and fragmented. These finer grains are then compacted into dense layers, often forming wind slabs. These slabs, typically found in deposition zones, are characterized by their hardness and potential for failure and represent a major avalanche hazard (Schweizer et al., 2003; Lehning et al., 2008).

Topography has a profound effect on wind patterns in mountainous terrain. Although prevailing winds may have a dominant large-scale direction, local wind behavior is often highly variable and turbulent due to complex interactions with terrain (Mott and Lehning, 2010). This makes it difficult to predict snow redistribution and slab formation with precision, especially at the local scale. Identifying likely slab formation zones requires not only meteorological data but also detailed terrain knowledge and an understanding of local wind patterns.

In addition to snow transport, wind also acts as a source or sink of energy for the snowpack. The advection of cold or warm air, combined with turbulent mixing near the surface, can result in rapid changes in snow temperature. A notable example is the Foehn wind, where downslope flow leads to strong warming at lower elevations, rapidly increasing snow temperatures, and potentially destabilizing the snowpack (Lehning and Fierz, 2008).

Wind promotes turbulent exchange at the air–snow interface, influencing the direction and intensity of sensible and latent heat fluxes. This energy exchange depends on the thermal gradient between the air and the snow surface and plays a key role in snowpack evolution, particularly during weather transitions (McClung, 2023).

Radiation

The radiation balance is a fundamental component of the snowpack energy budget, governing its warming or cooling and thus influencing snow metamorphism. By comparing incoming and outgoing radiation, we can assess whether the snowpack is gaining or losing energy.

Snow responds differently to various wavelengths of radiation. The shortwave component, primarily from the Sun, is largely reflected by snow, especially when fresh. The albedo, the ratio of reflected to incoming shortwave radiation, ranges from approximately 90–95% for new snow, decreasing to 40–50% for aged or melting snow with large grains or surface impurities such as dust or soot (Warren, 1982). A higher albedo implies more energy reflected back into the atmosphere and therefore less warming of the snowpack.

Incoming shortwave radiation varies seasonally, mainly due to changes in solar angle and day length. Under clear skies, peak solar radiation around solar noon can reach values of approximately 300–400 W m⁻² in December, increasing to about 700–800 W m⁻² in March (European Commission – Joint Research Centre, 2025; ENEA, 2025). Cloud cover significantly reduces incoming solar radiation, limiting the energy available to warm the snowpack. Localized cloud development during the day can temporarily slow down snow moistening, delaying or preventing wet snow instability.

Avalanches triggered by solar radiation are predominantly wet avalanches. In late winter and spring, these events are common due to daytime warming of the upper snow layers, which increases liquid water content and leads to instability. This is why avalanche bulletins often advise scheduling activities early in the day, before the snowpack experiences significant warming and liquid water infiltration that increase instability. South-facing slopes are particularly prone to wet avalanches due to their higher exposure to solar energy.

Conversely, snow is more strongly affected by longwave (thermal infrared) radiation. Snow has a high emissivity, typically $\varepsilon \approx 0.95$ – 0.99 , making it behave almost like a blackbody (Dozier and Warren, 1982). This has two key consequences: (1) it absorbs nearly all incoming longwave radiation, and (2) it re-emits longwave radiation very efficiently.

The first effect implies that downwelling longwave radiation from the sky, especially from clouds, is fully absorbed by the snowpack, contributing to surface warming. The second effect means that snow emits thermal radiation at a high rate. For example, under clear-sky conditions, a snow surface at -10°C emits approximately 270 W m⁻², following the Stefan–Boltzmann law :

$$L_{\text{out}} = \varepsilon \sigma T_s^4.$$

This radiative loss is the main driver of nighttime cooling, particularly at the snow surface, while the snowpack base tends to remain near the ground temperature (around 0°C). It is common to observe surface snow temperatures several degrees lower than the air temperature during clear, calm nights.

The total radiation budget of the snowpack is therefore the result of both shortwave and longwave fluxes. High daytime solar input combined with nighttime cloud cover can enhance snowpack warming and moistening. In contrast, clear nights favor strong surface cooling. Under intermediate conditions, such as partial cloud cover, the snowpack response depends on which radiation component (SW or LW) dominates.

Typical spring weather, featuring clear days and clear nights, promotes melt–freeze cycles that lead to the formation of melt–freeze crusts (MF). As discussed previously, these crusts are relevant to snowpack stability, providing potential weak layers and smooth sliding surfaces for avalanches (Colbeck, 1973; Jamieson, 2006).

Relative Humidity

Relative humidity (RH) is an important atmospheric variable that directly affects snow metamorphism and the formation of surface crystals within the snowpack, with significant implications for snow stability and avalanche hazard (Colbeck, 1986; McClung, 2023).

High relative humidity near the snow surface promotes the growth of characteristic ice crystals, such as platelets or faceted grains, which can form weak layers in the snow profile (Colbeck, 1991; Schweizer et al., 2003). When RH approaches saturation, surface hoar (SH) can develop. These surface crystals tend to be large and poorly bonded, reducing cohesion between snow layers (McClung, 2023).

These fragile layers are particularly dangerous because they facilitate fracture initiation and propagation within the snowpack, increasing the likelihood of spontaneous or human-triggered avalanches (Schweizer et al., 2003; McClung, 2023). Conversely, low relative humidity favors sublimation and the transformation of snow into smaller, well-bonded grains, which generally enhances snowpack stability (Colbeck, 1986).

Moreover, RH interacts closely with temperature, influencing thermal metamorphism, the processes of crystal growth and recrystallization within the snowpack (Colbeck, 1986, 1991). Sudden changes in humidity and temperature can lead to the formation of weak layers or ice crusts, altering the internal balance and cohesion of the snowpack.

2.3.2 Snowpack Evolution and Metamorphism

The evolution of the snowpack strongly depends on the interaction of multiple factors, including meteorological conditions, topography, and local environmental characteristics. For instance, the interaction between snow and forest canopy remains one of the most relevant open research questions.

To highlight the complexity of snow evolution, we refer to the conceptual diagram developed for the SNOWPACK model (Fig. 2.1), which illustrates the main physical processes influencing snowpack development.

Figure 2.1: Physical processes in snow evolution (SLF, 2024.)

Snowpack evolution begins in the atmosphere, where the microphysical processes governing snow crystal formation are controlled primarily by temperature and supersaturation levels (Libbrecht, 2005). The initial crystal habit is determined by these thermodynamic conditions, while subsequent aggregation through collisions with other snowflakes and vapor deposition from supercooled cloud droplets further modify the crystal morphology, resulting in a range of regular or irregular structures.

Once deposited on the ground, snow crystals undergo metamorphic processes driven by the energy balance at the surface and gravitational compaction (Colbeck, 1986; Fierz et al., 2009). These processes tend to modify the original crystal structure toward a more thermodynamically stable configuration.

Snow grains, classified according to the standard system proposed by Fierz et al. (2009), continuously change their structure throughout the snow season in response to environmental conditions, specifically, the snowpack's energy balance. A key factor driving this metamorphic evolution is the temperature gradient within the snowpack, defined as the temperature difference between two points divided by their vertical distance. The magnitude and direction of this gradient determine the type of metamorphism that occurs, influencing both the mechanical stability and cohesion of the snow layers.

Constructive metamorphism

Constructive metamorphism, also referred to as kinetic growth metamorphism, occurs when a high temperature gradient exists in the snowpack, typically greater than 10°C per meter (Colbeck, 1986; Sturm and Benson, 1997). Such conditions often occur near the snow surface during clear, cold nights, where the surface rapidly cools while deeper layers remain warmer.

Water vapor migrates from warmer to colder regions, sublimating from concave or flat surfaces and depositing on convex ones such as crystal tips or edges. This directional vapor flux promotes the growth of angular, poorly bonded crystals such as faceted crystals (FC) and depth hoar (DH). These grains are weakly cohesive, forming persistent weak layers that greatly reduce snowpack stability and contribute to slab avalanche risk (Sturm and Benson, 1997).

Destructive metamorphism

Destructive metamorphism occurs under a low temperature gradient, typically less than 10°C per meter (Colbeck, 1986). These conditions are common in deeper snow layers or during periods of persistent cloud cover and minimal thermal contrast.

In this case, vapor sublimates from convex surfaces and deposits onto concave ones, reducing the curvature differences among grains. As a result, snow grains become more rounded and interlocked, increasing their bonding and cohesion (Fierz et al., 2009). This process gradually transforms the snow into a denser and more stable layer. Typical grains include decomposed fragments (DF) and rounded grains (RG).

Isothermal metamorphism

Isothermal metamorphism takes place when the snowpack is at or near 0°C, under uniform thermal conditions (Brun et al., 1989). This occurs during late spring or warm spells when surface melting causes liquid water to percolate through the snowpack.

During daytime melting, snow grains are partially dissolved, and as temperatures drop at night, the liquid refreezes, forming dense melt–freeze crusts (MF) or ice layers (IC). These cycles progressively round the grains and enhance bonding. While refreezing tends to strengthen the snowpack, excess water that cannot drain effectively can temporarily reduce cohesion, increasing the potential for wet snow avalanches.

Isothermal metamorphism plays a key role in spring avalanche dynamics, as the melt–freeze cycles can both stabilize the snowpack or, under saturation, create conditions for glide or wet slab avalanches (Brun et al., 1989).

2.4 Nivo-Meteorological Data Collection

2.4.1 Instruments and Observations

Accurate avalanche prediction relies on the analysis of various types of data. Depending on whether the forecast is for a local or regional scale, both the volume and diversity of data can increase significantly, adding complexity to the process (McClung, 2023). However, this complexity also allows forecasters to identify recurring patterns that can simplify and improve prediction accuracy (Lachapelle, 1980; Schweizer et al., 2003). Key data sources include automatic weather stations, manual snowpack observations, snow stability tests, reports of recent avalanche activity, insights from local experts, and numerical models (Canadian Avalanche Association, 2016; WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024). Each of these elements contributes valuable information for assessing avalanche risk and enhancing forecasting reliability (Bellaire and Jamieson, 2013).

Automatic Weather Station (AWS)

The analysis of current and past weather conditions is a fundamental step in avalanche forecasting (McClung, 2023; Schweizer et al., 2003). Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) operating in mountainous regions provide continuous recordings of key meteorological variables such as air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, precipitation, and snow depth; in some cases, they also measure solar radiation (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024). Data from these sensors are managed by a data logger, which compiles and transmits data strings to a central datacenter for archiving and visualization (Canadian Avalanche Association, 2016).

Most AWS are equipped with standard sensors, such as temperature and humidity probes, anemometers, tipping-bucket rain gauges, and ultrasonic snow depth sensors. Some advanced stations, like those in the Swiss IMIS (International Measurement and Information System) network, are fully equipped with high-end instruments (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024). These may include sensors for all four components of radiation, 3D ultrasonic anemometers for high-resolution wind field measurements, lidar-based snow depth sensors, and infrared thermometers for surface snow temperature monitoring (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024).

Technological advancements in AWS instrumentation contribute significantly to improving the physical representation of the snowpack in numerical models like SNOWPACK and CROCUS. However, the deployment and maintenance of AWS in mountain environments face serious challenges. Extreme cold, strong winds, snow drifts, thunderstorms, and lightning can damage the equipment. Moreover, network connectivity, often reliant on GSM or radio transmission, is frequently unstable or unavailable. In high alpine regions with heavy snowfall, solar-powered systems may not supply adequate energy, and maintenance becomes logistically difficult and dangerous for technicians (Mott et al., 2018).

As a result, missing data from the mountain AWSs is quite common. Imputing these gaps is particularly delicate, as the microclimates in which these stations operate are often highly localized and unique to their specific settings (Grunewald and Lehning, 2015).

Manual snow observations

In selected locations, manual observation sites are established to monitor the daily evolution of key meteorological and snowpack parameters, typically every morning (Canadian Avalanche Association, 2016; WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024; Cagnati, 2013). At these sites, simple meteorological data such as air temperature, snow height, cloud cover, visibility, and wind activity related to snow drift are recorded. Simultaneously, observers track changes in the snowpack by collecting information about its surface characteristics, temperature, and resistance (Cagnati, 2013). Avalanche activity in the surrounding area is also assessed (Schweizer et al., 2003).

Air temperatures are recorded using commercial analog or digital thermometers that log the minimum and maximum values over the previous 24 hours. Cloud cover, visibility, and wind activity are evaluated by expert observers who classify these conditions based on standardized criteria (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024). Snow height and new snowfall are measured with a graduated ruler. Snow surface resistance is assessed using a Ram Penetrometer, which applies a force of 1 N to the upper snow layer (Cagnati, 2013). The depth reached by the ram provides an estimate of the snowpack’s upper structure. Snow temperature is measured at depths of 10 cm and 30 cm to monitor temperature gradients within the snowpack.

All these data are recorded in tables and sent to the regional avalanche service office, where they are entered into a database (Associazione Interregionale NEve e VALanghe, 2013; Cagnati, 2013). Regional forecasters then compare data from multiple sites to develop their final avalanche bulletins (McClung, 2023).

One of the main advantages of this manual data collection method is its reliability in nearly all weather conditions. This approach provides a comprehensive, long-term database of avalanche-relevant information, with consistent methods that have remained largely unchanged for over 30 years. In contrast, Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) undergo frequent hardware and software updates, which can affect data consistency over time.

Snow profiles

Snow profiles involve analyzing the internal structure of the snowpack to identify the types and characteristics of snow grains present (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024; Fierz et al., 2009). These profiles can be conducted near Automatic Weather Stations (AWS), at manual observation sites, or ideally in representative locations close to avalanche-prone slopes (Schweizer and Wiesinger, 2001). This method is crucial for detecting weak layers within the snowpack, particularly in areas that most accurately reflect the conditions leading to avalanches.

Regularly conducting snow profiles (on average, every week or every 10 days) allows forecasters to track the snowpack’s evolution over time and recalibrate the “virtual stratigraphy” they maintain mentally during forecasting (Lachapelle, 1980).

The techniques for conducting snow profiles vary slightly depending on the methodology followed by different organizations. For example, AINEVA, SLF, and Meteo France begin by applying a ram with consistent force to test layer resistance and identify structural differences. After excavating the snow pit, they evaluate grain type, size, and hardness. Additionally, temperature measurements are taken every 10 cm to reconstruct the temperature profile within the snowpack and assess metamorphism (Cagnati, 2013; WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024; Fierz et al., 2009).

In contrast, the Austrian Avalanche Warning Service uses a faster, more results-oriented method. They first dig the trench, immediately perform a stability test to locate weak layers, and then identify grain types using a magnifying lens and a black background board.

Recently, a special probe has been introduced that can measure resistance and infrared temperature simultaneously, allowing for instantaneous snow profile assessments by simply inserting it into the snow (Bellaire et al., 2017).

Stratigraphic analysis is essential for identifying weak layers within the snowpack. However, choosing a representative location for digging a snow pit is a complex task that requires time, experience, and expert

knowledge of the terrain and avalanche behavior. The suitability of the site can only be confirmed after completing the snow profile. If the site does not accurately reflect the local snow conditions, there is a high risk of misinterpreting the data, which can lead to incorrect conclusions about avalanche risk. Therefore, expertise and familiarity with the area are critical for selecting the most appropriate spot for snow profiling.

Stability tests

Stability tests may be performed alongside snow profiles or independently for spatial coverage (Schweizer and Bruce Jamieson, 2010). Common operational methods include:

- **Column Test (CT)**: is designed to evaluate the strength and stability of a weak layer within the snowpack. In this test, a column of snow approximately 30 by 30 centimeters is isolated, and progressively stronger taps are applied to the top surface using a hammer to induce failure in the weak layer. The ease with which the column fractures indicates the local stability of the snow, and the force required to cause failure is recorded. While this test is quick and simple to perform and useful for detecting weak layers, it does not reliably predict whether fractures will propagate (Canadian Avalanche Association, 2016).
- **Extended Column Test (ECT)**: builds upon the CT by assessing not only the strength of the weak layer but also the potential for fracture propagation. In the ECT, a wider column, typically around 30 by 90 centimeters, is isolated. Taps are applied progressively to observe if a fracture propagates along the entire length of the column. The presence of full-length fracture propagation suggests a higher risk of avalanches caused by propagating failures. This test provides more relevant information regarding avalanche release potential compared to the CT (Simenhois and Birkeland, 2009).
- **Rutschblock (RB)**: This test checks how stable a snow slab is on a slope by adding weight step by step. A large block of snow, about 2 by 1.5 meters, is cut out. The tester stands on it first, then adds more force by jumping or other movements until the block slides or breaks. How easily the block fails shows how stable the slope is. The RB test takes more time and skill to do but gives a good, realistic idea of how the slope might behave (Schweizer and Wiesinger, 2001).
- **Propagating Saw Failure Test (PST)** is a more recent and advanced method used to evaluate the tendency of fractures to propagate within a weak snow layer. In this test, a snow column is isolated, and a specialized saw or blade is used to initiate and propagate a fracture along the weak layer. The resistance and energy required for propagation are measured. The PST provides detailed information on fracture mechanics that are closely linked to avalanche risk, offering a more precise assessment of the potential for fracture propagation within the snowpack (Gauthier and Jamieson, 2006).

Combining the results of multiple tests and comparing them with existing studies helps assess snowpack stability (Schweizer and Bruce Jamieson, 2010).

Instability signals

During outdoor activities in avalanche-prone areas, it is crucial to pay close attention to signs that may indicate unstable snow conditions. These instability signals, observed either directly or reported by others, serve as valuable empirical data for avalanche forecasting. They are observations of snow behavior that have been correlated with avalanche occurrence (Schweizer et al., 2003; Canadian Avalanche Association, 2016).

The most important instability signal is recent avalanche activity. By analyzing the location, size, characteristics, and frequency of recent avalanches, forecasters can identify conditions that are likely to lead to similar events. This information forms the foundation of avalanche danger assessments and is typically included in official avalanche bulletins.

Skiers and other backcountry travelers should also be alert to signs such as cracking sounds in the snow and the distinct “whoomph” noise. Cracking indicates the presence of a slab layer capable of fracture propagation, while the “whoomph” sound signals the sudden collapse of a weak layer beneath the snowpack (McClung, 2023). When gravitational forces are sufficient, these factors can lead to human-triggered avalanches.

Another important localized hazard is cornices, overhanging snow formations created by wind. Large cornices can collapse due to increased stress or additional loading, potentially triggering avalanches on slopes

below. Conversely, walking on cornices is highly dangerous because, although they are composed of wind-deposited, cohesive snow crystals, it is difficult to know how much force is needed to break them (WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research SLF, 2024).

To improve avalanche prediction, some mountain guide associations and professional forecasters have initiated collaborative efforts to systematically collect and share observations of these instability signs.

Numerical models

Numerical models serve as essential tools for supporting avalanche forecasting by simulating the stratigraphy and physical evolution of the snowpack. Among the most widely used models for operational forecasting are SNOWPACK (Lehning et al., 2002), developed by the WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF) in Switzerland, and CROCUS (Brun et al., 1992), developed by Météo-France. Both models solve the coupled energy and mass balance equations to simulate the temporal evolution of snow layers, using meteorological input data from fully equipped Automatic Weather Stations (AWS).

Traditionally, the reliability of these models has depended heavily on the availability and quality of local AWS data. However, to address the challenge of sparse or missing station data, recent advancements have incorporated satellite remote sensing and numerical weather prediction (NWP) models as alternative or supplementary input sources (Morin et al., 2020; Quéno et al., 2020). This has enabled the generation of spatially distributed snowpack simulations, providing gridded virtual snow profiles over complex terrain and broader regions.

To further improve regional avalanche hazard assessment, a machine learning-based framework named AWSOME (Automatic WEather and Snowpack Observation-based Machine learning Estimator) was developed. AWSOME integrates simulated snowpack features from SNOWPACK with historical avalanche data and expert labels to classify regional snow stability levels (Herla et al., 2024). This approach represents a promising direction toward automating and enhancing regional-scale avalanche danger mapping with quantitative, data-driven methods.

Official data provider in Italy

In Italy, avalanche forecasting is supported by a network of official institutions operating at both national and regional levels. The most prominent among these are AINEVA (Associazione Interregionale di Coordinamento e Documentazione per i Problemi della Neve e delle Valanghe), the regional avalanche services (which are members of AINEVA), as well as the Meteomont network operated by the Italian Army and the Carabinieri Forestali. These organizations are responsible for collecting snow and meteorological data, performing stability analyses, and issuing official avalanche bulletins to the public (Associazione Interregionale NEve e VALanghe, 2025; Comando Carabinieri – Ufficio Meteomont, 2025; Comando Truppe Alpine Esercito Italiano – Servizio Meteomont, 2025).

At the local scale, Local Avalanche Commissions (Commissioni Valanghe Locali) support municipalities in managing avalanche risk in critical areas. Furthermore, local avalanche experts, particularly those working within ski resorts, are tasked with evaluating and mitigating avalanche danger for resort operations and visitor safety.

A two-way communication structure is in place: regional services provide technical support and meteorological data to local authorities, while local experts contribute field-based observations such as snow profiles, daily stability tests, and records of avalanche activity. These data are integrated into regional forecasting workflows.

This collaborative system enhances the identification of local avalanche problems, refines regional-scale assessments, and supports more effective risk management and protection strategies for the population.

2.4.2 Avalanche Classification and Forecasting Challenges

Understanding the characteristics of avalanches, when, where, and under which conditions they form, is essential for accurate forecasting. For effective communication and operational risk management, it is equally important to standardize terminology. Misunderstandings caused by inconsistent language can lead to poor decision-making and increased risk.

In this section, we briefly introduce the most important avalanche terminology, based on the standards defined by the European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS) (European Avalanche Warning Services, 2018), and summarize the fundamental physical principles behind avalanche formation.

Avalanches occur when the delicate balance between the resistance of the snowpack, determined by the bonding and friction between snow grains, and the external stress applied to it (such as snow accumulation, a skier’s weight) is disrupted. When the applied tension exceeds the internal resistance, the snowpack becomes unstable, and an avalanche can be triggered.

Among the different types of avalanches, two are particularly important to distinguish due to their different dynamics and forecasting implications:

- **Loose snow avalanches** initiate at a single point when cohesion between surface snow crystals fails, often due to new snow, radiation, or temperature increase.
- **Slab avalanches** involve a cohesive snow layer sliding over a weaker layer. These are more dangerous due to the potential for wide fracture propagation and large volumes of snow involved.

Avalanches are classified based on several parameters (European Avalanche Warning Services, 2022). Regarding the release mechanism, they can be divided into loose snow avalanches, which typically have a pear-shaped release zone, and slab avalanches, characterized by a long, planar fracture. Considering the depth of the sliding surface, avalanches may start within a specific snowpack layer, at the surface, or involve the entire snowpack down to the ground. Based on snow type, dry or wet, which strongly influence avalanche dynamics, the combination of snow type and morphology results in two main avalanche types: powder avalanches, distinguished by a spectacular airborne cloud of snow, and dense avalanches, which flow closely along the ground. Avalanches are also classified by terrain characteristics, differentiating between those that run on open slopes and those confined to channels. Throughout their movement, avalanches exhibit varying physical properties such as velocity and density, which change dynamically and affect their interaction with surrounding elements like terrain, vegetation, structures, and people.

To aid forecasting and public communication, the European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS) have identified five typical avalanche problems, each with specific causes and risk profiles:

- **New Snow:** Increased load from recent snowfall can reduce snowpack stability, especially if graupel or intense precipitation is involved.
- **Wind Slab:** Wind transports and compacts snow into dense slabs prone to sudden release, often above weak layers.
- **Persistent Weak Layer:** Weak layers (e.g., faceted crystals, surface hoar) buried deep in the snowpack can remain unstable for weeks, posing a hidden danger.
- **Wet Snow:** Rain or melting leads to water infiltration, reducing cohesion and triggering wet slab or loose avalanches, usually naturally.
- **Gliding Snow:** Entire snowpack slides over the ground, often unpredictably, due to low friction at the snow-soil interface.

Understanding these mechanisms is essential for assessing the weather conditions that lead to avalanche release, and for identifying the most strategic parameters and observations that support accurate avalanche forecasting.

In this study, we focus on loose snow avalanches, which are more directly influenced by surface conditions and meteorological variables, and thus more suitable for data-driven prediction approaches.

2.4.3 Managing Data for Effective Avalanche Forecasting

Avalanche forecasting, a historical overview

Avalanche risk has long been a significant issue for alpine communities. In pre-modern times, catastrophic avalanche events were documented in religious and civil archives and often commemorated with crosses

and paintings in churches (Ancey, 2007). During the First World War, especially in the Alpine regions, systematic observations of avalanches were conducted for military and logistical purposes. Photographs and written reports, such as letters and diaries, were used to document and monitor avalanche activity.

Subsequently, specialized institutions were established to manage avalanche risk through scientific approaches. Among the most important are SLF in Switzerland, Météo-France, and AINEVA in Italy, founded between the 1940s and 1980s to standardize data collection and train snow observers and specialized technicians (Cagnati, 2013).

The development of winter tourism further accelerated the adoption of forecasting and risk management tools, including the creation of observation networks in ski resorts and the dissemination of avalanche bulletins (Maggioni and Gruber, 2003).

Today, avalanche risk forecasting integrates meteorological data, field observations, and physical and statistical models. The recent operational introduction of artificial intelligence by SLF during the 2023–2024 winter season represents a significant advancement in improving forecast accuracy (Pérez-Guillén et al., 2022; Hendrick et al., 2023).

Forecasting workflow

Understanding how an avalanche forecast is developed is essential to grasp both the power and limitations of the avalanche bulletin. Depending on the scale of application, forecasts can be regional, issued by national or regional avalanche centers, or local, produced by local experts for the practical management of ski resorts, municipal areas, road networks, or critical infrastructure such as power lines and mountain huts.

Both regional and local forecasts rely on the analysis of nivo-meteorological conditions. Key sources of data include meteorological information from Automatic Weather Stations (AWS), manual observations collected at snow observation sites, and numerical weather forecasts for upcoming days. By tracking the evolution of weather conditions throughout the winter season, forecasters begin to develop a mental model of the snowpack, identifying possible critical layers and anticipating dangerous configurations.

The second step involves validating the conceptual model using both direct and indirect observations. Snow stratigraphy data collected from representative sites enable forecasters to identify weak layers and evaluate the structure of the snowpack. Additionally, physically-based models like SNOWPACK (Lehning et al., 2002) and CROCUS (Brun et al., 1992) simulate snowpack stratigraphy, serving as valuable support tools. These models accurately reproduce the layering within the snowpack, helping forecasters gain deeper insight into the physical processes that lead to instability.

In addition to structural analysis, assessing the stability of the snowpack is essential. The results of stability tests, along with their location, provide critical information about the likelihood of triggering avalanches.

This aspect becomes particularly important in local forecasting, where instability signs, such as recent avalanche activity, cracks, or "whumpf" sounds, are given significant weight. When making decisions such as closing a ski slope or an entire ski area, relying on clear, observable signs of instability is crucial to ensure safety and avoid unnecessary risk.

Results from these tests, combined with field observations and model outputs, are interpreted in light of current scientific understanding (Schweizer et al., 2003).

The avalanche danger level is determined using a standardized procedure developed by the European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS, 2022). The process includes seven key steps:

- **Identify Avalanche Problems:** Determine which of the recognized avalanche problems (e.g., wind-drifted snow, new snow, persistent weak layers) are present. If no problems are identified, the danger level is 1 – Low.
- **Define Location and Timing:** For each problem, specify where (altitude and aspect) and when (time of day) it is expected to occur.
- **Assess Snowpack Stability:** Estimate how easily an avalanche can be triggered under the current conditions (e.g., poor, fair, good stability).
- **Determine Trigger Frequency:** Evaluate how widespread the critical weak points are, ranging from isolated to widespread areas.

- **Estimate Avalanche Size:** Assess the potential maximum size of avalanches, from small (size 1) to very large or catastrophic (size 5).
- **Use the EAWS Matrix:** Combine the results of steps 3–5 using the EAWS matrix to determine the corresponding danger level for each problem.
- **Select the Final Danger Level:** If more than one avalanche problem is present, the highest danger level identified is taken as the final forecast level.

This multi-step process, grounded in both physical science and expert judgment, makes avalanche forecasting a complex yet essential tool for public safety and mountain risk management.

Chapter 3

Study Area

The focus of this study is the Pejo Ski Area, located in a tourist village within Val di Peio, a side valley of Val di Sole in the northwestern part of the Autonomous Province of Trento, northern Italy. This entire region is situated within the protected boundaries of Stelvio National Park.

Due to the park's conservation status, it was essential to implement avalanche risk mitigation measures to minimize environmental impact, especially in the upper portion of the ski area. As a result, extensive use of traditional protective structures like dams, avalanche barriers, nets, and fixed blasting systems (Gazex) was avoided. This situation required the development of alternative management strategies specifically designed to meet these constraints.

The ski area encompasses the watersheds of Rio Vioz, Rio Taviela, and the upper section of Rio Marassina, covering approximately 15 km². Geographically, it extends between latitudes 46.351° and 46.402° N and longitudes 10.606° to 10.677° E (WGS 84).

The ski slopes descend from the highest point at Crozi Taviela (3000 meters above sea level) down to the village of Peio Fonti (1400 meters a.s.l.), surrounded by peaks rising above 3600 meters.

Figure 3.1 illustrates the study area boundaries highlighted in red, alongside the ski slopes and lifts. The map also features avalanche hazard zones classified by the Autonomous Province of Trento (Provincia Autonoma di Trento, 2023), following a European standard based on return periods and impact pressures on structures. Additionally, the locations of current and former weather stations and snow observation sites are shown.

The avalanche hazard classification incorporates historical avalanche data and estimates hazard zones based on return periods, represented by red, blue, and yellow colors. The avalanche paths correspond with the watershed of Rio Taviela, where avalanches can reach the base of Val Taviela near the Mezoli area at 1,400 meters a.s.l., and the watershed of Rio Vioz, where avalanches stop at the 'Vasche di Blockhaus' zone at the end of Val de la Mite.

This watershed is further divided into three subsections: to the left, the Saline Glacier with Punta Taviela (3612 m); in the center, Col del Vioz (3301 m), a pass leading to the Forni Glacier; and to the right, the ridge surrounding Monte Vioz (3645 m), which includes the Pala del Vioz Glacier.

Figure 3.1: Study area overview: boundaries, ski infrastructure, avalanche hazard maps, and meteorological sites

3.1 Rationale for Study Area Selection

The Pejo Ski Area was chosen as the focus of this study because it offers a unique combination of scientific relevance, practical importance, and contextual suitability that aligns well with the research objectives.

First and foremost, the area presents a complex avalanche-prone alpine environment, characterized by steep terrain, diverse slope aspects, and significant elevation gradients ranging from approximately 1400 m to 3000 m a.s.l. These geomorphological characteristics make it an ideal natural laboratory for studying snow dynamics and avalanche risk in high mountain settings. The presence of both natural triggers and anthropogenic influences, such as ski infrastructure and human activity, provides opportunities to analyze different types of avalanche scenarios.

Secondly, the Pejo Ski Area is located within the Stelvio National Park, a protected area that combines conservation with controlled tourism development. This dual character raises important questions regarding sustainable land use, hazard mitigation, and environmental protection, all of which are key elements of the research.

Another critical factor in selecting this area is the availability and quality of data. The ski area is covered by a comprehensive avalanche risk management plan (Barberi, 2017), which includes historical avalanche records, snowpack observations, meteorological data, and detailed hazard mapping provided by the Autonomous Province of Trento. Several meteorological and snow observation stations, both currently active and historically available, offer valuable time series data for model validation and analysis.

Moreover, the area has seen a number of documented avalanche events in recent decades, providing real-world case studies to support both the theoretical and applied components of this research. The presence of vulnerable elements such as ski lifts, slopes, and populated facilities further underscores the importance of effective avalanche forecasting and risk mitigation.

In summary, the Pejo Ski Area combines environmental complexity, practical relevance, and data availability, making it a uniquely suitable case study for investigating snow-related hazards and improving local avalanche risk management strategies.

3.2 Environmental Characteristics

3.2.1 Climatology

The valley experiences a typical alpine climate of the southern Central Alps, characterized by cold winters and cool summers. Due to its geographic position, the area is relatively dry, particularly during the winter months. Precipitation primarily originates from the south or southwest, often when a low-pressure system is positioned over the Gulf of Genoa. Weather systems from other directions are largely blocked by the Alps. Strong Föhn winds, dry, warm downslope winds, are frequently observed during winter.

Local temperature and precipitation patterns are strongly influenced by altitude, slope exposure, valley confluences, and proximity to mountain passes.

Data from the Pejo weather station (1574 m a.s.l.), operational since 1986, indicate an average annual temperature of 6.8 °C. The coldest months, January and February, average around 0.5 °C, while July and August are the warmest, with mean temperatures near 15.2 °C. The area experiences notable annual and diurnal temperature variations, with frequent late spring frosts (May–June) and early autumn frosts (September–October) that pose risks to vegetation (Barberi, 2017).

Average annual precipitation, recorded between 1920 and 2002, is approximately 986 mm, with peaks in autumn and spring. August also receives moderate precipitation, though less than the main peaks. Snowfall mainly occurs between November and March, with maximum accumulation in late autumn and March; January and February often have limited snowfall. Above 1800 m a.s.l., significant snowfall can also occur in April and May (Barberi, 2017).

Wind patterns vary seasonally: prevailing winds come from the west and southwest during spring and autumn, while sporadic southeast winds occur in summer and can occasionally be strong. In winter, northerly winds linked to the Föhn phenomenon bring warm, dry air descending into the valley, while colder, stronger northerly winds affect higher mountain elevations. This contrast notably influences local weather and snow conditions (Barberi, 2017).

3.2.2 Topography

The topography of the area is characteristic of high Alpine environments, with surrounding peaks reaching elevations of 3600–3700 m a.s.l. The upper elevations are marked by steep slopes, rugged peaks, gullies, and generally inaccessible terrain. The landscape has been heavily shaped by glacial activity, which has carved out U-shaped valleys and deposited lateral moraines. Evidence of past glacial deposition is visible in several flat areas at the outlet of Val de la Mite, such as Vasche di Blockhaus, Doss dei Cembri, and Piani del Vioz—as well as in the Covell plain further downslope.

In contrast, Val Taviela features both glacial landforms and active fluvial processes. In this valley, a small stream, fed by the Taviela Glacier, flows through a narrow, carved channel. The outlet of this gully, located in the Mezoli area, an area historically affected by avalanche events, is primarily composed of debris flow deposits transported by the Rio Taviela.

Figure 3.2: Slope map (left) and aspect map (right) derived from 10m DTM

In Figure 3.2, we present the slope (left panel) and aspect (right panel) of the study area. The slope map is color-coded from blue to red, highlighting steeper areas where the probability of avalanche release is higher, typically between 28° and 65° , as well established in the literature (among others: McClung (2023)). The aspect map shows the orientation of slopes relative to the sun. A notable concentration of south- and southwest-facing slopes is observed, which corresponds with areas where several naturally triggered avalanches discussed in this study have occurred.

3.2.3 Vegetation

From a vegetation perspective, the upper elevations, above 2500–2700 m a.s.l., are largely barren or sparsely vegetated, with only isolated patches of hardy grasses present on sun-exposed slopes. In transitional zones, grassland species dominate, among which falasco (a long-stemmed grass species) is commonly found in meadows and moisture-rich areas. Shrub vegetation is primarily composed of rhododendrons (*Rhododendron* spp.), which are widespread in the subalpine belt and play a crucial role in slope stabilization. These shrubs can also contribute to avalanche dynamics by altering snowpack structure and anchorage.

Trees begin to appear below approximately 2300 m a.s.l.. In the upper subalpine forest, *Pinus cembra* (Swiss stone pine) and *Larix decidua* (European larch) are the dominant species. At lower elevations, *Larix decidua* becomes increasingly abundant, and coniferous species such as *Picea abies* (Norway spruce) and *Abies alba* (silver fir), as well as some broadleaf deciduous trees, are also present.

3.2.4 Avalanches

From an avalanche perspective, the highest zones, characterized by rocky terrain and steep alpine faces, are prone to large avalanches, particularly during periods of significant snow accumulation and strong wind transport. In the intermediate zone, where grasses and shrubs dominate, springtime wet snow avalanches are more common, often occurring on very steep slopes. In the lower part of the study area, avalanche occurrence is relatively rare; the presence of mature, well-structured forest stands often indicates a low probability of medium- to large-scale avalanche activity.

3.3 Socio-economic Overview

The municipality of Peio is a small alpine community located in the Trentino region, within the Stelvio National Park. It has a sparse population, typical of high mountain areas. The local economy heavily relies on tourism, particularly focused around the Pejo Ski Area, which offers skiing in winter and trekking, nature exploration, and mountain climbing in the summer. Other economic activities include thermal tourism, small-scale agriculture, livestock farming, hydroelectric production, and forest management.

The Pejo Ski Area represents a critical economic resource for the region, attracting both national and international visitors. It includes a network of six lifts, about 20 km of ski slopes, and related infrastructure ranging in elevation from approximately 1400 m at Peio Fonti to 3000 m at Crozi Taviela. The ski resort is also integrated into broader year-round eco-tourism strategies thanks to its location within a protected natural area.

However, the development and operation of the ski area pose several environmental challenges, particularly in relation to avalanche risk. Many ski slopes and lift lines pass through or near areas identified as avalanche-prone zones, based on historical data and geomorphological assessments. Natural avalanche events have previously affected access routes, infrastructure, and in some cases, necessitated the temporary closure of ski runs.

To mitigate these risks, the ski area follows a comprehensive avalanche risk management plan (Barberi, 2017). This plan includes monitoring snow and weather conditions and, at times, with opening and closing the ski slopes procedures. Artificial protection structures, such as snow fences and nets, are installed only to safeguard ski lifts. Additionally, controlled avalanche triggering using helicopters (Daysibell) is reserved for very critical situations and requires authorization from the National Stelvio Park. These measures are essential to ensure the safety of visitors and maintain the economic viability of the ski resort.

3.4 Data availability

In the study area, various sources of meteorological and nivological data are available, offering valuable insights into local climate and snow dynamics. Several automatic weather stations (AWS), installed over the past 20 years, operate at different elevations and provide continuous measurements of key atmospheric variables.

Complementing these, there is an official snow observation site, active since 1980, which provides one of the longest and most consistent records in the region.

Starting in the early 2000s, the monitoring of avalanche activity also became more structured. This shift was driven in part by the development of the Piano Unitario per la Difesa dal Pericolo Valanghe (Barberi, 2017), which aimed to improve avalanche hazard assessment and territorial planning.

Automatic Weather Stations : AWSs are located within a 10 km radius, distributed across different altitudes. These stations capture the distinct meteorological characteristics of the specific locations where they are installed.

The first AWSs were deployed in the early 1990s. Since then, additional stations have been installed, while older ones have been either decommissioned or upgraded. As a result of this progressive development, the stations differ in terms of installed sensors, measured parameters, and data sampling strategies, which were adapted over time to meet the operational forecasting needs of different historical periods.

In the table below, we present the available AWS along with their geographic coordinates, the start and the end dates of data collection, and the recorded parameters.

ID	Station	Lat.	Lon.	Elev.	Start	End	Param.
<i>T0063</i>	Pian Palu (Diga)	46.3366	10.6139	1800	05/12/1991	09/10/2023	P, Ta
<i>T0064</i>	Peio	46.3640	10.6757	1565	18/07/1985	14/12/2007	P, Ta

<i>T0065</i>	Careser (Diga)	46.4226	10.6991	2600	21/12/1990	---	P, Ta, RH, WD, WV
<i>T0066</i>	Cima Cavaion	46.4230	10.7150	2895	09/10/2018	---	P, Ta, RH, WD, WV, Patm
<i>T0068</i>	Cogolo Pont (Centrale)	46.3650	10.6889	1190	18/11/1991	28/08/2014	P, Ta
<i>T0308</i>	Careser Alla Baia	46.4308	10.7066	2635	13/04/2012	---	Ta
<i>T0366</i>	Peio	46.3644	10.6778	1585	17/05/2002	---	P, Ta, RH, WD, WV, Patm, SR
<i>T0372</i>	Peio (Crozzi Taviela)	46.3842	10.6320	2960	22/09/2002	---	Ta, RH, WD, WV, Patm, SR
<i>T0380</i>	Pian Palu (Malga Giumella)	46.3409	10.6126	1945	18/10/2011	---	P, Ta
<i>T0473</i>	Ghiacciaio Del Careser	46.4513	10.7183	3093	02/09/2011	---	Ta, RH, WD, WV, Patm
<i>IT-32- TN-19</i>	Peio Doss dei Cembri	46.3799	10.6596	2300	01/01/2004	---	P, Ta, RH, WV, WD, Ts, HS

Table 3.1: Metadata of automatic weather stations in the Pejo area: location, operational period, and available meteorological parameters

In Table 3.1, we report the meteorological and nivological parameters collected by the automatic weather stations (AWS) in the study area. It is important to note that not all parameters were recorded throughout the entire operational period of each station. The table includes all parameters that were measured for at least one winter season.

The available parameters are:

- **P:** Accumulated Precipitation
- **Ta:** Air Temperature
- **RH:** Relative Humidity
- **WD:** Wind Direction
- **WV:** Wind Velocity
- **Patm:** Atmospheric Pressure
- **SR:** Solar Radiation
- **HS:** Snow Height
- **Ts:** Snow Temperature

The sampling interval varies between stations, variables, and time periods, ranging from 5 minutes up to 3 hours. Depending on the parameter, different aggregation methods are used: accumulated values for precipitation (e.g., **P**), average values for temperature and relative humidity (e.g., **Ta**, **RH**), and discrete measurements for snow depth (e.g., **HS**).

Two automatic weather stations (AWS) within the ski area are particularly important for avalanche forecasting. The first is located at approximately 3000 m a.s.l. in the upper Val de la Mite near Crozzi

Taviela, just a few meters from the top station of the Pejo 3000 Funifor lift. The second station is situated at 2300 m a.s.l., close to the top station of the Doss dei Cembri chairlift, only a few hundred meters from the runout zone of Val de la Mite.

These two stations provide critical data for monitoring snowpack and meteorological conditions in key areas of the resort and support real-time avalanche risk assessment when data are available.

Snow Observation Site The snow observation site 1PEI Pejo Tarlenta is situated in the central area of the ski resort at an elevation of approximately 2000 m a.s.l., near Rifugio Scoiattolo. This site constitutes a valuable historical archive, having been operational since December 1980. Over the past 45 years, it has continuously collected both meteorological and nivological data and remains active to this day.

ID	Station	Lat.	Lon.	Elev.	Start	End	Param.
1PEI	Pejo Tarlenta	46.3704	10.6627	1985	20/12/1980	—	Meteo, Snow, Avalanches

Table 3.2: Metadata of the Pejo Tarlenta snow observation site: location, operational period, and collected data types

Daily observations are carried out throughout the winter season by trained personnel from Pejo Funivie, and weekly snow profiles are done by the Forestry Corps of the Autonomous Province of Trento. The data are collected following standardized procedures (Cagnati, 2013), ensuring high consistency and comparability over time. In addition to point measurements, observations encompass the entire ski area, allowing for systematic documentation and classification of all avalanche events occurring in the region.

A detailed description of the measured parameters and observation protocols is provided in the following chapters.

The relevance of the 1PEI Pejo Tarlenta site for avalanche forecasting lies in:

- its long-term, continuous data series, with minimal data gaps;
- the standardized data collection methodology, unchanged since 1995;
- the integrated monitoring of both meteorological and snowpack variables, including direct avalanche observations.

This unique combination makes 1PEI a key reference point for understanding local snow and avalanche dynamics and a crucial resource for both operational forecasting and scientific research.

Pejo Funivie Avalanche database: Over the past two decades, Pejo Funivie has developed and maintained an internal avalanche database aimed at improving risk assessment and operational safety across the ski area. The most significant avalanche events have been systematically georeferenced, catalogued, and documented with field photographs that capture the dynamics and characteristics of each event. In several cases, dynamic avalanche modeling was conducted to evaluate whether the recorded avalanches could interfere with ski slopes or other critical infrastructure, supporting more informed mitigation strategies.

Since 2021, data collection efforts have become significantly more intensive. A growing number of avalanche experts have contributed to on-site documentation, greatly expanding the scope and accuracy of the database. This improvement has been facilitated by the adoption of a dedicated mobile application, which enables real-time georeferencing, photographic documentation, and the direct upload of avalanche observations from the field. As a result, the vast majority of avalanches occurring in the area during recent seasons have been recorded, making the database a comprehensive and valuable tool for both operational decision-making and for more efficient avalanche hazard mapping.

Chapter 4

Methodology

This chapter details the methodological framework used to develop a data-driven model for avalanche prediction, with a particular focus on the use of Support Vector Machines (SVMs). The approach integrates domain expertise, robust data preprocessing, and modern machine learning techniques to create a scalable and interpretable forecasting model, especially suited for local-scale operational use in data-scarce regions.

We begin in Section 4.2 with a literature review of recent advances in machine learning applications for avalanche forecasting. While substantial progress has been made in regional-scale prediction, limited attention has been given to localized, operationally relevant models. Our approach builds upon the existing body of work by demonstrating how data-driven techniques, when combined with expert knowledge, can yield reliable models even with relatively limited data availability.

In Section 4.1, we introduce the theoretical foundation of Support Vector Machines (SVMs), which serve as the primary classification tool in our study. We explain the core concepts behind SVMs, including their formulation, decision boundaries, and kernel functions. This section also addresses performance metrics and model evaluation criteria, followed by a discussion of the specific advantages and limitations of applying SVMs in the context of avalanche forecasting.

Section 4.3 presents the modeling pipeline and development strategy in a comprehensive, step-by-step manner. We begin with data preprocessing and feature engineering techniques, followed by the initial preparations required for SVM implementation. A focus is placed on hyperparameter selection, tuning methodologies, and model training procedures. Given the imbalanced nature of avalanche datasets, we dedicate subsections to balancing strategies and feature selection approaches. Additionally, we incorporate feature extraction using Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and describe our model monitoring and interpretability framework to ensure the model's operational relevance and reliability.

By the end of this chapter, the reader will have a detailed understanding of the methodologies employed to construct and validate a robust, interpretable, and scalable avalanche forecasting model.

4.1 Machine Learning in Avalanche Forecasting, a literature review.

In recent years, the application of machine learning (ML) approaches in avalanche forecasting has gained increasing interest from both the scientific community and operational forecasters. When combined with traditional methods, these approaches enhance predictive performance and strengthen conventional forecasting tools. Machine learning models are particularly well-suited for analyzing large and heterogeneous datasets, enabling the identification of complex patterns characteristic of avalanche dynamics. These models provide probabilistic predictions, offering valuable insights for risk estimation. A range of algorithms, including Random Forests (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and Decision Trees (DT), have been employed to predict avalanche risk across various temporal and spatial scales.

Machine Learning Models Used

Several studies have investigated the application of machine learning for classifying avalanche danger levels, based on the European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS) danger scale, or for binary classification of avalanche release probability. Based on a literature review, the following models are identified as the most commonly used:

- **Random Forest (RF):** A robust ensemble method based on multiple decision trees, Random Forest is highly effective in noisy and non-linear environments. Pérez-Guillén et al. (2022) applied RF in their study and implemented it operationally during the 2023–2024 winter season to forecast avalanche danger across Switzerland. Similarly, Viallon-Galinier (2022) utilized a Random Forest model to predict avalanche activity at regional spatial scales, while Hendrick et al. (2023) used it to identify days with wet snow avalanches in Switzerland.
- **Decision Trees (DT):** Known for their simplicity and interpretability, Decision Trees were employed by Mayer et al. (2022) to model the relationship between nivo-meteorological parameters and avalanche occurrence, including size estimation, in Switzerland. Součková et al. (2022) combined Decision Trees with Random Forest to identify meteorological and snowpack drivers of wet and slab avalanches in a subregion of the Czech Republic. Hybrid approaches have also been proposed by Hendrikx et al. (2014) for regional-scale applications and by Marienthal et al. (2014), focusing on deep slab avalanches and persistent weak layers at local scales.
- **Support Vector Machines (SVM):** SVMs excel in handling high-dimensional data with complex non-linear relationships. Pozdnoukhov et al. (2008) applied this method at a regional scale to classify avalanche danger conditions based on spatio-temporal features.
- **Artificial Neural Networks (ANN):** ANNs are capable of modeling intricate non-linear relationships and interactions among features, though they require large and well-preprocessed datasets. Singh and Ganju (2008) explored their use in estimating the probability of avalanche release due to meteorological conditions in a region of the Indian Himalayas.

Datasets Used and Key Predictive Features

Machine learning studies in avalanche forecasting commonly rely on datasets combining field observations, meteorological data, and outputs from physically-based models. Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) provide key inputs such as fresh snow accumulation, air temperature, wind speed/direction, and snow water equivalent.

In Switzerland, several studies (Pérez-Guillén et al., 2022; Hendrick et al., 2023; Mayer et al., 2022) utilize AWS with advanced instrumentation, enabling integration with models like SNOWPACK and CROCUS. These models provide features such as stability indices and liquid water content, which improve predictive performance.

Gridded datasets from reanalysis products like ERA5 (Kronholm, 2006) extend historical coverage and provide spatial variables, including wind fields, compatible with Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) outputs.

Observed avalanche event datasets are critical for supervised learning, providing ground-truth labels for training. Key predictive features include fresh snow in the past 24 hours, snow water equivalent, liquid water content, surface temperature, wind activity (last 24–72 hours), model-derived stability indices, and topographic variables (elevation, slope, aspect).

An operational example is the model by Pérez-Guillén et al. (2022), used by SLF during the 2023–2024 winter season to support daily avalanche bulletins. As noted by Pérez-Guillén et al. (2022) and Hendrick et al. (2023), the model aims to complement, not replace, expert forecasters by enhancing decision-making with data-driven insights.

Machine Learning Models vs. Traditional Avalanche Forecasting Tools

The use of both physically-based models and machine learning (ML) models in avalanche forecasting highlights two fundamentally different yet complementary approaches, each with its own strengths and limitations.

The choice between these methods depends heavily on the specific application context. Understanding their respective advantages and constraints is key to selecting the most suitable approach for a given forecasting task.

Machine learning models are notable for their high predictive accuracy, especially when trained on large and heterogeneous datasets. Studies such as Pérez-Guillén et al. (2022) and Mayer et al. (2022) demonstrate that models like Random Forests and Decision Trees can efficiently predict avalanche danger levels based on meteorological and snowpack-related variables. However, ML models have notable limitations. One of the main concerns is their "black-box" nature, many ML algorithms lack transparency, making it difficult to interpret how decisions are made. Furthermore, if the dataset is small or highly imbalanced (as is often the case in avalanche forecasting, where avalanche events are rare compared to safe days), the model is prone to overfitting, as discussed by Pozdnoukhov et al. (2011). To mitigate this, datasets should be preprocessed and balanced, ensuring that minority classes (avalanche events) are adequately represented to prevent the model from learning predominantly from the majority class.

Physically-based models like SNOWPACK (Lehning et al., 2002) and CROCUS (Brun et al., 1992) simulate snowpack evolution by solving energy and mass balance equations, offering detailed vertical resolution for identifying weak layers. While valuable for operational forecasting, they require high-quality, costly sensor data from Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) and are limited to point-specific predictions. These models do not account for lateral energy exchanges and offer limited spatial coverage. Extensions to 3D, such as Alpine3D (Lehning et al., 2006), exist but are computationally demanding and not practical for large-scale applications.

A promising solution is the hybrid approach, as employed by Pérez-Guillén et al. (2022), Hendrick et al. (2023), and Viallon-Galinier (2022), which combines machine learning techniques with features derived from physically-based models. This approach leverages the predictive power of ML while maintaining the interpretability and physical grounding offered by process-based models. Such integration not only improves forecast performance but also increases the trust of human forecasters in the model outputs, an important factor in operational settings. When forecasters can understand and contextualize the predictions, they are more likely to incorporate them effectively into decision-making processes.

Spatial Scales and Limitations of Local Datasets

The spatial scale of a dataset significantly impacts the effectiveness and generalizability of predictive models. National-level applications (e.g., SLF in Switzerland, Météo-France) benefit from large and diverse datasets, which enable the development of statistically robust models. However, these models often lack site-specific precision due to the broad geographical scope.

Large-scale avalanche forecasting models (e.g., Pérez-Guillén et al., 2022; Hendrick et al., 2023) offer consistent performance across regions thanks to extensive datasets and standardized procedures. However, they may struggle to capture localized phenomena and microclimatic variations that are critical for precise forecasting in complex alpine terrain. In contrast, local models, such as those developed for Bridger Bowl (Marienthal et al., 2014), leverage detailed site-specific knowledge and fine-grained observations, leading to improved accuracy within narrowly defined areas. However, the limited variability and geographic scope of these datasets often reduce statistical robustness and hinder generalizability to other alpine regions, complicating both validation and broader operational deployment.

Avalanche occurrence is a rare event, which leads to highly imbalanced datasets dominated by non-event days. This class imbalance reduces the sensitivity of machine learning models, which tend to favor the majority class (i.e., no avalanche). To address this issue, data rebalancing techniques are commonly applied. Methods such as SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) (Chawla et al., 2002) and majority class downsampling can improve classification performance by increasing the presence or weighting of the minority class. These techniques have been successfully used in recent studies on avalanche forecasting using ML (Pérez-Guillén et al., 2022).

Conclusion

In recent years, many studies have applied machine learning to avalanche forecasting, typically at national or regional scales using large, standardized datasets. For instance, Součková et al. (2022) demonstrated that

data-driven models can perform well even at subregional levels, using data from semi-automated observation networks and simulated avalanche events. However, these studies often rely on meteorological, snowpack, and stability data derived from physically-based models rather than direct measurements. This reliance introduces an additional layer of uncertainty into the training process, as model outputs may not fully capture local-scale variability or measurement errors.

In contrast, the present study investigates the applicability of Support Vector Machines (SVM) as a binary classifier, leveraging their ability to capture the complex non-linearity inherent in avalanche activity classification within high-dimensional datasets that include limited avalanche occurrences. This analysis is conducted in a highly localized alpine context, specifically, the Val de la Mite of the Peio ski area. The dataset consists of daily, manually collected observations spanning multiple winter seasons, allowing the use of high-certainty avalanche records from a verified local database rather than relying on model-derived estimates. To address the common class imbalance between avalanche and non-avalanche days, random undersampling of the majority class is employed.

This methodological shift, from large-scale, often automated datasets to finely verified local data, aims to test the hypothesis that robust predictive performance can still be achieved despite the limited spatial extent and volume of data. In doing so, this thesis not only confirms the core findings of previous literature but also extends their applicability to under-instrumented areas, where local expertise and data quality can compensate for lower data quantity.

4.2 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

4.2.1 Introduction

Avalanche forecasting is a complex, multidisciplinary task that involves physical, meteorological, and geospatial factors. Avalanches occur when the balance between internal snowpack cohesion and external stresses is disrupted, influenced by variables such as temperature, precipitation, terrain, and snow stratigraphy. The non-linear interplay among these factors, combined with the scarcity of observed avalanche events relative to the abundance of meteorological data, makes prediction particularly challenging. This results in highly unbalanced datasets and necessitates advanced models capable of identifying patterns in limited data (Schweizer et al., 2003; Jamieson, 2006; Bellaire and Jamieson, 2013).

In this chapter, we describe the development of a predictive model for avalanche activity using snowpack and meteorological observations. Accurate models are essential to support forecasters and reduce the likelihood of human error. Following exploratory data analysis, Support Vector Machines (SVM) were selected due to their suitability for high-dimensional, low-sample datasets (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995).

The dataset was sourced from Mod.1 AINEVA observations at the Pejo Tarlenta site, comprising daily weather and snowpack measurements collected over multiple winter seasons. Variables include air temperatures, snowfall, snow depth and its variation, thermal gradients, and temporal trends of key indicators. The dataset’s high dimensionality, with many correlated or redundant features, posed a challenge for traditional modeling approaches (Hastie et al., 2017).

Avalanche events constitute a small fraction of the dataset (approximately 10:1 imbalance), making the classification problem more difficult. Standard models tend to favor the majority class, risking poor sensitivity to actual avalanche occurrences (He and Garcia, 2009). This, coupled with the risk of overfitting due to the large number of features, calls for techniques that manage both class imbalance and dimensionality. In the next chapter, we address these challenges through class balancing and feature selection (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003).

SVMs are particularly well-suited for this context due to their robustness in high-dimensional and imbalanced data settings. By maximizing the margin between classes and focusing on critical support vectors, SVMs achieve strong generalization performance (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995). Moreover, their ability to model non-linear relationships through kernel functions—especially the Radial Basis Function (RBF)—makes them effective for capturing the complex dynamics underlying avalanche formation (Schölkopf and Smola, 2005).

SVMs require tuning only a few key hyperparameters: the regularization parameter C and the kernel coefficient γ . Proper tuning enables a balance between model accuracy and complexity, helping avoid overfitting and improving generalization (Bishop, 2006).

4.2.2 Theory of SVM

Support Vector Machines (SVM) are supervised learning algorithms widely used for classification tasks, particularly when the relationship between variables is complex or non-linear. The core idea behind SVM is to find the optimal decision boundary, known as a hyperplane, that best separates data points from different classes.

In the simplest, linearly separable case, SVM identifies the hyperplane that maximizes the margin, which is the distance between the hyperplane and the closest data points from each class. These critical points are called support vectors and are essential in defining the decision boundary (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995). Maximizing this margin tends to produce a model with better generalization to new, unseen data (Bishop, 2006).

Figure 4.1: Linear SVM: optimal hyperplane, margin boundaries, and support vectors (Source: Scaler Topics, 2023)

A hyperplane in an n -dimensional space is an affine subspace of dimension $n - 1$. For two-dimensional input data, this is a line; for three dimensions, it is a plane. The equation of a hyperplane is:

$$w \cdot x + b = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

where w is the normal vector to the hyperplane, x is the input feature vector, and b is the bias term. The goal of SVM is to find the w and b that define the hyperplane with the largest margin while correctly classifying the training samples.

For linearly separable data, the optimization problem is:

$$\min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 \quad \text{subject to} \quad y_i(w \cdot x_i + b) \geq 1 \quad (4.2)$$

Here, $\|w\|$ is the norm of the weight vector, and the constraints ensure that each data point lies on the correct side of the margin. The margin itself is given by:

$$\text{margin} = \frac{2}{\|w\|} \quad (4.3)$$

Maximizing the margin leads to better separation and improved generalization (Hastie et al., 2017).

For a more comprehensive mathematical treatment of linear SVMs, see (Cristianini and Schölkopf, 2002).

Soft Margin and Regularization

In real-world problems such as avalanche prediction, data is often not perfectly separable due to noise, measurement errors, or overlapping class distributions.

Figure 4.2: Soft-margin SVM with slack variables allowing margin violations (Medium, 2019)

To address this, SVM introduces slack variables $\xi_i \geq 0$ to allow certain margin violations. This leads to the soft margin formulation:

$$\min_{w,b,\xi} \left[\frac{1}{2} |w|^2 + C \sum_i \xi_i \right] \quad \text{subject to} \quad y_i(w \cdot x_i + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i \quad (4.4)$$

The parameter $C > 0$ controls the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing classification errors:

- A large C penalizes margin violations more heavily, potentially leading to overfitting.
- A small C allows more violations, which may improve generalization.

This flexibility makes the soft-margin SVM applicable to noisy datasets like those encountered in meteorological contexts.

For further details on soft margin formulation and regularization theory, refer to (Schölkopf and Smola, 2005).

Non-linear Classification and the Kernel Trick

When the relationship between features and class labels is non-linear, as is often the case in avalanche prediction, a linear decision boundary is insufficient. SVM addresses this using the kernel trick, which implicitly maps the input data into a higher-dimensional feature space where a linear separator may exist.

Figure 4.3: Kernel trick concept: nonlinear data in 2D vs. linear separation in higher-dimensional space (Medium, 2018)

Rather than computing this transformation explicitly, SVM uses a kernel function $K(x_i, x_j)$ to compute the inner product in the transformed space:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = x_i \cdot x_j \quad (4.5)$$

Common kernels include:

- **Linear kernel:** $K(x_i, x_j) = x_i \cdot x_j$
- **Polynomial kernel** $K(x_i, x_j) = (x_i \cdot x_j + c)^d$
- **Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel** $K(x_i, x_j) = \exp[-\gamma \|x_i - x_j\|^2]$

In this study, we use the RBF kernel, which is particularly suited for modeling complex, non-linear relationships. The parameter γ controls the influence of individual data points:

- Low γ results in smoother decision boundaries.
- High γ leads to more localized and complex decision boundaries, which may overfit.

Using the kernel function, the SVM decision function becomes:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b \quad (4.6)$$

Only the support vectors ($\alpha_i > 0$) contribute to this decision boundary, making SVM both efficient and interpretable. For a deeper theoretical understanding of SVMs and the kernel trick, including practical applications, we recommend (Vapnik and N., 1995).

Advantages for Avalanche Prediction

The ability of SVM to handle non-linear boundaries, noisy data, and high-dimensional inputs makes it a powerful tool for avalanche forecasting, where environmental variables often interact in complex, non-linear ways. By carefully selecting the kernel and tuning parameters like C and γ , SVM can provide robust and generalizable models for identifying avalanche-prone conditions.

4.2.3 Performance Evaluation

A fundamental step in evaluating the performance of a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model is to divide the dataset into two distinct parts: a training set and a test set. The training set is used to develop the model and tune its hyperparameters, while the test set remains completely untouched during model development. This separation is essential to ensure an unbiased estimation of the model's performance on unseen data, reducing the risk of overfitting and enhancing the reliability of the evaluation process (Hastie et al., 2017).

In our study, the dataset was split into 75% for training and 25% for testing. This proportion strikes a balance between providing a sufficient number of samples for training and retaining a statistically meaningful test set for robust performance assessment. After applying the selected feature subset and balancing procedures, we typically obtained around 350 samples, with approximately 260–265 samples in the training set and 85–90 samples in the test set.

It is crucial to emphasize that all preprocessing steps, including balancing, feature selection, and hyperparameter tuning, were performed exclusively on the training set. This approach avoids data leakage and ensures that the test set serves as a true proxy for unseen data (Kuhn and Johnson, 2013). The final model, trained on the training data, was then evaluated on the untouched test set to simulate real-world deployment conditions.

We evaluate the performance of the SVM model using several key metrics to gain a comprehensive understanding of its effectiveness. A critical component of this evaluation is the confusion matrix, which provides valuable insight into how well the model is performing (Sokolova and Lapalme, 2009). For binary classification, the confusion matrix compares the predicted labels with the actual labels, helping to identify where the model makes errors.

The confusion matrix is structured as follows:

	Predicted Positive	Predicted Negative
Observed Positive	TP (True Positive)	FN (False Negative)
Observed Negative	FP (False Positive)	TN (True Negative)

Table 4.1: Confusion matrix for binary classification

Based on the confusion matrix, we consider the following metrics:

- **Accuracy:** Proportion of correct predictions out of all samples. It can be misleading in imbalanced datasets, as predicting the majority class can yield high accuracy even if the minority class is poorly predicted. (Chawla et al., 2002).

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{Total\ samples} \quad (4.7)$$

- **Precision:** Proportion of true positives among all predicted positives. Important when false positives are costly (Sokolova and Lapalme, 2009).

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (4.8)$$

- **Recall (Sensitivity):** Proportion of true positives among all actual positives. Crucial when missing positives is more serious than false alarms (Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015).

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4.9)$$

- **F1-score:** Harmonic mean of precision and recall. Balances both metrics, making it useful for imbalanced datasets (Powers, 2020).

$$F1 - Score = 2 \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (4.10)$$

- **Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC):** A balanced measure that evaluates binary classification performance using all elements of the confusion matrix. It ranges from -1 (total disagreement) to 1 (perfect prediction) and is robust to class imbalance (Chicco et al., 2021).

$$MCC = \frac{(TP \times TN) - (FP \times FN)}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (4.11)$$

- **Heidke Skill Score (HSS)**: Measures improvement over random chance using all confusion matrix terms. Ranges from $-\infty$ to 1, with 1 being perfect. Useful for rare event prediction and imbalanced datasets (Wilks, 2020).

$$HSS = \frac{2(TP \times TN) - (FP \times FN)}{(TP + FN)(TN + FN) + (TP + FP)(TN + FP)} \quad (4.12)$$

- **Hanssen–Kuipers Score (HK) / True Skill Statistic (TSS)**: Assesses classification skill by subtracting the false positive rate from the true positive rate. Ranges from -1 to 1. Suitable for imbalanced classification and threshold optimization (Powers, 2020)

$$HK = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} - \frac{FP}{TN + FP} \quad (4.13)$$

To facilitate a clear understanding of the advantages and limitations of each evaluation metric, Table 4.2 provides a comparative overview. This summary highlights the key strengths, potential drawbacks, and the contexts in which each metric is most appropriately applied, thereby guiding the selection of suitable performance measures for assessing the SVM classifier in avalanche prediction.

Metric	Strengths	Limitations	Best Suited For
Accuracy	Simple and intuitive; provides a general measure of correctness.	Misleading in imbalanced datasets; can mask poor minority class performance.	Balanced datasets where both classes are equally important.
Precision	Highlights reliability of positive predictions; reduces false alarms.	Ignores false negatives; may be high even if most actual positives are missed.	Applications where false positives are costly (e.g., avalanche warnings on safe days).
Recall	Emphasizes detection of true positives; reduces missed high-risk events.	May increase false positives; not sufficient alone for imbalanced data.	Safety-critical systems where missing positive cases is unacceptable.
F1-score	Balances false positives and false negatives; single robust metric.	Ignores true negatives; less informative when both classes are important.	Imbalanced classification problems requiring a balance between precision and recall.
MCC	Uses all confusion matrix elements; robust to class imbalance.	Can be complex to interpret; undefined if the denominator is zero.	Binary classification with imbalanced data and need for overall model reliability.
HSS	Measures performance gain over random chance; interpretable in forecasting contexts.	Less recognized outside meteorology; sensitive to marginal distributions.	Rare event forecasting, especially in meteorological applications.
HK	Separates true skill from chance; not biased by class imbalance.	Can be overly optimistic if used in isolation; needs complementary metrics.	Threshold-based decision making and operational forecasting with class imbalance.

Table 4.2: Comparison of performance metrics used to evaluate the SVM classifier

In the context of avalanche prediction, the selection of appropriate performance metrics is critical due to the inherent class imbalance, where avalanche occurrences are much rarer than non-avalanche days. Although Random UnderSampling was applied to mitigate this imbalance, it remains a fundamental consideration in guiding metric selection.

While accuracy is an intuitive and commonly used measure, it can be misleading in this setting; a model that predicts "no avalanche" for all instances may yield high accuracy but fail in its primary purpose of detecting hazardous conditions. Consequently, more informative and sensitive metrics were prioritized.

The F1-score was chosen to balance the trade-off between false positives and false negatives, both of which have significant operational consequences. Recall was given particular emphasis, as failing to identify true avalanche events poses unacceptable safety risks.

To complement these, the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) was included for its robustness and ability to provide reliable performance assessment under class imbalance.

In summary, focusing on the F1-score, recall, and MCC offers a comprehensive and realistic evaluation of the SVM model's performance. Most importantly, minimizing false negatives is not merely a statistical objective but a vital operational requirement for deploying a dependable and effective avalanche prediction system.

4.2.4 Advantages and Disadvantages of SVM in Avalanche Predictions

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a widely used algorithm for binary classification tasks, valued for its flexibility and strong performance (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995). In this study, SVM is particularly effective in handling high-dimensional feature spaces relative to a limited number of samples (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003). The regularization parameter C helps prevent overfitting, ensuring the model maintains good generalization on unseen data (Hsu et al., 2016). Additionally, the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel and the kernel trick enable SVMs to capture complex, non-linear relationships without explicitly increasing feature dimensionality (Schölkopf and Smola, 2005). Together with mature, well-optimized Python implementations, these characteristics make SVMs well-suited for avalanche prediction, even with constrained computational resources.

However, the SVM approach has notable limitations. Scalability is a primary concern, as training time increases substantially with larger datasets, potentially limiting its feasibility for very large-scale problems. Moreover, interpretability is challenging, especially with non-linear kernels (Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017). While visualization of decision boundaries is feasible in two-dimensional settings, understanding model decisions in high-dimensional spaces is impossible. To mitigate this, we applied a post hoc interpretability technique using SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), a model-agnostic, game-theoretic method that elucidates individual feature contributions to predictions (Lundberg and Lee, 2017), thereby improving transparency.

SVM performance is also highly sensitive to hyperparameter tuning, particularly the regularization parameter C and kernel width γ . To enhance robustness, we performed a fine-grained grid search around the optimal values identified by GridSearchCV (Hsu et al., 2016).

Critically, SVMs require balanced datasets to effectively learn from minority classes (He and Garcia, 2009). Given the pronounced class imbalance in avalanche prediction data, addressing this challenge was essential.

By thoroughly understanding these strengths and limitations, we establish a strong foundation for designing the subsequent modelling pipeline. This pipeline integrates careful data preprocessing, strategic balancing methods, and feature selection to optimize predictive performance and reliability in avalanche forecasting.

4.3 Modelling Pipeline and Development Strategy

The development of an effective machine learning model for avalanche forecasting requires not only appropriate algorithm selection but also a structured approach to data preparation, dimensionality reduction, hyperparameter optimization, and interpretability. This section outlines the full pipeline adopted in this study, detailing both the operational workflow and the rationale behind each phase (Kuhn and Johnson, 2013; Mountrakis et al., 2011; Cortes and Vapnik, 1995).

Data preprocessing forms the foundation of any robust ML pipeline. We first improved data quality by removing noise and addressing issues such as multicollinearity. Highly correlated features were removed

to simplify the model, enhance learning efficiency, and reduce overfitting risk (Dormann et al., 2013; Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003).

Hyperparameter tuning was performed via Grid Search to optimize key SVM parameters C and γ . A 5-fold cross-validation was used to provide unbiased performance estimates across data splits (Hsu et al., 2016; Kohavi and Elud, 1993). Metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and MCC were averaged over folds to determine the best parameter combination. Tuning was repeated for each balancing method and feature subset to ensure fairness in comparison.

A critical challenge is the **class imbalance** between avalanche and non-avalanche days. Models often underperform when rare but important events are underrepresented (He and Garcia, 2009). To address this, we tested resampling techniques, including oversampling and undersampling (Chawla et al., 2002). Care was taken to standardize data for centroid-based methods and ensure the physical plausibility of synthetic data. These strategies improved sensitivity to rare events without compromising generalization.

Feature selection and dimensionality reduction refined the dataset. We used filter, wrapper, and embedded methods to identify key predictors. Additionally, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) was applied to improve class separability and reduce dimensionality while preserving relevant variance.

With a refined feature set, we trained a **Support Vector Machine (SVM)** classifier. The choice of SVM with an RBF kernel was based on both theoretical and empirical grounds. Meteorological data often exhibits non-linear patterns; the RBF kernel projects data into higher-dimensional space to capture such complexity (Cristianini and Schölkopf, 2002; Schölkopf and Smola, 2005).

Beyond performance, we emphasized **interpretability and reliability**. SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values were used to quantify feature contributions, ensuring transparency in predictions (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). **Bootstrap analysis** assessed model stability across data samples, and final evaluation was conducted on an independent dataset of real avalanche cases to validate generalization.

Figure 4.4 illustrates the full methodological pipeline, color-coded by phase: data collection and preprocessing (blue), model training and tuning (red), and interpretability and evaluation (green).

Figure 4.4: Methodological pipeline overview

4.3.1 Data Preprocessing and Feature Engineering

The dataset from Mod.1 AINEVA, collected at the Pejo Tarlenta snow observation site, underwent thorough preprocessing before integration into the SVM model.

Preprocessing began with an exploratory data analysis to characterize the collected measurements and

identify inconsistencies. Data cleaning involved correcting common errors such as inverted minimum and maximum air temperatures. Minor missing values were imputed using adjacent days' measurements, provided no significant meteorological events occurred. Otherwise, gaps remained unfilled to preserve data integrity. Outliers, often caused by transmission errors (e.g., snow temperature recorded as 57 instead of -7°C), were identified based on physical plausibility and removed to ensure data quality.

Avalanche data was filtered to include only events classified as New Snow and Wet Snow problems. Wind slab avalanches and days characterized by wind-driven snow were excluded to maintain focus on the relevant avalanche types.

Avalanche dynamics and expert forecasting methods indicate that avalanche risk depends not only on conditions from a single day but also on their evolution over several days. Additionally, snowpack responses are often gradual rather than abrupt, suggesting that cumulative and variation-based features provide key predictive value. Accordingly, we engineered features that capture averages, cumulative sums, and temporal variations of critical variables.

The dataset obtained from Mod.1 Aineva, together with the derived features, is categorized as follows:

1. Basic Meteorological and Snow Parameters

Daily measurements describing atmospheric and snowpack conditions:

- N, V: Cloud cover and visibility at observation time.
- TaG, TminG, TmaxG: Daily mean, minimum, and maximum air temperatures.
- HSnum: Snow depth (HS), in centimeters.
- HNnum: New snow accumulation (HN), in centimeters.
- TH01G, TH03G: Snow temperature at 10 cm and 30 cm below the surface.
- PR: Ram penetration depth, indicating snow hardness.
- DayOfSeason: Number of days since December 1 (start of the season).

2. Wind-Related Features

Variables related to wind activity and snow transport:

- VQ1: Wind intensity.
- VQ2: Predominant areas of wind-driven snow deposition.
- SnowDrift_1d to SnowDrift_5d: Wind transport potential indices over the past 1 to 5 days.

3. Snow Depth Variation

Indicators of recent changes in snow depth:

- HS_delta_1d, HS_delta_2d, HS_delta_3d, HS_delta_5d: Snow depth variation over the past 1, 2, 3, and 5 days.

4. Cumulative New Snowfall

Aggregated snowfall over recent time windows:

- HN_2d, HN_3d, HN_5d: Total new snow accumulation HN over the past 2, 3, and 5 days.
- FreshSWE: Snow water equivalent (SWE) of new snow.
- SeasonalSWE_cum: Cumulative SWE from all snowfall events during the season.

5. Snowfall Timing

Time since the last snowfall event:

- DaysSinceLastSnow: Number of days since the last measurable snowfall.

6. Aggregated Temperature Statistics

Temperature extremes over fixed time intervals:

- Tmin_2d, Tmax_2d, Tmin_3d, Tmax_3d, Tmin_5d, Tmax_5d: Minimum and maximum air temperatures over the past 2, 3, and 5 days.

7. Temperature Amplitudes and Gradients

Indicators of thermal variability and snowpack instability:

- `TempAmplitude_1d`, `TempAmplitude_2d`, `TempAmplitude_3d`, `TempAmplitude_5d`: Daily temperature amplitudes over recent days.
- `TempGrad_HS`: Snowpack temperature gradient ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{m}$).

8. Temperature Trend (Delta) Features

Recent changes in air temperature:

- `TaG_delta_1d` to `TaG_delta_5d`: Change in mean air temperature over the past 1 to 5 days.
- `TminG_delta_1d` to `TminG_delta_5d`: Change in minimum temperature over the same period.
- `TmaxG_delta_1d` to `TmaxG_delta_5d`: Change in maximum temperature over the same period.

9. Mean Air Temperature

- `T_mean`: Daily average air temperature.

10. Precipitation Accumulation

Total precipitation over recent periods:

- `Precip_1d`, `Precip_2d`, `Precip_3d`, `Precip_5d`: Accumulated precipitation over the past 1, 2, 3, and 5 days.

11. Snow Surface Temperature Variation

Changes in surface snow temperature:

- `Tsnow_delta_1d` to `Tsnow_delta_5d`: Change in surface temperature over the past 1 to 5 days.

12. Snow Surface Characteristics

Observational descriptors of the snow surface:

- `SnowConditionIndex`: Index of surface snow condition.
- `MFCrust_present`: Presence of a melt-freeze crust based on visual observation.
- `NewMFCrust`: Formation of a new crust not observed in previous days.
- `ConsecCrustsDays`: Number of consecutive days the crust has persisted.

13. Wet Snow Conditions

Indicators of wet snow presence and persistence:

- `WetSnow_CS`: Binary indicator of wet snow from surface observation.
- `WetSnow_Temperature`: Binary indicator based on snow temperature at 10 cm exceeding -1°C .
- `ConsecWetSnowDays`: Number of consecutive wet snow days.

14. Snow Temperature Transformations

Emphasizing near-zero snow temperatures:

- `TH10_tanh`: Hyperbolic tangent transformation of snow temperature at 10 cm.
- `TH30_tanh`: Hyperbolic tangent transformation of snow temperature at 30 cm.

This comprehensive feature set combines physical principles and empirical avalanche knowledge, enabling the model to capture both immediate fluctuations and cumulative environmental effects. Such temporal depth enhances the model's capability to generalize avalanche risk accurately.

Before applying any SVM training, we conducted a preliminary manual exclusion of certain variables based on domain knowledge and interpretability considerations. Specifically, the features `N` (cloud cover) and

V (visibility) were removed, as they reflect transient atmospheric conditions at the time of observation and offer limited physical relevance to avalanche triggering mechanisms.

Additionally, we excluded several wind- and snow-related features based on domain-specific considerations and the scope of our study. The wind-related variables VQ1 (wind intensity) and VQ2 (wind direction), along with SnowDrift_1d to SnowDrift_5d, which estimate recent snow transport, were omitted, as our analysis does not focus on wind slab avalanches. These types of avalanches are particularly difficult to predict due to their strong dependence on topography, mechanical layering, and small-scale triggering dynamics.

We also removed FreshSWE, which represents the amount of new snow in terms of snow water equivalent, as it is highly correlated with recent precipitation. Additionally, SeasonalSWE_cum, a cumulative measure of seasonal snow water equivalent, was excluded because it closely mirrors snow depth trends without accounting for compaction effects.

Several wet snow indicators, WetSnow_CS, WetSnow_Temperature, ConsecWetSnowDays and SnowConditionIndex, as well as crust-related features such as MFCrust_present, NewMFCrust and ConsecCrustsDays, were also excluded. These variables tend to be highly site-specific and may not accurately reflect conditions along actual avalanche paths.

Finally, we discarded the features TH10_tanh and TH30_tanh, which are hyperbolic tangent transformations of snow temperature variables. Although these transformations were intended to approximate a normal distribution, they compromise the physical interpretability of the data, potentially complicating the analysis and understanding of model outputs.

Correlated variables can be removed because they do not provide additional useful information to the model. In our case, we decided to remove features that are highly correlated with each other (absolute correlation > 0.9). For each pair of highly correlated features, we removed the one with the lower correlation to the target variable (AvalDay). The features removed based on this criterion are: HN_2d, HN_3d, HN_5d, TminG, TmaxG, Tmin_3d, Tmin_5d, Tmax_2d, Tmax_3d, Tmax_5d.

In summary, our data preprocessing and feature engineering steps carefully combined domain knowledge with statistical techniques to construct a robust, physically meaningful feature set. By excluding redundant, irrelevant, or highly correlated variables, we aimed to enhance the interpretability and predictive performance of the SVM model, while maintaining a focus on key avalanche-relevant processes. This approach ensures that the model leverages the most informative features to effectively capture the complex environmental conditions leading to avalanche events.

4.3.2 Preliminary step for SVM modelling

To prevent feature scaling from biasing the results, the data was normalized. This approach preserves the original data distribution while ensuring that all features are comparable, preventing any single feature from dominating the model due to differences in scale.

The dataset was split into two parts: a training set containing 75% of the available data, and a testing set containing the remaining 25%. The training set was used to fit the model and to explore the relationships between features and the target variable (avalanche occurrences) in a supervised learning framework. The testing set remained completely unseen during training and was reserved solely for evaluating the model's predictive performance.

It is important to note that for each balancing method and feature selection step, the dataset size may vary because some features contain missing values (NaNs). Observations with missing data for selected features were excluded, which affects the total number of samples and, consequently, the composition of the training and testing splits.

After normalization and dataset splitting, the model was trained multiple times to identify the optimal hyperparameters, as detailed in the following section.

4.3.3 Hyperparameter Interpretation and Tuning Strategy

Support Vector Machines (SVM) rely on two critical hyperparameters, C and γ , which jointly influence model complexity and generalization, especially when using a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel.

The regularization parameter C controls the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing classification errors. A small C allows for a wider margin by tolerating more misclassifications, promoting

generalization. In contrast, a large C imposes a higher penalty for errors, encouraging the model to fit the training data more closely, at the risk of overfitting (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995).

The kernel parameter γ determines the influence of individual training samples. A low γ value leads to smoother, more generalized decision boundaries, while a high γ creates more complex and localized ones. Excessively high γ may lead to overfitting, whereas too low a value can result in underfitting (Schölkopf and Smola, 2005).

The interaction between C and γ is crucial:

- **High C , high γ :** Very flexible model, prone to overfitting (Bishop, 2006).
- **Low C , low γ :** Simpler model, may underfit the data (Cristianini and Schölkopf, 2002).
- **Balanced values:** Better generalization and stable decision boundaries.

To identify optimal combinations of these parameters, a **Grid Search** strategy was employed in conjunction with 5-fold cross-validation. This exhaustive technique systematically evaluates every pair of C and γ values on a predefined grid, selecting the configuration that maximizes model performance, measured using the F1 score, averaged across all folds (Hsu et al., 2016; Kuhn and Johnson, 2013).

To visualize performance trends in the hyperparameter space, we used a two-dimensional heatmap, where:

- The horizontal axis represents C , the vertical axis represents γ .
- The color of each cell encodes model performance (F1 score), with warmer colors indicating better results.

Such visualizations help identify regions of stable performance and guide further refinement. A well-defined area with consistently high scores suggests that the model is robust to minor variations in the parameters. Conversely, isolated peaks may indicate sensitivity and the need for finer granularity or regularization (Bergstra and Bengio, 2012).

The standard grid used was relatively dense:

- $C \in \{0.001, 0.002, \dots, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1, 2, \dots, 10, 20, \dots, 1000\}$ (56 values)
- $\gamma \in \{0.0001, 0.0002, \dots, 0.001, 0.002, \dots, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 100\}$ (56 values)

However, in more computationally intensive experiments, especially those involving feature selection methods such as Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), Forward Feature Selection (FFS), and Backward Feature Elimination (BFE), a coarser grid was adopted to reduce runtime while preserving coverage of key regions:

- $C \in \{0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000\}$ (7 values)
- $\gamma \in \{0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100\}$ (7 values)

For each feature subset, each data balancing strategy, and each model variation, hyperparameter tuning was repeated independently. This ensured that parameter optimization was context-specific and adapted to the characteristics of each configuration, rather than relying on a global, one-size-fits-all solution.

This strategy is aligned with findings in the literature showing that feature selection and hyperparameter tuning are deeply interdependent (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003; Blum and Langley, 1997). By customizing hyperparameter search per configuration, we improved both model performance and robustness across scenarios.

4.3.4 Model training and performance evaluation

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) model was trained on the training dataset to identify the optimal decision boundary that best separates the classes. By maximizing the margin between samples of different classes, the SVM aims to enhance generalization performance on unseen data. In this study, an RBF kernel was used to effectively capture the underlying nonlinear relationships in the data.

The key input parameters for the SVM training include the kernel type and the hyperparameters C (regularization) and γ (kernel width), which were determined through hyperparameter tuning. This process ensures that the model can effectively discriminate between classes.

After training, the model’s performance was evaluated by comparing its predictions on the test dataset with the actual observations. The primary evaluation metrics used were the F1-score and the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), which together provide a balanced assessment by considering both precision and recall, while effectively handling class imbalance and minimizing false negatives.

Applying this training framework across different approaches—including dataset balancing, feature selection, and feature extraction, enabled the comparison of various SVM models to identify the configuration with the best predictive performance.

4.3.5 Dataset Balancing

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are sensitive to class imbalance, particularly in scenarios where the minority class carries greater importance, as with avalanche prediction. In imbalanced datasets, the classifier tends to favor the majority class due to the abundance of training examples, which can lead to poor predictive performance on the minority class. This bias arises because the model seeks to minimize overall error, often at the expense of misclassifying rare but critical events such as avalanches (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995; He and Garcia, 2009).

Our dataset, filtered to include complete observations from 1995 to 2024, comprises 1980 non-avalanche days (81.3%) and 454 avalanche days (18.7%) when considering all avalanche events. However, if small avalanches are excluded, the dataset contains 1816 non-avalanche days (91.3%) and 172 avalanche days (8.7%) for the same period.

Training an SVM model on such an imbalanced dataset would likely lead to high accuracy in predicting non-avalanche days but poor recall for avalanche days. This imbalance poses a significant challenge, as it risks compromising the primary goal of this study: developing a reliable tool for accurate avalanche forecasting.

To mitigate this imbalance and improve model performance on the minority class, we apply data balancing techniques, including both undersampling the majority class and oversampling the minority class. These methods help prevent the classifier from becoming biased toward the majority class and support learning a decision boundary that better distinguishes between avalanche and non-avalanche days (Chawla et al., 2002; Fernández et al., 2018).

A range of resampling strategies, from basic to advanced, are evaluated to determine which best enhances performance when paired with the SVM model (He and Garcia, 2009; Fernández et al., 2018). For each resampling method, we explore a simplified 2D scenario using two features as predictors to visually assess how the method affects class distribution and SVM classification behavior. Scatter plots are generated before and after resampling to visualize changes in class distribution and their effect on the decision boundary. Additionally, the full set of features is evaluated to assess how feature selection impacts model performance.

To address the class imbalance in our avalanche dataset, we explore several resampling techniques available in the Python `imbalanced-learn` library. This library provides a suite of tools designed to handle imbalanced classification problems through various resampling strategies. Comprehensive documentation for each method can be found at [this link](#). The following paragraphs summarize the main undersampling and oversampling approaches evaluated in our study.

Undersampling Methods

Random Undersampling is a basic yet effective technique that randomly removes samples from the majority class to match the number of minority class observations. While computationally efficient and easy to implement, it risks discarding potentially informative data and can lead to underfitting due to the loss of a large portion of the training data (Lemaître et al., 2015).

Time-Limited Random Undersampling is a variation we introduce, where the majority class samples are drawn only from a 10-day window surrounding each avalanche event. This approach targets days with similar snow conditions, aiming to enhance model sensitivity to avalanche precursors. However, it removes many majority-class samples from low-risk periods, potentially omitting useful information.

NearMiss is a family of heuristic methods that selects the majority class samples based on their distances to minority class instances. NearMiss-1 retains those closest to the minority class points, focusing on refining

the decision boundary, but can be sensitive to noise. NearMiss-2 favors those farthest from the minority class, reducing the influence of borderline noise. NearMiss-3 combines both approaches through a two-step process, enhancing robustness while preserving discriminatory information (Tomek, 1976a).

Condensed Nearest Neighbour (CNN) seeks to retain only the most informative majority class samples, those nearest to the minority class, thereby defining the decision boundary with fewer, more relevant points. This technique reduces redundancy in the data but may suffer from sensitivity to noise, particularly in high-dimensional spaces (Hart, 1968).

Edited Nearest Neighbours (ENN) improves data quality by removing samples whose class labels disagree with the majority of their nearest neighbors, typically using a k-nearest neighbors algorithm. This refines the dataset by eliminating ambiguous or mislabeled points, leading to cleaner class boundaries and potentially better generalization (Wilson, 1972).

Cluster Centroids applies KMeans clustering to the majority class and replaces groups of samples with their corresponding centroids. This reduces the dataset size while maintaining the spatial distribution of the majority class. Though effective in high-dimensional data, the abstraction of samples into centroids may lead to the loss of fine-grained information (Tomek, 1976b).

Tomek Links identifies and removes pairs of samples from opposite classes that are each other's nearest neighbors and not closer to any third point. These borderline pairs typically represent noisy or overlapping instances. By eliminating the majority class sample in such links (or both, if specified), this method clarifies the decision boundary and improves class separability, though its effect is limited in datasets with severe imbalance (Tomek, 1976b).

Oversampling Methods

Random Oversampling balances the dataset by randomly duplicating minority class samples until both classes have equal representation. This method is easy to implement and can improve classifier sensitivity to the minority class but risks overfitting since no new data is introduced (Lemaître et al., 2015).

SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) creates synthetic minority samples by interpolating between existing points and their nearest neighbors. This increases the diversity of the minority class and helps reduce overfitting, although it may generate noisy or unrealistic examples, especially if the minority class contains outliers or in high-dimensional spaces (Chawla et al., 2002).

ADASYN (Adaptive Synthetic Sampling) It builds on SMOTE by adaptively generating synthetic samples, focusing more on minority instances that are difficult to classify or located in sparse regions. This targeted approach can improve the decision boundary, but it may also increase noise if the dataset contains outliers (He et al., 2008).

SVMSMOTE integrates SMOTE with Support Vector Machines by generating synthetic samples near the SVM decision boundary, guided by support vectors. This focuses sample generation on the most informative areas, potentially improving classification performance. However, it requires more computational resources and can be sensitive to noise (Nguyen et al., 2011).

Comparison

Handling class imbalance is crucial in tasks like avalanche prediction, where correctly identifying the minority class is essential. Two common strategies are undersampling and oversampling.

Undersampling reduces the majority class to balance the dataset, lowering computational costs and helping the model focus on decision boundaries. However, it risks losing important information and may lead to underfitting.

Oversampling increases minority class instances by duplication or synthetic generation, improving recall and reducing class bias. While it preserves all original data, it can cause overfitting and increase training time. Techniques like SMOTE and ADASYN help mitigate these issues but may introduce noise.

Each method has trade-offs: undersampling prioritizes efficiency, while oversampling enhances sensitivity. In practice, hybrid approaches are often used for better balance.

The selection of the most appropriate balancing strategy is based on a comparative analysis of how each method influences SVM performance, assessed through standard evaluation metrics.

4.3.6 Feature Selection

This section outlines the methods used for selecting the most relevant features. Feature selection plays a critical role in SVM models by enhancing performance, reducing complexity, and improving interpretability. Eliminating irrelevant or noisy features helps prevent overfitting, allows the model to focus on the most informative patterns, and leads to more accurate predictions. It also accelerates training time and simplifies the modeling process, particularly when working with high-dimensional data. Moreover, feature selection highlights the most important variables, making the model's decisions easier to understand and explain (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003; Hastie et al., 2017).

Three main categories of feature selection methods are commonly found in the literature: filter methods, wrapper methods, and embedded methods. In this study, we evaluate a range of techniques from each category to ensure a more robust and comprehensive approach to feature selection (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003).

The filtered (correlated features are removed), normalized, and balanced dataset is then used to evaluate various feature selection methods. For each method, we determine the optimal number of features that yields the best model performance. A comprehensive comparison of these results is provided at the end of this chapter.

Filter Methods

Filter methods are a class of feature selection techniques that are computationally efficient and straightforward to implement (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003; Chandrashekar and Sahin, 2014). Depending on the performance of a specific model, filter methods assess each feature independently using statistical metrics to evaluate its relevance to the target variable.

A key advantage of filter methods is their model-agnostic nature, allowing them to be used in conjunction with any learning algorithm. Common statistical measures employed include correlation coefficients, mutual information, and chi-square tests, which quantify the strength of association between each feature and the target (Chandrashekar and Sahin, 2014). Features that demonstrate significant relevance are retained, while those deemed irrelevant or redundant are discarded.

Because filter methods base their evaluation solely on individual feature statistics, without considering the effect of features in combination or their interactions, they offer high computational efficiency and scalability to large datasets. However, this independence can be a limitation, as these methods may overlook important feature dependencies that influence model performance.

ANOVA f-test: In a binary classification setting, a feature showing a significant difference in means between the two classes, indicated by a low p-value, is considered important, as it may enhance the model's predictive ability. Conversely, a high p-value (typically above 0.05) suggests that the feature does not differ substantially between classes and is likely less informative (Kuhn and Johnson, 2013).

However, ANOVA has notable limitations when applied to feature selection for SVMs with RBF kernels. Primarily, ANOVA assesses mean differences under the assumption of linear relationships, which may cause it to miss features that influence nonlinear decision boundaries critical to RBF kernels. Additionally, it evaluates each feature independently, ignoring potential interactions between features that can be vital for model performance. Since the RBF kernel maps data into a high-dimensional space, feature importance can differ from what ANOVA suggests, potentially leading to the exclusion of features that are valuable in combination. Lastly, features that do not show significant individual mean differences can still be important

when considered alongside others in a non-linear context, and the univariate approach of ANOVA can overlook such subtleties, reducing the overall effectiveness of feature selection.

In summary, ANOVA assists feature selection in binary classification by identifying features with significant mean differences between classes. While useful for initial screening, it should be complemented with other methods to capture nonlinear relationships and feature interactions important for RBF kernel SVMs.

Wrapper Methods

Wrapper methods are based on a specific machine learning algorithm fitted to a given dataset (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003). The idea is to select a subset of features and test how the model works. The selection is made by maximizing the performance of the model for each specific feature setup.

Permutation ranking: Permutation importance is a model-agnostic technique used to evaluate the significance of each feature by measuring the impact of random shuffling on model performance (Breiman, 2001; Molnar, 2019). The central idea is that if a feature is important for making accurate predictions, disrupting its relationship with the target variable will degrade the model’s performance. Conversely, if permuting the feature has little or no effect, it is likely of low relevance.

In this study, permutation importance was applied to a Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel. The model was trained after applying random undersampling to balance the classes. The dataset was then split into training (75%) and testing (25%) subsets, and normalized using the Min-Max scaling method. SVM hyperparameters (C and γ) were optimized via grid search with cross-validation to ensure reliable model performance before feature importance evaluation.

Feature importance was assessed using F1-score as the scoring metric. Each feature was randomly shuffled 100 times, and the average decrease in model accuracy was calculated. Features were ranked according to the magnitude of this decrease, with error bars representing the standard deviation across the 100 iterations.

A cumulative ranking strategy was employed, retaining features that together accounted for 95% of the total performance reduction. This threshold was chosen to strike a balance between model interpretability and predictive power, ensuring only the most influential features are preserved while reducing the risk of overfitting.

Backward Feature Elimination (BFE): BFE is a wrapper-based feature selection technique that aims to improve model performance by iteratively removing the least relevant features. Unlike filter methods, BFE involves repeated training and evaluation of a machine learning model, making it more computationally demanding but also more closely aligned with the model’s actual performance (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003; Kuhn and Johnson, 2013).

The process begins with all candidate features included in the dataset. The model is trained and evaluated using a performance metric, in this study, the F1-score, which balances precision and recall across all classes, making it well-suited for imbalanced classification tasks. The least important feature is identified based on the model’s internal assessment (e.g., coefficients or importance scores), and then removed.

This process is repeated iteratively: at each step, the model is retrained on the reduced feature set, and performance is re-evaluated. If removing a feature does not degrade performance, the feature is permanently excluded. Conversely, if performance drops significantly, the feature is retained. The procedure continues until no further improvement can be achieved by eliminating additional features.

To ensure computational feasibility, a coarse logarithmic grid was used to define the SVM hyperparameters. Specifically, a 7×7 grid was established, where $C \in (0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000)$ and $\gamma \in (0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100)$

This grid allows for efficient exploration of the parameter space without requiring fine-tuning, since the objective of this step is feature evaluation rather than hyperparameter optimization.

Prior to BFE, the dataset was cleaned by removing missing values and highly correlated features. Random undersampling was applied to address class imbalance, and data normalization was performed using Min-Max scaling. The dataset was then split into training (75%) and test (25%) subsets.

Backward Feature Elimination (BFE) was implemented using the `SequentialFeatureSelector` function from *mlxtend* Python library, with the parameter `forward = False` to indicate backward elimination. The number of features to select, k_{features} , was defined as a range from 1 to 39, enabling the algorithm to explore all

possible subset sizes. At each iteration, model performance was evaluated using 5-fold cross-validation, and hyperparameter tuning was performed through GridSearchCV on a predefined logarithmic parameter grid

Forward Feature Selection (FFS): FFS, like Backward Feature Elimination (BFE), is a wrapper method used to identify the most informative features for a machine learning model. In this case, it is applied to a Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003; Kuhn and Johnson, 2013). The RBF kernel is particularly effective in capturing non-linear relationships by projecting the input space into a higher-dimensional feature space. However, this also increases the risk of overfitting and computational burden, making feature selection essential.

FFS begins with an empty feature set and adds one feature at a time. At each iteration, the feature whose inclusion yields the greatest improvement in model performance, evaluated via metrics such as F1-score, is added. This process continues until no further significant improvements are observed or a predefined maximum number of features is reached.

Redundant features were first removed based on correlation and variance thresholds to reduce noise and multicollinearity. A pipeline was implemented using the SequentialFeatureSelector (SFS) from the mlxtend library, combined with a Support Vector Classifier (SVC) and Random Undersampling to address class imbalance.

Hyperparameters C and γ were optimized using GridSearchCV over a coarse logarithmic grid $C \in (0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000)$ and $\gamma \in (0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100)$

Feature evaluation was based on F1-score using 5-fold cross-validation. The algorithm explored all subset sizes from 1 to 39, identifying the feature combination that achieved the best average performance.

Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV): RFECV is a wrapper-based feature selection method used to identify the most relevant features for a model by recursively removing the least important features while using cross-validation to evaluate model performance (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003).

In this study, RFECV is implemented using a Linear Support Vector Classifier (LinearSVC) as the estimator (Pedregosa et al., 2011). LinearSVC is well-suited for feature selection because it assigns coefficients (weights) to features, which can be interpreted as their relative importance. It is not possible to use an RBF (Radial Basis Function) kernel for this type of feature selection because non-linear kernels like RBF do not provide interpretable feature importance scores. The RBF kernel maps the input data into a high-dimensional space where the original features are no longer explicitly represented, making it impossible to assign direct importance weights to them. Therefore, RFECV relies on linear models such as LinearSVC, where feature importance can be directly derived from the model’s learned coefficients.

A 5-fold cross-validation strategy is employed to ensure robust performance evaluation. At each iteration, the model is trained using a subset of the data and validated on the remaining fold, rotating through all combinations.

The RFECV process begins with all available features. Features are ranked based on the absolute value of their weights from the linear SVM. The feature with the lowest weight is removed, and the process repeats until performance (measured by macro F1-score) no longer improves.

Before applying RFECV, the dataset is processed using Random Undersampling to balance the class distribution and MinMax scaling to normalize the feature values. The feature selection is performed within a pipeline to ensure that scaling and undersampling are consistently applied across the cross-validation folds.

Embedded Methods

SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP): SHAP is a model-agnostic method used to interpret machine learning models and understand feature importance (Lundberg and Lee, 2017; Molnar, 2019). It is based on Shapley values from game theory, which measure the contribution of each player (feature) to the outcome of a coalition (model prediction). SHAP applies this concept to machine learning by quantifying each feature’s contribution to a model’s predictions.

For feature selection, SHAP identifies the most influential features by calculating SHAP values for each feature across all predictions in a dataset. These values indicate how much a feature contributes to increasing or decreasing individual predictions. By averaging the absolute SHAP values for each feature across all

samples, a global feature importance score is derived. Features with higher scores are considered more influential and can be prioritized for selection.

The process begins by training a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model on a preprocessed and randomly undersampled dataset. Preprocessing steps, including removal of correlated and low-variance features, followed by MinMax scaling, mirror those described in previous methods. Hyperparameters C and γ are fine-tuned using cross-validation.

SHAP values are computed using the `shap.KernelExplainer` (Lundberg and Lee, 2017), a model-agnostic explanation method compatible with non-linear models like SVM. It approximates each feature’s contribution to the model’s output probabilities using Shapley values.

Once SHAP values are computed for each feature and each sample, they are reshaped to focus on the values associated with the positive class (class 1), which corresponds to the prediction of avalanche events. The feature importance is calculated as the average of the absolute SHAP values across all samples. Both features that push the model toward predicting an avalanche and those that push it away are considered informative. SHAP values close to zero indicate a minimal contribution to the prediction.

Two approaches are used to select the best features:

- **Cumulative SHAP Contribution:** Selecting the top features that account for 95% of the total mean absolute SHAP value sum.
- **Incremental Feature Addition:** Training an SVM model using the top N features (ranked by SHAP importance) and evaluating its performance as more features are added, one at a time.

Following the approach used in other feature selection methods, we primarily employ the Incremental Feature Addition method to directly evaluate the impact of feature selection on the SVM model’s performance.

Comparison of Methods

The following table summarizes the description of each method and highlights the advantages and disadvantages of their application to an SVM with an RBF kernel.

Method	Description	Pros	Cons
ANOVA F-test	Statistical test used to compare the variance between classes and features. It measures the relationship between each feature and the target.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple and fast. - Good for datasets with many features. - Helps identify strong relationships between features and target. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assumes features are normally distributed. - Not suitable for non-linear relationships. - Can be sensitive to outliers.
Permutation Ranking	Involves shuffling the target variable and observing the change in performance metrics to assess feature importance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model-agnostic (doesn’t assume a specific model). - Can capture complex, non-linear relationships. - No assumptions about data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computational expensive, especially for large datasets. - Requires significant resources to permute and calculate performance.

Backward Feature Elimination (BFE)	Iteratively removes the least important feature based on performance metrics until an optimal subset is reached.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple and intuitive. - Works well with high-dimensional data. - Reduces overfitting by eliminating irrelevant features. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computationally expensive as it evaluates multiple models. - May remove features that are important in combination with others.
Forward Feature Selection (FFS)	Starts with an empty set of features and adds one feature at a time, based on performance improvement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficient with smaller datasets. - Can improve model accuracy by adding only the most relevant features. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May overlook feature interactions. - Computationally expensive as it requires multiple model evaluations.
Recursive Feature Selection (RFS) with Cross Validation	Recursively removes the least important features based on model performance (usually with cross-validation).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduces overfitting. - More reliable since it uses cross-validation. - Well-suited for SVMs and non-linear models like RBF. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computational Expensive due to cross-validation and recursion. - Can be slow for large datasets.
SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations)	Provides a game-theoretic approach to measure feature importance by assigning "Shapley values" to features.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly accurate and interpretable. - Works for both linear and non-linear models. - Provides detailed insights into feature contributions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computational intensive, especially for large datasets. - Requires a trained model to calculate Shapley values.

Table 4.3: Comparison of feature selection methods for SVM with RBF kernel

4.3.7 Feature Extraction: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)

An alternative to feature selection is feature extraction, which combines existing features to create new, more informative ones that enhance classification. In this study, we employed Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) to reduce dimensionality and assess whether projecting features into a lower-dimensional space could improve the performance of a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier.

LDA is a supervised linear transformation technique that aims to find the feature space projection maximizing class separability. It does so by computing two scatter matrices: the within-class scatter, which measures variability within each class, and the between-class scatter, which captures the separation between class means. The goal of LDA is to identify directions (eigenvectors) that maximize the ratio of between-class to within-class scatter (McLachlan and Rayens, 2004).

LDA assumes that each class follows a normal (Gaussian) distribution, that all classes share the same covariance structure, and that the classes are linearly separable. However, since our data does not fully meet these assumptions, the applicability and effectiveness of LDA in this context may be limited.

Unlike Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which is unsupervised and agnostic to class labels, LDA is explicitly designed to improve class discrimination, making it more suitable when labels are available (Jolliffe, 2002; Belhumeur et al., 1997).

To evaluate the integration of LDA with SVM, we considered four configurations:

- SVM trained on all 39 features
- SVM trained on the LDA projection of all features (reduced to 1 component)
- SVM trained on the top 20 SHAP-selected features
- SVM trained on the LDA projection of the 20 SHAP-selected features (reduced to 1 component)

In summary, LDA, in the context of binary classification, can help reduce dimensionality by creating a feature that maximizes class separation, thereby potentially improving classification accuracy. However, because it assumes classes are normally distributed and linearly separable, conditions not fully met in our data, its benefits might be limited. Thus, while LDA is useful for highlighting important class differences, its effectiveness depends on the dataset and should be tested alongside other approaches.

4.3.8 Model Monitoring and Interpretability

Following data preprocessing, feature engineering, normalization, and data balancing with the optimal strategy, an SVM model was trained using the most relevant selected features.

The trained model was then evaluated not only in terms of predictive performance but also for its interpretability, to assess whether the results align with the physical principles underlying avalanche forecasting.

Additionally, the model's stability was examined by analyzing its sensitivity to variations in hyperparameters and fluctuations in the data.

Finally, the model was exported and applied to a real-world case study to evaluate its practical applicability as a forecasting tool. In this real-case application, the results were also interpreted through the lens of physical avalanche phenomena to ensure meaningful and actionable insights.

Testing model performance

The model was evaluated on an unseen test set of 88 samples. Performance was assessed using standard classification metrics, including F1-score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), accuracy, precision, and recall. These were computed from the confusion matrix, which was also plotted to visualize the distribution of true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives. This helped identify specific error types made by the model.

A learning curve was also analyzed to observe how performance evolves with increasing amounts of training data. This provides insight into the model's generalization ability and helps detect signs of overfitting or underfitting by comparing training and test performance across sample sizes.

Lastly, a decision metric curve was used to explore how key metrics (e.g., F1-score, MCC, Heidke Skill Score, Hanssen–Kuipers discriminant) vary as the classification threshold changes. In this study, the optimal

threshold was found to be close to the default value of 0.5, suggesting that threshold tuning offers no significant advantage in this case.

Interpretability of the SVM model

Interpretability is a fundamental aspect when developing predictive models, especially for applications like avalanche forecasting, where understanding model decisions is crucial for operational reliability.

Some models, such as linear regression and decision trees, are intrinsically interpretable, with transparent structures and parameters. However, Support Vector Machines (SVMs), like other black-box models (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting), require post-hoc interpretability techniques to explain their predictions.

Interpretability can be categorized by scope:

- **Global interpretability** aims to understand the model’s overall behavior across the dataset, identifying key features and their relationships with predictions.
- **Local interpretability** focuses on individual predictions, explaining why a specific input was classified in a certain way.

Interpretability methods can be classified as model-specific or model-agnostic based on their reliance on the internal structure of the model.

- **Model-specific methods** utilize the internal mechanics of particular model types (e.g., decision trees or linear regression) to provide direct and often more efficient explanations. However, they cannot be easily generalized to other models.
- **Model-agnostic methods** treat the model as a “black box,” analyzing how changes in inputs affect predictions without requiring knowledge of the model’s internals. This makes them flexible and applicable to any model, including complex ones like SVMs or neural networks, though sometimes at a higher computational cost.

SHAP (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) is a widely used model-agnostic method, especially valuable for interpreting complex, non-linear models such as SVMs.

SHAP is grounded in cooperative game theory and assigns each feature a Shapley value, quantifying its average contribution to the difference between a model’s prediction for a given instance and a baseline expectation. This attribution respects desirable properties such as efficiency (total contribution sums to prediction difference), symmetry, and linearity.

SHAP provides both global explanations (e.g., feature importance summaries) and local explanations (e.g., force plots highlighting influential features for a single prediction).

In this work, we applied the model-agnostic KernelExplainer implementation of SHAP to our SVM classifier. KernelExplainer estimates feature contributions using predicted class probabilities, allowing us to understand how each feature influences the model’s predicted class probabilities, providing a more nuanced view than the predicted label alone.

To use KernelExplainer, we provided:

- A function returning the SVM’s predicted class probabilities.
- A background dataset of scaled training samples to estimate the expected baseline prediction.

We computed SHAP values for each test instance, quantifying the marginal contribution of each feature by considering all possible feature coalitions. This approach yields transparent, instance-level explanations of the SVM model’s decision-making process.

Stability of the Model Using Bootstrap

Bootstrapping is a resampling technique used to estimate the variability of performance metrics by generating multiple datasets through sampling with replacement (Johnson, 2001). It allows us to simulate performance variation without needing new data.

We applied bootstrapping to assess the stability of our Support Vector Machine (SVM) model. Specifically, we generated 50 bootstrap replicates of the test set and calculated the standard deviation of metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, and MCC. Low variability across replicates indicates a robust model, while high variability suggests sensitivity to test data composition.

In addition, we evaluated the stability of the model’s hyperparameters—namely the regularization parameter C and RBF kernel parameter γ . Around the optimal values found via GridSearchCV, we tested neighboring values using bootstrapping to observe how performance varies. This helps verify that our chosen hyperparameters lead not only to high accuracy but also to consistent and generalizable performance (Hastie et al., 2017; Varma and Simon, 2006).

Robustness Evaluation Using Real-World Data

Model Export and Deployment : After training with SHAP-selected features, the SVM model with an RBF kernel ($C = 2$, $\gamma = 0.5$) was exported for real-world application. The export included the MinMaxScaler and SHAP explainer, enabling not only predictions but also interpretation of feature contributions for each case. The `joblib` library was used for efficient saving and loading of these components, ensuring reproducibility and straightforward deployment.

Robustness Evaluation Using Real-World Data : The exported model, along with the scaler and SHAP explainer, was applied to predict avalanche activity during the 2024–2025 winter season, data completely unseen during training and validation (which used data from 1995–1996 to 2023–2024). This new dataset was preprocessed according to the procedures described in data preprocessing and feature engineering. A thorough manual review corrected inconsistencies such as column inversions in air variables, and missing data for 3 of 108 days were imputed using adjacent weather patterns and webcam imagery.

Predictions were compared against observed avalanche events in the Pejo ski area. For each event, weather conditions were analyzed to verify if the avalanche type (e.g., new snow or wet snow) fell within the model’s predictive scope. SHAP values were used to interpret selected predictions, shedding light on the model’s reasoning for both correct classifications and errors.

To evaluate operational viability, daily predictions (simulating morning forecasts) were compared with avalanche observations recorded the following day. This approach tests the model’s ability to forecast avalanche risk over the next 24 hours, aligning with real-time forecasting requirements.

The model’s strong performance on this independent dataset demonstrates its readiness for operational deployment. However, ongoing monitoring and periodic retraining are advised to maintain accuracy and adapt to changing climatic conditions.

Chapter 5

Applications

5.1 Data

5.1.1 Data source

The primary dataset comprises long-term manual snow and weather observations (Mod.1 AINEVA) recorded at the Pejo Tarlenta site, along with avalanche occurrence records spanning the winter seasons from 1980–1981 to 2024–2025.

The Mod.1 AINEVA data for Pejo Tarlenta were downloaded from the official MeteoTrentino web portal: <https://www.meteotrentino.it/index.html#!/content?menuItemDesktop=47>, where individual CSV files are available for each winter season.

To complement the core dataset, meteorological data from automatic weather stations (AWS) located in the Val di Peio area were also evaluated. The goal was to assess their quality and temporal coverage, as well as to identify the limitations that ultimately led to their exclusion from the final modeling framework. Historical AWS records (1985–2024), with variable coverage depending on station and parameter, were accessed via the MeteoTrentino archive at this link: <http://storico.meteotrentino.it/>. Data were manually downloaded by selecting hourly values for each parameter and time range.

Additional data were acquired from an AWS operated by the MeteoMont service of the Italian Army. These data, provided in both hourly and tri-hourly formats, were obtained through an official request to the Comando Truppe Alpine – Sezione MeteoMont. This station has been operational since 2002.

Avalanche activity records were obtained from both the Pejo Tarlenta observation site and the Pejo Funivie ski area management database. While the ski operator has documented major avalanche events since 1999, comprehensive records, including minor events, have only been systematically recorded since 2021.

The purpose of the data collection and analysis was to verify whether the available datasets are suitable for training a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model for avalanche risk forecasting. This requires high-quality, complete data with sufficiently long historical records to ensure an adequate number of samples for model training.

5.1.2 Data Characteristics

Automatic Weather Stations

A preliminary assessment was carried out on AWS stations in the Peio valley to evaluate the suitability of meteorological data to develop a machine learning model for avalanche forecasting. The analysis aimed to determine whether AWS data could serve as reliable input for machine learning models and potentially for physical snow modelling tools such as SNOWPACK.

Measurements: Although the selected stations had long data records, some of them since 1985, and were considered relatively reliable, the analysis revealed critical issues in terms of data quality, continuity, and consistency. These limitations ultimately led to the exclusion of AWS data from the forecasting framework.

AWS stations typically record a range of meteorological parameters relevant to snowpack evolution and avalanche hazard assessment, including:

- **Air temperature:** Measured using thermistors or PT100 sensors; crucial for analyzing temperature fluctuations that influence weak layer formation and variations in snow cohesion.
- **Precipitation:** Recorded with heated tipping-bucket gauges; essential for estimating snow accumulation and snowpack loading. However, during winter, precipitation can be underestimated due to low temperatures, especially since not all rain gauges are heated.
- **Wind speed and direction:** Captured by cup or ultrasonic anemometers and wind vanes; important for detecting wind slab formation and snow redistribution.
- **Solar radiation:** Measured with pyranometers; affects surface melting, crust formation, and the snow’s radiation energy balance.
- **Relative humidity:** Measured with capacitive or resistive hygrometers; influences snow crystal metamorphism and layer cohesion, such as surface hoar formation.
- **Atmospheric pressure:** Measured with digital barometers; generally excluded from avalanche models due to limited direct impact.
- **Snow height:** Measured using ultrasonic sensors that determine the distance from the sensor to the snow surface. Snow depth is then calculated by difference. These sensors are installed in only a few stations, and the data are not publicly available. Additionally, measurements are affected by several issues, including snow interference during snowfall and temperature compensation needs, which reduce data quality and limit usability.

Each AWS station may be equipped with a different combination of sensors. Historical data primarily include temperature, humidity, and precipitation; wind and solar radiation sensors have only been added in more recent years.

Quality Control: Numerous technical and operational challenges emerged during data inspection. Sampling frequencies varied not only between the MeteoTrentino and MeteoMont networks but also within individual stations over time due to hardware upgrades and changes in operational protocols. Aggregation methods (e.g., mean, maximum, cumulative) were often undocumented, reducing interpretability and hindering historical consistency.

Missing values were frequently represented by absent timestamps rather than explicit placeholders, resulting in discontinuous time series. The raw datasets also contained significant anomalies, such as:

- Out-of-range or physically implausible values,
- Extended periods of constant readings due to sensor malfunction,
- Sudden spikes likely caused by environmental interference or hardware failures.

To address these issues, a structured preprocessing pipeline was developed. Time series were first segmented according to sampling consistency, then resampled to a uniform hourly resolution. Quality control steps included variable-specific thresholds, spike and flatline detection, and both temporal and spatial interpolation. Anomaly detection and cleaning were performed using the MeteoIO library (Bavay and Egger, 2014), which is specifically designed for preprocessing meteorological datasets.

Despite these efforts, certain problems remained unresolved. In some cases, valid data were mistakenly removed by aggressive filtering algorithms, while subtle anomalies went undetected. Furthermore, hourly resampling introduced artifacts that affected data integrity at daily scales.

These findings highlight the inherent difficulties of using AWS data collected in high-alpine environments, where extreme weather, unstable power supplies, and limited accessibility often lead to sensor degradation, data outages, and maintenance challenges.

Conclusion: Despite extensive preprocessing, the AWS datasets did not meet the reliability standards necessary for inclusion in a machine learning–based avalanche forecasting model. Issues such as discontinuities in the time series, missing data, noise, and spurious values significantly compromised data usability. The high levels of uncertainty, combined with the risk of introducing artifacts through imputation or filtering and concerns over reproducibility, ultimately led to the decision to exclude AWS data from model training and validation.

Future improvements in sensor durability, standardized logging protocols, and centralized data validation could enhance the usability of AWS data in both operational forecasting and scientific research. Until such improvements are in place, manual snow and weather observations remain the most dependable data source for avalanche hazard modeling in this region.

Snow observation site

The 1PEI Pejo Tarlenta snow observation site, situated at 2000 m a.s.l. within the Pejo ski area (Trentino), it is representative of typical alpine terrain. Managed by MeteoTrentino in collaboration with Pejo Funivie and the Provincial Forestry Service, daily observations are conducted on-site between 7:00 and 10:00 a.m. during the ski season (December–April). Data are transmitted via a telephone and published by MeteoTrentino. Observations follow the AINEVA Mod.1 format (Associazione Interregionale NEve e VAlanghe, 2013), including meteorological and avalanche-related variables. Since 1995, a standardised classification system has been adopted, replacing an earlier, non-uniform coding structure.

Structure and Classification of the Dataset: The Mod.1 AINEVA dataset is organized into four main sections, each representing a distinct category of daily snow and weather observations.

The first section includes meteorological parameters: **WW** (weather conditions), **N** (cloud cover), **V** (visibility), **VQ1** (wind intensity and direction), **VQ2** (presence and distribution of wind slabs and cornices), **TaG** (air temperature at observation time), and **TminG/TmaxG** (daily minimum and maximum temperatures).

The second section describes snowpack properties: **HSnum** (total snow depth), **HNnum** (new snow depth), ρ (new snow density), **TH01G** and **TH03G** (snow temperature at 10 cm and 30 cm depths), **PR** (ram resistance), **CS** (surface characteristics), **S** (surface roughness), and **B** (presence of surface hoar).

The third section reports avalanche activity: **L1** (number and size of observed avalanches), **L2** (avalanche type: dry/wet, slab/loose), **L3** (aspect of release area), **L4** (altitude of release area), **L5** (time of occurrence), and **L6** (trigger: natural or artificial).

The fourth section contains the observer’s daily hazard assessment: **L7** indicates the estimated avalanche danger level on the European Avalanche Danger Scale, while **L8** reflects the forecasted danger trend (increasing, stable, or decreasing), based on EAWS guidelines (European Avalanche Warning Services, 2018) and expert judgment.

Notably, columns **L7** and **L8** represent subjective evaluations by trained observers and are not included in the publicly available downloads. Their interpretation requires contextual information, such as snow stratigraphy, recent meteorological evolution, and terrain factors, and they are not always comparable to official regional avalanche bulletins.

A major structural change occurred in the 1995/1996 season with the adoption of a revised AINEVA coding system, standardizing classification rules and column order. Prior to this, a different format with inconsistent symbols and scales was used. To ensure temporal consistency across the dataset, older entries were reclassified into the updated Mod.1 structure through a custom conversion procedure.

Descriptive Statistics: Table 5.1 provides a summary of the main descriptive statistics for the meteorological and snow-related variables collected through the Mod.1 AINEVA format at the 1PEI Pejo Tarlenta site, spanning the winters from 1980–1981 to 2023–2024. The analysis includes data types, observation counts, percentages of missing values, and basic statistical moments (mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum) for numerical variables. Categorical variables such as cloud cover (**N**), visibility (**V**), wind conditions (**VQ1**, **VQ2**), and surface characteristics (**CS**, **B**) exhibit varying degrees of completeness. Notably, fields such as **VQ1**, **VQ2**, and **CS** show over 40% missingness, largely due to changes in data collection protocols or observer focus over time. In contrast, core meteorological variables such as air temperature at observation

time (**TaG**), snow depth (**HSnum**), and new snow depth (**HNnum**) are well-represented, with less than 5% of entries missing.

For numerical variables, temperature-related fields show realistic value ranges: **TminG** and **TH01G** reach extreme minimums of $-29\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively, consistent with alpine winter conditions. Snowpack-related variables such as total snow depth (**HSnum**, max = 215 cm) and new snow accumulation (**HNnum**, max = 85 cm) exhibit substantial variability, indicating episodic heavy snowfall events. The snow density variable (**rho**) shows high variability as well (standard deviation = 34.38), reflecting the influence of snowfall type, wind compaction, and surface melting or refreezing processes.

Variable	Data Type	Count	Missing (%)	Mean	Std	Min	Max
N	Categorical	4547	213 (4.48%)	—	—	0	8
V	Categorical	4563	197 (4.14%)	—	—	0	8
VQ1	Categorical	2852	1907 (40.09%)	—	—	0	4
VQ2	Categorical	2848	1907 (40.09%)	—	—	0	5
TaG	Numerical \mathbb{Z}	4581	179 (3.76%)	-3.27	5.05	-27	19
TminG	Numerical \mathbb{Z}	4214	545 (11.46%)	-6.47	4.62	-29	7
TmaxG	Numerical \mathbb{Z}	4212	547 (11.50%)	4.98	5.53	-17	27
HSnum	Natural Number \mathbb{N}	4582	178 (3.74%)	68.92	36.68	0	215
HNnum	Natural Number \mathbb{N}	4554	206 (4.33%)	7.71	10.59	0	85
rho	Natural Number \mathbb{N}	3750	1010 (21.23%)	90.60	42.95	0	500
TH01G	Negative Integer \mathbb{Z}_-	4347	411 (8.64%)	-5.52	3.69	-30	0
TH03G	Negative Integer \mathbb{Z}_-	3735	1023 (21.51%)	-3.69	2.80	-27	0
PR	Natural Number \mathbb{N}	4468	291 (6.12%)	18.80	21.21	0	145
CS	Categorical	2825	1934 (40.66%)	—	—	11	25
B	Categorical	2823	1936 (40.70%)	—	—	0	3
L1	Categorical	4421	427 (8.81%)	—	—	0	8
L2	Categorical	4416	432 (8.91%)	—	—	0	6
L3	Categorical	4418	430 (8.87%)	—	—	0	8
L4	Categorical	4419	429 (8.85%)	—	—	0	9
L5	Categorical	4017	831 (17.14%)	—	—	0	6
L6	Categorical	2816	2032 (41.91%)	—	—	0	6

Table 5.1: Descriptive statistics of nivo-meteorological data from the Mod.1 Pejo Tarlenta station covering the period 1980–1981 to 2023–2024

Figure 5.1 visualizes the distributions of selected Mod.1 variables, highlighting skewness, outliers, and multimodal behavior in several cases (e.g., snow depth, temperature). These insights informed subsequent preprocessing and feature engineering steps before model development.

Figure 5.1: Data distribution of variables collected at 1PEI snow observation site

Figure 5.2: Correlation matrix of Mod.1 variables at 1PEI site

The correlation matrix in Figure 5.2 illustrates pairwise relationships among meteorological and snow variables collected at the 1PEI site, revealing linear associations within the dataset.

Strong positive correlations appear between temperatures T_{minG} and TaG (0.84), and between snow temperature $TH01G$ and both T_{minG} (0.78) and TaG (0.74), indicating close links between snow and air temperatures. $TH01G$ and $TH03G$ also correlate highly (0.85), showing consistency between snow temperature measurements. $VQ1$ and $VQ2$ correlate strongly (0.74), likely reflecting similar data.

Notable negative correlations include that between cloud cover (N) and visibility (V) (-0.63), reflecting the expected relationship: clear skies are associated with low cloud cover and high visibility. Another relevant negative correlation is observed between air temperature (TaG) and crust presence (PR) (-0.27), indicating that colder days tend to preserve softer snow conditions, while warmer days promote snow compaction or the formation of melt-freeze crusts.

Variables such as B , CS , and $VQ1$ show generally low correlations, indicating more independence. Overall, the matrix highlights key temperature relationships and some inverse links with precipitation factors.

Conclusion: Overall, the exploratory data analysis confirms the richness and potential of the Mod.1 dataset for avalanche and snowpack studies. However, it also highlights notable data quality issues, especially in optional or observer-dependent fields, with substantial missing values and inconsistencies over time. To fully leverage the dataset, it is essential to implement thorough data cleaning and imputation procedures to handle gaps and outliers effectively. Furthermore, relying solely on single-day observations may limit model performance due to natural variability and noise. Therefore, **feature engineering focused on extracting temporal trends, moving averages, and cumulative variables over multiple days** is crucial to capture meaningful patterns and improve predictive power in downstream modeling tasks. These preprocessing steps will enhance data consistency and enable the development of more robust and reliable avalanche forecasting models.

Avalanches data

A comprehensive exploratory analysis was performed on Mod.1 records with valid avalanche data (fields L1–L6), covering 5038 observation days from 1980 to 2024.

The columns representing avalanche activity, based on the AINEVA classification system (Cagnati, 2013), are listed in the table below:

Variable	Category	Description
L1	Avalanche size	1 = Small avalanches (sluff) 2 = Medium-size avalanches 3 = Many medium-sized avalanches 4 = Single large avalanches 5 = Several large avalanches 6–9 = Old classification
L2	Avalanche type	1 = Surface slab avalanches 2 = Ground slab avalanches 3 = Surface loose snow avalanches 4 = Ground loose snow avalanches 5 = Surface slab + loose snow 6 = Ground slab + loose snow
L3	Aspect	1 = North slopes 2 = East slopes 3 = South slopes 4 = West slopes 5 = Shade slopes 6 = Sunny slopes 7 = All aspects 8 = Sheltered from wind
L4	Elevation	1 = Below 1000 m 2 = 1000–1500 m 3 = Below 1500 m 4 = 1500–2000 m 5 = Below 2000 m 6 = 1800–2300 m 7 = 2300–2800 m 8 = Above 2800 m 9 = Various altitudes
L5	Time of release	1 = 07–11 2 = 11–16 3 = 16–20 4 = During day (07–20) 5 = During night (20–07)

		6 = During 24h
L6	Trigger mechanism	1 = Large group of skiers 2 = Single skier 3 = Explosive trigger: no release 4 = Explosive trigger: small/medium avalanches 5 = Explosive trigger: large avalanches 6 = Snow groomer release

Table 5.2: Description of avalanche-related categorical variables (L1 to L6) from the Codice Nivometeorologico (Associazione Interregionale NEve e VALanghe, 2013)

Number of avalanches per season: Avalanches were recorded on 668 days, averaging about 13 avalanche days per winter season. Variations in seasonal frequency reflect both year-to-year changes in snowpack conditions and shifts in the monitored area’s spatial coverage.

Figure 5.3: Number of days with avalanches (blue), no avalanches (orange), and missing data (grey) per winter season

Despite some variability, a notable increase in avalanche activity is observed after the 2011/2012 season. This trend coincides with the reopening of the Val de la Mite sector, closed since the major avalanche of February 1986 that destroyed the chairlift, and the inclusion of additional terrain in the monitoring area. These changes likely improved the detection of avalanche events, particularly at higher elevations and on northeast to southeast-facing slopes.

We observe a significant class imbalance in the target variable, with avalanche events (class 1, blue bars) being much rarer than non-avalanche instances (class 0, orange bars). This pronounced imbalance poses challenges for model training and may lead to biased predictions favouring the majority class. To address this issue, dataset balancing techniques are necessary to ensure more reliable and equitable model performance.

Sizes and Types of avalanches: Here we present the classification of avalanche sizes (with numeric codes) and avalanche types recorded in columns L1 and L2 of Mod.1.

Figure 5.4: Avalanche distribution by size (top) and type (bottom)

The classification of avalanche sizes (L1, upper panel) shows a nearly balanced distribution between small avalanches (sluffs), with 308 events, and medium to large avalanches, in total 351 events when combining classes 2 through 9. Single or few avalanches occur more frequently than multiple releases, indicating that avalanche prediction is likely related to local characteristics rather than a widespread avalanche problem.

The lower panel shows the classification of avalanche types (L2). Loose snow avalanches (orange) are the most common and typically originate within the snowpack, whereas avalanches reaching the ground occur less frequently. Slab avalanches (blue) are less represented, as slab formation is primarily associated with windy conditions. When both avalanche types occur together (violet), this may indicate new snow accumulation combined with wind influence.

Seasonality and Geographical Distribution of Avalanches Avalanche occurrences are strongly influenced by seasonal weather dynamics and the geographical characteristics of mountainous regions. Understanding both the temporal evolution and the spatial distribution of avalanches is essential for accurate risk assessment and the development of effective prevention strategies. This section examines how avalanche frequency varies throughout the winter season and how it is distributed across different slope aspects and elevation bands.

Figure 5.5: Seasonality of avalanche types: Slab, Loose Snow, and Mixed-type

Figure 5.5 shows the weekly mean number of avalanches, grouped by type, Slab (blue line), Loose Snow (orange line), and Mixed-type (violet line), over the core winter months (December to April). Loose Snow avalanches exhibit a consistently higher mean frequency than the other types, peaking around early March. In contrast, Slab avalanches show a more modest peak in mid-March. The number of Mixed-type avalanches remains consistently low throughout the season. Due to the relatively low absolute counts of slab and mixed-type avalanches, often fewer than 10 events per week, statistical interpretation of these patterns should be approached with caution. Additionally, reduced data availability during the final weeks of the winter season (e.g., April), often corresponding to varying ski area closure dates, may influence the shape and reliability of the observed trends.

The geographical distribution of avalanche occurrences helps to identify not only where avalanches are most frequent, but also offers insight into why they occur. This distribution is closely tied to topographical features, such as slope aspect and elevation. In our dataset, 174 avalanches occurred on south-facing slopes between 2300 and 2800 meters above sea level. This corresponds to the Val de la Mite region, which also recorded the most intense avalanche activity overall.

As illustrated in Figure 5.6, this pattern suggests that solar radiation is a major contributing factor in triggering avalanches in this area. These avalanches are predominantly of the loose snow type, further supporting the hypothesis that diurnal warming and solar exposure are the primary drivers of avalanche activity on south-facing slopes. This aligns with the seasonal peak in loose snow avalanches discussed earlier.

Figure 5.6: Geographical distribution of avalanches by aspect and elevation

Conclusion This exploratory analysis highlights that loose snow avalanches are the most frequently observed type in the study area, particularly on south-facing slopes and within the 2300–2800 m elevation band. These avalanches exhibit a strong seasonal pattern, with a peak in early March, and are primarily influenced by solar radiation and daily warming cycles. Given their prevalence, clear triggering mechanisms, and distinct seasonality, **loose snow avalanches were selected** as the modeling target for subsequent predictive analyses. Slab avalanches, being less frequent and more spatially heterogeneous, were excluded from the modeling scope to reduce complexity and improve model reliability. Furthermore, the target classes are highly imbalanced, with avalanche events being much rarer than non-avalanche instances; therefore, **class balancing techniques are essential** to ensure robust and unbiased model training.

5.2 Feature Engineering for Avalanche Forecasting

5.2.1 New variable creation

Based on the literature (McClung, 2023; Schweizer and Fohn, 1996; Pozdnoukhov et al., 2011; Součková et al., 2022; Pérez-Guillén et al., 2022; Viallon-Galinier, 2022), many studies highlight the importance of capturing the temporal evolution of daily observations to improve the accuracy of avalanche release probability estimation. In this context, we developed a set of new features derived from manual observations, designed to enhance avalanche forecasting models. These features serve as inputs to a machine learning framework, which will evaluate their predictive relevance.

The newly derived variables include multiple temporal windows to better capture relevant phenomena, such as intense snowfall over short periods and prolonged warm spells.

A particularly illustrative example is the Snow Water Equivalent (SWE). Snowfall characteristics can vary significantly with elevation, for instance, rainfall at 1500 m, heavy snow at 2000 m, and lighter snow at 3000 m. While fresh snow height (HN) may fluctuate considerably, total precipitation tends to remain more stable, aside from elevation-dependent trends. By calculating SWE as the product of fresh snow height and

adjusted snow density, we obtain a more physically meaningful measure of precipitation effects, offering a robust indicator for avalanche risk assessment.

Below, alongside the original variables in Model 1, we list the newly engineered variables with descriptions of their calculation methods:

1. Basic Meteorological and Snow Parameters

Daily measurements characterizing atmospheric and snowpack conditions:

- **DayOfSeason**: Day count since December 1, marking seasonal progression. An indicator of potential solar radiation.

2. Wind-Related Features

Variables describing wind activity and snow transport processes:

- **SnowDrift_1d** to **SnowDrift_5d**: Summed snow drift indices over 1 to 5 days, computed by rolling sums of daily wind intensity.

3. Snow Depth Variation

- Recent snow depth changes over various time windows:

$$HS_delta_xd = HS_{today} - HS_{today-x} \quad \text{for } x \in \{1, 2, 3, 5\} \text{ days}$$

4. Cumulative New Snowfall

Aggregated new snowfall amounts:

- Snowfall amount over the last x days

$$HN_xd = \sum_{i=1}^x HN_{today-i} \quad \text{for } x \in \{2, 3, 5\} \text{ days}$$

- Snow water equivalent of snowfall

$$\text{FreshSWE} = \frac{HN \times \rho_{adjusted}}{100}$$

where $\rho_{adjusted}$ is the adjusted snow density (kg/m^3); if missing, a default of $100 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ is used.

- **SeasonalSWE_cum** is incremented daily by **FreshSWE**, representing cumulative SWE for the season.

5. Snowfall Timing

- **DaysSinceLastSnow**: Days elapsed since the last measurable snowfall, counting days with zero new snow.

6. Aggregated Temperature Statistics

Minimum and maximum air temperatures over moving windows:

- Minimum temperature over the last x days

$$T_{min,xd} = \min [T_{min,today-x+1}, \dots, T_{min,today}]$$

- Maximum temperature over the last x days

$$T_{max,xd} = \max [T_{max,today-x+1}, \dots, T_{max,today}]$$

for $x \in \{2, 3, 5\}$ days.

7. Temperature Amplitudes and Gradients

- Daily temperature amplitude:

$$\Delta T_{xd} = T_{max,xd} - T_{min,xd} \quad \text{for } x \in \{1, 2, 3, 5\}$$

- Snowpack temperature gradient:

$$TempGrad_HS = \frac{T_{10cm} - T_{ground}}{HS}$$

where $T_{ground} = 0^\circ C$.

8. Temperature Trend (Delta) Features

Changes in air temperature over recent days:

- Delta air temperature over the last x days:

$$TaG_{\Delta(xd)} = TaG_{today} - TaG_{today-x}$$

- Delta minimum air temperature over the last x days:

$$TminG_{\Delta(xd)} = TminG_{today} - TminG_{today-x}$$

- Delta maximum air temperature over the last x days:

$$TmaxG_{\Delta(xd)} = TmaxG_{today} - TmaxG_{today-x}$$

for $x \in \{1, 2, 3, 5\}$ days.

9. Mean Air Temperature

$$T_{mean} = \frac{T_{max} + T_{min}}{2}$$

10. Precipitation Accumulation

Total precipitation over multiple time windows, converted from SWE:

$$Precip_{xd} = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \frac{HN_{today-i} \times \rho_{adjusted, today-i}}{100}$$

for $d \in \{1, 2, 3, 5\}$ days.

11. Snow Surface Temperature Variation

Changes in snow surface temperature:

$$T_{snow\Delta,xd} = T_{10cm,today} - T_{10cm,today-x}$$

for $x \in \{2, 3, 5\}$ days.

12. Snow Surface Characteristics

Qualitative descriptors:

- **SnowConditionIndex**: Categorizes snow temperature at 10 cm as cold ($< -10^\circ C$), warm ($-10^\circ C \leq T_{10cm} < -2^\circ C$), or wet ($\geq -2^\circ C$)
- **MFCrust_present**: Presence of melt-freeze crust
- **NewMFCrust**: Indicator of newly formed crust
- **ConsecCrustsDays**: Duration in days of continuous crust presence

13. Wet Snow Conditions

Indicators of wet snow:

- `WetSnow_CS`: Binary wet snow index from surface observation
- `WetSnow_Temperature`: Binary indicator when snow temperature at 10 cm exceeds -1°C
- `ConsecWetSnowDays`: Number of consecutive days with wet snow

14. Snow Temperature Transformations

Hyperbolic tangent transformations to emphasize temperatures near freezing:

- Hyperbolic tangent snow temperature at 10 cm of depth.

$$\text{TH10_tanh} = \tanh(T_{10\text{cm}})$$

- Hyperbolic tangent snow temperature at 30 cm of depth.

$$\text{TH30_tanh} = \tanh(T_{30\text{cm}})$$

These engineered features not only represent instantaneous measurements but also capture temporal trends and cumulative processes, thereby enhancing the predictive power of avalanche release models.

5.2.2 Final consideration

A total of 68 features were initially generated through extensive feature engineering, capturing various meteorological, snowpack, and temporal dynamics derived from the Mod.1 dataset, which spans the winter seasons from 1995–1996 to 2023–2024.

The correlation matrix (Figure 5.7) reveals key structural patterns among the engineered variables, identifying groups of highly correlated features, particularly among temperature-, snow-, and precipitation-related indicators. These clusters reflect shared physical processes and suggest redundancy, especially in temporally-derived variables computed over 1-day, 3-day, and 5-day windows. In such cases, the inclusion of all correlated variables may introduce multicollinearity, which can impair model interpretability and stability. Consequently, dimensionality reduction or careful **feature selection becomes essential**.

Some variables, such as `SnowDrift`, exhibit low correlation with other features, suggesting they may carry independent and potentially valuable information for avalanche prediction. These insights informed a targeted refinement process aimed at reducing feature redundancy while preserving predictive diversity.

Before model training, a manual exclusion step was performed based on domain knowledge and physical interpretability. Specifically, features such as `N` (cloud cover) and `V` (visibility) were removed due to their transient nature and limited physical relevance to avalanche triggering mechanisms. Similarly, wind-related variables (`VQ1`, `VQ2`) and snow transport indicators (`SnowDrift_1d` through `SnowDrift_5d`) were excluded, as the focus of this work does not include wind slab avalanches, which are highly dependent on localized topography and difficult to generalize in statistical models.

Further removals included `FreshSWE` and `SeasonalSWE_cum`, both of which were found to be redundant due to high correlation with recent precipitation and cumulative snow depth, respectively. Wet snow variables (`WetSnow_CS`, `WetSnow_Temperature`, `ConsecWetSnowDays`, `SnowConditionIndex`) and crust-related indicators (`MF_Crust_Present`, `New_MF_Crust`, `ConsecCrustDays`) were also excluded, as they tend to be site-specific and do not reliably reflect conditions across diverse avalanche paths.

Lastly, we removed `TH10_tanh` and `TH30_tanh`, which are hyperbolic tangent transformations intended to approximate normality. While statistically motivated, these features compromised physical interpretability and were not essential for our model design philosophy, which prioritized transparency and explainability.

Figure 5.7: Correlation matrix of engineered features

As a result of these refinement steps, the feature set was reduced from 68 to 39 well-justified and non-redundant variables. Although dimensionality reduction techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) are often employed to address multicollinearity, particularly in kernel-based models like Support Vector Machines (SVMs), we intentionally opted against this approach. Retaining standardized, physically meaningful features allows for better interpretability of model outputs and facilitates insight into avalanche-relevant processes. Instead, feature relevance was assessed through model-based selection methods integrated with the SVM framework and validated via cross-validation.

The resulting set of 39 features forms the basis for subsequent model development. The next step involves addressing class imbalance in the dataset, a critical challenge for avalanche prediction given the naturally skewed distribution between avalanche and non-avalanche events.

5.3 Balancing the Imbalanced Datasets

Experimental Setup

Class imbalance represents a critical challenge in avalanche prediction, where the minority class, avalanche days, must be detected reliably despite being underrepresented. To address this, we conducted four experiments to evaluate various resampling techniques applied to Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification, focusing on their ability to improve model performance under different feature and target configurations.

The experiments are defined as follows:

- **Case 1:** Using two key features (HSnum: snow height, and HN_3d: total fresh snow over 3 days) with all avalanche events included.
- **Case 2:** Using a comprehensive set of 39 features derived from weather and snow data, with all avalanches.
- **Case 3:** Same two features as Case 1, but filtering the dataset to include only medium and large avalanches, excluding small localized events.
- **Case 4:** Same 39 features as Case 2, but filtered to medium and large avalanches.

For each case, the data was split into 75% training and 25% testing subsets. All features were normalized to the $[0,1]$ range to prevent bias due to scale differences. SVM parameters C and γ were optimized using a grid search with cross-validation, searching over wide ranges $[0.001, 1000]$ for C and $[0.0001, 100]$ for γ . The Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel was used throughout.

We evaluated the models primarily using the F1-score and the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), as these metrics balance precision and recall, particularly important to minimize false negatives (missed avalanche days).

Comparative Analysis

Table 5.3 summarizes the F1-score and MCC for each resampling method across the four experimental cases.

	Method	F1-score				MCC			
		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
	<i>No resampling</i>	<i>0.572</i>	<i>0.663</i>	<i>0.588</i>	<i>0.576</i>	<i>0.244</i>	<i>0.370</i>	<i>0.305</i>	<i>0.167</i>
Undersampling	Random	0.649	0.734	0.621	0.744	0.318	0.469	0.289	0.487
	Random 10d	0.593	0.687	0.585	0.616	0.195	0.375	0.183	0.234
	NearMiss v3, k=1	0.621	0.646	0.634	0.670	0.256	0.292	0.268	0.347
	NearMiss v3, k=3	0.674	0.634	0.739	0.610	0.369	0.270	0.492	0.228
	NearMiss v3, k=5	0.663	0.621	0.757	0.692	0.360	0.242	0.528	0.396
	NearMiss v3, k=10	0.684	0.672	0.757	0.616	0.427	0.344	0.528	0.232
	NearMiss v3, k=25	0.684	0.711	0.740	0.638	0.402	0.424	0.486	0.277
	NearMiss v3, k=50	0.663	0.683	0.760	0.681	0.360	0.366	0.574	0.371
	CNN	0.610	0.685	0.523	0.567	0.298	0.370	0.083	0.145
	ENN	0.690	0.740	0.693	0.663	0.450	0.489	0.484	0.351
	Cluster Centroids	0.674	0.687	0.608	0.666	0.348	0.378	0.313	0.350
	Tomek Links	0.595	0.672	0.588	0.642	0.262	0.367	0.279	0.306
Oversampling	Random	0.626	0.442	0.543	0.477	0.260	0.000	0.114	0.000
	SMOTE	0.574	0.491	0.570	0.577	0.173	0.110	0.198	0.193

ADASYN	0.575	0.499	0.516	0.533	0.191	0.096	0.108	0.129
SVMSMOTE	0.620	0.491	0.580	0.579	0.242	0.110	0.163	0.204

Table 5.3: Performance comparison of SVM using various resampling methods across four experimental cases; metrics reported: F1-score and MCC

Table 5.3 present the F1-score and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) for each resampling technique. The first row of the table reports the baseline performance without any resampling, where the dataset remains imbalanced.

Bold numbers in the table highlight the methods that achieve the best performance in each test case (Cases 1 to 4), allowing for quick identification of the most effective strategies.

Overall, balancing methods tend to improve predictive performance, particularly in higher-dimensional feature spaces (Cases 2 and 4). In contrast, simpler feature spaces (Cases 1 and 3) generally exhibit more limited gains, highlighting the importance of richer feature representations for capturing the complex physical processes underlying avalanche formation. An important exception is the NearMiss undersampling method, which performs competitively even in these lower-dimensional scenarios, suggesting that carefully designed undersampling techniques can still yield meaningful improvements when data complexity is limited.

Filtering out small avalanches during training (as done in Cases 2 and 4) consistently enhances the performance of many resampling strategies. This supports the hypothesis that small avalanches, often caused by localized snowpack instabilities, are less representative and introduce noise, which negatively affects model generalization within the Mod.1 dataset.

Models trained without any resampling (*No Resampling*) frequently exhibit signs of overfitting, especially evident in Case 4 where performance sharply declines (MCC = 0.231). Although some cases, such as Case 3, show moderate predictive ability without resampling, the high variability and poorer generalization observed across cases reinforce the necessity of balancing techniques for stable and reliable deployment. This limitation is visually emphasized in the heatmap by the predominance of red-colored cells in MCC values corresponding to the *No Resampling* baseline.

Comparing resampling approaches, undersampling techniques consistently outperform oversampling methods across all cases in both F1-score and MCC metrics. Oversampling strategies such as SMOTE and ADASYN underperform, particularly in high-dimensional feature spaces, likely due to their limited ability to accurately model the complex, sparse minority class distribution of avalanche events. Furthermore, these methods risk overfitting by introducing synthetic samples that may not reflect realistic data patterns. In contrast, undersampling reduces dataset size but leads to simpler and more robust models with improved generalization.

Among undersampling techniques, Edited Nearest Neighbours (ENN) stands out by achieving the highest MCC values in Case 1 (0.450) and Case 2 (0.489). NearMiss v3 exhibits strong performance in Case 3, especially with larger neighborhood sizes (e.g., $k = 50$), indicating that a broader data context can enhance generalization in lower-dimensional spaces, although its performance is less consistent across other cases.

Random Undersampling, while not always the top performer, delivers consistently solid results across all scenarios (e.g., MCC = 0.469 in Case 2 and 0.487 in Case 4). Its simplicity, computational efficiency, and stability make it a pragmatic and robust choice for operational use. These qualities, coupled with reliable performance in the most realistic and challenging conditions (Cases 2 and 4), justify its selection for further analysis.

It is important to recognize that not all balancing methods yield improvements over the *No Resampling* baseline. Notably, certain oversampling techniques can impair performance, particularly regarding MCC, revealing the potential pitfalls of applying unsuitable resampling strategies. This emphasizes the necessity of carefully selecting methods that align with the underlying data characteristics and the complexity of the task. When an appropriate resampling approach is employed, model performance is significantly enhanced, highlighting the effectiveness of tailored balancing techniques in mitigating class imbalance.

In summary, these results highlight the crucial importance of selecting appropriate resampling strategies to address dataset imbalance. This step lays a solid foundation for effective feature selection and reliable model development in the subsequent stages.

Final Method Selection

The comparative analysis of the resampling techniques clearly shows that undersampling methods consistently outperform oversampling approaches in terms of both F1-score and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). This trend is especially evident in Cases 2 and 4, which include a richer set of predictive variables and exclude small-scale avalanche events, thereby representing more realistic operational conditions.

Among the tested techniques, Random Undersampling stands out as the best compromise between performance and implementation simplicity:

- **F1-score:** 0.734 (Case 2), 0.744 (Case 4), among the highest observed
- **MCC:** 0.469 (Case 2), 0.487 (Case 4), indicating a strong correlation between predictions and actual outcomes

Although more advanced methods such as **Edited Nearest Neighbours (ENN)** and **NearMiss v3** (with high k values) marginally outperform Random Undersampling in some cases (e.g., ENN in Case 2: MCC = 0.489; NearMiss v3 $k = 50$ in Case 3: MCC = 0.574), they are more sensitive to parameter tuning and computationally expensive. This limits their applicability in real-time or large-scale operational contexts.

Advantages of Random Undersampling

- **Computational efficiency:** Lightweight and fast, making it suitable for real-time operational pipelines with resource constraints
- **Simplicity and transparency:** Unlike oversampling methods (e.g., SMOTE or ADASYN), it does not generate synthetic data, thus avoiding artificial or unrealistic patterns—an important consideration in safety-critical systems
- **Strong performance in realistic scenarios:** In Cases 2 and 4 (rich feature space + exclusion of small avalanches)

In summary, Random Undersampling offers a strategically sound and operationally efficient choice for the continuation of this study. It will be adopted as the reference resampling technique in the following chapters on variable selection, ensuring consistent and realistic model performance evaluations across operational scenarios.

5.4 Feature selection

In this section, we present the results of the feature selection process aimed at identifying the most informative subset of features to enhance the SVM model's performance. For each evaluated method, we report the key features selected based on their impact on classification metrics. These selections were derived using metrics and algorithms specifically suited to each resampling technique. Finally, a comparative analysis highlights the features that consistently contribute to improved performance across methods, pinpointing the best candidates for use in subsequent modeling steps.

ANOVA f-test

To identify the most relevant features for our predictive models, we employed the ANOVA F-test, which ranks features based on mean differences between classes. The selection process involved varying the number of selected features, k , from 1 to 39, the total remaining after removing highly correlated variables and site-specific snow field measurements introduced during feature engineering.

Model performance was assessed for each value of k . Although peak performance occurred at $k = 35$, a more compact subset of 10 features achieved comparable results. This subset was therefore selected to balance predictive accuracy with computational efficiency.

Figure 5.8 summarizes these results, showing how the F1-score, MCC, precision, accuracy, and recall change as the number of selected features increases. The curves indicate that performance stabilizes after about 15 to 20 features, suggesting limited gains from adding more variables.

Figure 5.8: Performance of feature subsets selected via ANOVA

The final 10-feature subset includes:

HSnum, TH01G, TH03G, HS_delta_1d, TminG_delta_5d, TmaxG_delta_5d, Precip_2d, Precip_3d, Precip_5d, TempGrad_HS.

The ANOVA F-test provides a fast and interpretable approach to feature selection, making it suitable as a preliminary method for SVMs with RBF kernels. It simplifies the model, reduces training time, and lowers the risk of overfitting by eliminating uninformative features.

However, the method has limitations: it assumes linear relationships and assesses each feature independently, ignoring potential interactions. As a result, features that are important only in combination, or those contributing nonlinearly, may be overlooked. Given that RBF kernels capture complex, high-dimensional patterns, relying solely on ANOVA could exclude valuable information.

In conclusion, the ANOVA F-test offers a strong starting point for feature selection, but it should ideally be complemented by techniques that consider feature interactions and nonlinearity to fully exploit the modeling capacity of RBF-based SVMs.

Permutation Ranking

To further refine the feature subset, we applied permutation importance, a model-agnostic technique that measures the impact of each feature on the model's predictive accuracy by randomly shuffling its values and observing the resulting performance drop. Features causing a larger decrease in accuracy are deemed more important. After preprocessing and training, each feature's importance score was calculated as the average accuracy reduction over 100 permutations to ensure statistical robustness.

Figure 5.9 presents the permutation importance scores for all features, ranked by their impact on the model's F1-score. Features marked in blue contribute to the top 95% of cumulative importance and exceed the significance threshold (gray dashed line at 0.0044). Features shown in red fall below this threshold and were excluded from further modeling steps.

The ranking revealed a separation between features with strong influence and those with minimal contribution. To identify the most informative subset, we selected the group of features that together accounted for 95% of the cumulative reduction in model accuracy. This approach led to a compact yet expressive set of predictors that retained most of the model's predictive power, while also reducing complexity and enhancing interpretability.

The 13 features selected through permutation importance are:

HSnum, HS_delta_5d, Tsnow_delta_3d, HS_delta_2d, PR, HS_delta_1d, TminG_delta_3d, TmaxG_delta_5d, DayOfSeason, TmaxG_delta_3d, TmaxG_delta_2d, TH01G, Precip_3d.

These features are considered the most informative for predicting avalanche occurrences under the tested configuration.

Despite its advantages, permutation importance presents some limitations. First, it is computationally intensive, especially with non-linear models such as SVMs with RBF kernels. Second, when features are highly correlated, the importance of one may be underestimated, as the model can rely on its counterpart. Finally, the method assesses features individually, without capturing potential interaction effects, which are especially relevant in non-linear models.

Figure 5.9: Feature importance via permutation ranking (F1-score)

Backward Feature Elimination (BFE)

Backward Feature Elimination (BFE) was performed using a Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel. The macro-averaged F1-score was used as the primary performance metric. Starting from the full set of 39 features, the algorithm iteratively removed the least informative feature, retraining the model at each step to assess the change in performance.

Figure 5.10 shows how the F1-macro score evolves with the number of features. Performance stabilizes after 11 variables, supporting the decision to favor a smaller, more interpretable model.

Figure 5.10: F1-score vs. number of selected features during backward feature elimination

The highest F1-macro score was achieved with 22 features; however, a more compact subset of 11 features yielded nearly identical results. This allows for a more interpretable model without significant loss in performance.

The selected 11 features are:

```
HSnum, TH03G, HS_delta_1d, HS_delta_5d, TempAmplitude_2d, TminG_delta_3d,
TminG_delta_5d, TmaxG_delta_3d, TmaxG_delta_5d, Precip_3d, Tsnow_delta_3d.
```

This reduced set simplifies the model, decreases training time, and highlights the most relevant meteorological and snowpack-related variables for avalanche prediction.

Despite its strengths, BFE is computationally demanding, particularly when used with nonlinear kernels like RBF. To address this, a reduced 7×7 hyperparameter grid was employed, keeping the training time within a few hours, acceptable for practical applications.

In summary, BFE proved to be a robust and interpretable feature selection method, effectively identifying a compact and high-performing feature subset. However, its high computational cost limits the feasibility of using a fine-grained hyperparameter grid during the selection phase, potentially constraining the thoroughness of SVM performance evaluation.

Forward Feature Selection (FFS)

Similarly to BFE, Forward Feature Selection (FFS) was performed using a Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel. The macro-averaged F1-score served as the evaluation metric, given its suitability for imbalanced classification problems. In contrast to Backward Feature Elimination, FFS starts with an empty feature set and iteratively adds the feature that yields the greatest improvement in model performance at each step.

Figure 5.11 illustrates the evolution of the F1-score as a function of the number of selected features. The performance curve highlights a clear improvement in predictive accuracy with additional features, followed by a plateau, indicating diminishing returns beyond a certain subset size.

Figure 5.11: F1-score vs. number of selected features during forward feature selection

The highest F1-score was obtained with a subset of 22 features:

```
TaG, HSnum, HS_delta_2d, HS_delta_3d, DaysSinceLastSnow, Tmin_2d,
TempAmplitude_1d, TempAmplitude_2d, TempAmplitude_3d, TaG_delta_2d, TaG_delta_3d, TminG_delta_1d,
TminG_delta_2d, TminG_delta_3d, TmaxG_delta_5d, T_mean, Precip_1d, Precip_2d, Precip_3d,
TempGrad_HS, Tsnow_delta_2d, Tsnow_delta_5d
```

This feature set captures a broad spectrum of meteorological and snowpack indicators, including snow depth variation, recent precipitation, temperature gradients, and multi-day temperature amplitudes, all of which are critical for modeling avalanche dynamics.

A small subset of only four features (HSnum, HS_delta_2d, HS_delta_3d, TempGrad_HS) also achieved reasonable performance. However, this minimal configuration lacked the representational complexity required to capture non-linear interactions and temporal dependencies essential to accurately modelling avalanche formation processes. In this case, the 22-feature model offers a more favourable balance between complexity and predictive performance.

Overall, Forward Feature Selection proved to be an effective approach for building a performant and interpretable model, successfully identifying the most informative predictors of avalanche occurrence. However, like Backward Feature Elimination, its applicability is limited by the significant computational resources required for thorough feature evaluation.

Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV)

Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV) was employed to identify the most informative subset of features for avalanche prediction. The final model used a Support Vector Classifier (SVC) with an RBF kernel, while feature ranking during elimination was performed with a LinearSVC for computational efficiency.

RFECV iteratively removes the least important features and evaluates model performance using cross-validation at each step. The optimal subset is selected based on the highest average macro F1-score across folds.

Figure 5.12 illustrates the F1-score progression throughout the elimination process, confirming performance peaks at 9 features. Including additional features beyond this point does not improve performance and may even slightly degrade it due to overfitting or redundancy.

The procedure identified an optimal subset of 9 features:

```
HSnum, TH01G, PR, HS_delta_1d, HS_delta_5d, TminG_delta_3d, TminG_delta_5d,
TmaxG_delta_3d, Precip_3d.
```

This compact set balances dimensionality reduction with predictive performance, capturing key avalanche-related factors such as snowpack depth, recent changes, precipitation, and temperature dynamics.

Figure 5.12: F1-score vs. number of selected features during recursive feature elimination with cross-validation

Despite its strengths, RFECV has limitations. The LinearSVC used for ranking assumes linear relationships, which may not fully represent the non-linear interactions modeled by the final RBF SVM. Consequently, features valuable in non-linear combinations might be undervalued or excluded.

Moreover, RFECV evaluates feature importance independently, overlooking complex interdependencies common in non-linear models. As a result, features weak in isolation but influential in combination may be mistakenly discarded.

SHAP

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) is used for feature selection to retain variables that improve model performance and discard those that hinder it. By quantifying each feature’s contribution to predictions, SHAP enables both local and global interpretability, particularly useful for complex models like SVMs with RBF kernels. This enables us to isolate key features and construct a simpler, more interpretable model without compromising accuracy.

Methodology and Experimental Setup

The SHAP analysis was conducted on a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model using a radial basis function (RBF) kernel, with optimized hyperparameters C and γ . The optimized hyperparameter was calculated via Grid Search + Cross Validation on a random undersampled dataset with the 39 features obtained after domain-knowledge selection from feature engineering.

The objective of this analysis is to assess the relative importance of each feature in contributing to avalanche predictions (positive class). SHAP values were computed for each instance in the dataset, and the mean absolute SHAP value was calculated per feature. This aggregation provides a global view of feature relevance, independent of directionality (positive or negative influence), allowing us to identify which variables consistently impact the model’s decisions.

This setup enables a robust, interpretable evaluation of model behavior and supports both feature selection and model debugging. Features with high SHAP importance are candidates for retention in the final model, while those with negligible contributions can be excluded to improve model efficiency and generalization.

The SHAP values were calculated using the KernelExplainer, which is suitable for black-box models like SVMs. The resulting importances were aggregated and visualized in a sorted bar chart, offering a clear view of the most influential variables in the model’s decision-making process.

Global Feature Importance

We selected the most relevant features using the Cumulative SHAP Contribution method. This approach identifies the smallest subset of features that collectively account for 95% of the total sum of mean absolute SHAP values, ensuring that only the most impactful predictors are retained while reducing dimensionality, following a strategy similar to that adopted with Permutation Importance Ranking.

Figure 5.13 displays a bar plot showing the global importance of each feature, based on SHAP values for predicting avalanche events (class 1). The plot ranks features according to the mean of their absolute SHAP values, which reflects the average contribution of each feature to the model’s predictions, irrespective of whether the effect is positive or negative. Blue bars indicate the selected features, while red bars represent those excluded. The solid yellow line marks the threshold corresponding to 95% of the cumulative sum of mean absolute SHAP values.

Based on this criterion, 18 features were selected:

```
HSnum, TH01G, PR, DayOfSeason, TmaxG_delta_5d, TH03G, HS_delta_5d, HS_delta_1d, TmaxG_delta_3d,
Precip_3d, TempGrad_HS, HS_delta_2d, TmaxG_delta_2d, TminG_delta_5d, Tsnow_delta_3d,
TminG_delta_3d, TaG_delta_5d, TmaxG_delta_1d
```

The top five features `HSnum`, `TH01G`, `PR`, `DayOfSeason`, and `TmaxG_delta_5d` demonstrate the highest impact on model predictions. The first 10–15 features show a significant contribution. At the same time, the importance drops sharply after the 25th feature, suggesting that these lower-ranked features are less informative or may introduce noise, making them less useful for avalanche forecasting.

There is a notable influence of snow-related and thermal variables, which is consistent with the nature of the classification task, assessing conditions likely to lead to avalanche activity.

Rapid Thermal variation, as captured by the 3–5 day variations in temperature (e.g., `TmaxG_delta_5d`, `TminG_delta_3d`), appears to be highly predictive, indicating that rapid temperature changes are an important precursor to avalanche events.

The inclusion of `DayOfSeason` among the top features highlights the presence of a strong seasonal pattern in the target variable, which aligns with the known seasonality of avalanche occurrences. This suggests the relation with the solar radiation, which is not directly measured and evaluated in the dataset

Interestingly, PR (penetration resistance) ranks highly, suggesting that the presence of soft layers (either dry or wet) near the snow surface may be a key indicator of instability and potential avalanche release.

Additionally, derived variables such as HS_delta_5d, tend to be more informative than raw measurements. This emphasizes the relevance of dynamic behavior (i.e., changes over time) over static conditions in identifying avalanche-prone scenarios.

Figure 5.13: Global feature importance based on mean absolute SHAP values

Incremental Feature Addition

A more robust, performance-driven approach was Incremental Feature Addition. Guided by SHAP-based feature importance rankings, features were added one at a time in descending order of importance. Model performance was evaluated at each step, and the process was halted once additional features no longer improved or began to degrade performance, indicating redundancy or negative contribution.

Figure 5.14 illustrates how performance metrics evolve with the incremental inclusion of features.

Figure 5.14: Performance of feature subsets selected via SHAP values

A noticeable increase in model performance can be observed when incorporating the first 16 to 20 features. This suggests that the majority of the model’s predictive power is captured within this subset. Beyond approximately 25 to 30 features, the performance either stabilizes or begins to slightly decline, indicating that additional features may introduce noise or redundancy rather than contributing meaningful information.

The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), represented by the purple line, starts at a lower value and increases more gradually. Given its sensitivity to class imbalance, MCC provides a robust measure of binary classification quality. Its trend generally follows that of the F1-score but with greater variability, reflecting its stricter assessment of performance.

This analysis confirms the validity of the SHAP-based feature ranking by directly linking feature importance to classification performance. It also highlights an optimal feature count of 20, as a balance between model complexity and predictive accuracy. Selecting features beyond this threshold offers limited benefit and may lead to overfitting, emphasizing the importance of dimensionality reduction for enhancing generalization.

The 20 selected features are:

```
HSnum, TH01G, PR, DayOfSeason, TmaxG_delta_5d, HS_delta_5d, TH03G, HS_delta_1d, TmaxG_delta_3d,
Precip_3d, TempGrad_HS, HS_delta_2d, TmaxG_delta_2d, TminG_delta_5d, TminG_delta_3d,
Tsnow_delta_3d, TaG_delta_5d, Tsnow_delta_1d, TmaxG_delta_1d, Precip_2d
```

Based on the analysis of the two approaches (Cumulative SHAP Contribution and Incremental Feature Addition) we opted to prioritize the latter, as it is more directly aligned with performance optimization. Both methods effectively achieve the goal of filtering out uninformative features, thereby enhancing model performance, reducing the risk of overfitting, and eliminating noise from the dataset. However, the Incremental Feature Addition method offers a more practical, data-driven perspective by explicitly evaluating how each additional feature impacts predictive performance.

Final Method Selection

To compare the effectiveness of different feature sets, we adopt the following approach: for each group of features selected by a specific feature selection method, we train a Support Vector Machine (SVM) on the training set and evaluate its performance on the test set. The hyperparameters C and γ for each subset are optimized using grid search with cross-validation. The results are summarized in the table below.

Method	N. Features	F1-score	MCC	Precision	Recall	Accuracy
All features	39	0.744	0.487	0.744	0.744	0.744
ANOVA	10	0.725	0.451	0.724	0.727	0.732
Permutation	13	0.719	0.438	0.719	0.719	0.719
BFE	11	0.688	0.377	0.689	0.688	0.689
FFS	22	0.663	0.330	0.665	0.665	0.663
RFECV	9	0.733	0.502	0.764	0.739	0.739
SHAP	20	0.827	0.659	0.834	0.825	0.830

Table 5.4: Comparison of feature selection methods based on SVM performance

Based on these results, we select the feature set identified by the SHAP method. This approach outperforms the other methods in terms of performance. These selected features are not only more interpretable but also better aligned with the physical processes driving avalanche release and operational forecasting. Compared to the full feature set, the SHAP method enhances SVM model performance by eliminating irrelevant features that introduce noise and do not contribute useful information.

5.5 Feature extraction (LDA)

In this study, SHAP was employed for feature selection to identify the most informative variables, while Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) was used as a feature extraction technique to reduce dimensionality by projecting features into a lower-dimensional space. Following SHAP-based feature selection, we further investigated whether applying LDA could enhance classification performance when combined with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model. The impact of these approaches was evaluated by comparing the classification results across different feature sets.

To assess the combined effects of feature selection and dimensionality reduction on SVM performance, we evaluated the following four configurations:

- SVM trained on all 39 features
- SVM trained on the LDA projection of all features (reduced to 1 component)
- SVM trained on the top 20 SHAP-selected features
- SVM trained on the LDA projection of the 20 SHAP-selected features (reduced to 1 component)

Table 5.5 summarizes the performance of each configuration

Method	N. Features	F1-score	MCC	Precision	Recall	Accuracy
All features	39	0.744	0.487	0.744	0.744	0.744
All features + LDA	1	0.743	0.487	0.744	0.743	0.744
SHAP	20	0.827	0.659	0.834	0.825	0.830
SHAP + LDA	1	0.784	0.573	0.786	0.787	0.784

Table 5.5: Comparison of feature extraction methods based on SVM performance

The best results were achieved using the 20 SHAP-selected features without dimensionality reduction, with an F1-score of 0.827 and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) of 0.659. This underscores the strength of SHAP in identifying the most relevant and non-redundant features for this task.

Reducing the SHAP-selected features to a single LDA component led to a decline in performance, with the F1-score dropping to 0.784 and MCC to 0.573. This suggests that while SHAP identifies informative features, compressing them into a single linear direction via LDA removes valuable nonlinear structure.

Applying LDA to the full feature set did not improve performance, with the F1-score decreasing marginally from 0.744 to 0.743 and the MCC remaining unchanged at 0.487. This confirms that linear projection fails to capture sufficient discriminatory information from the data, likely due to its inherent nonlinearity.

These findings highlight that SHAP-based feature selection is both effective and interpretable. In contrast, LDA, though useful in some contexts, underperforms in this non-linear classification setting, especially when overly reducing the feature space. The results emphasize the importance of applying dimensionality reduction methods thoughtfully and selectively.

Chapter 6

Results and Discussion

6.1 Overview of the Experimental Setup

After completing the data preprocessing and feature engineering steps, various data balancing techniques were evaluated to address the pronounced class imbalance. Random undersampling was selected as the most suitable method due to its balance of operational simplicity and effective performance. The original dataset included 1856 non-avalanche samples and 175 avalanche samples; after undersampling, it was balanced to 175 avalanche and 175 non-avalanche days.

To improve model efficiency and mitigate the curse of dimensionality, several feature selection techniques were considered. Among them, the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) method stood out as the most effective, offering both robustness and interpretability in identifying relevant features.

The final set of 20 selected features includes:

```
HSnum, TH01G, PR, DayOfSeason, TmaxG_delta_5d, HS_delta_5d, TH03G, HS_delta_1d, TmaxG_delta_3d,
Precip_3d, TempGrad_HS, HS_delta_2d, TmaxG_delta_2d, TminG_delta_5d, TminG_delta_3d,
Tsnow_delta_3d, TaG_delta_5d, Tsnow_delta_1d, TmaxG_delta_1d, Precip_2d
```

This selection defined the final model setup. The balanced dataset was normalized to the $[0, 1]$ range using Min-Max scaling, then split via stratified sampling: 75% (262 samples) for training and 25% (88 samples) for testing. The SVM model was trained using the training set, including grid search with cross-validation for hyperparameter tuning, while the testing set was used to assess generalization performance.

We then trained a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel, using the optimal hyperparameters $C = 2$ and $\gamma = 0.5$. These values were determined via an exhaustive Grid Search with Cross-Validation, conducted over a 56×56 parameter grid. The grid covered:

- $C \in \{0.001, 0.002, \dots, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1, 2, \dots, 10, 20, \dots, 1000\}$
- $\gamma \in \{0.0001, 0.0002, \dots, 0.001, 0.002, \dots, 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1, 2, \dots, 100\}$

Figure 6.1 illustrates the contour plot depicting the mean cross-validation F1-score corresponding to each pair of hyperparameters C and γ identified during the Grid Search procedure.

Figure 6.1: Contour plot of mean cross-validated F1-score from grid search over C and γ

The red marker indicates the optimal combination of hyperparameters. Yellow regions represent areas of higher performance, while blue regions indicate lower performance. Performance remains relatively stable around the central area near the red marker, suggesting that this combination of hyperparameters is robust. As a result, further fine-tuning is unlikely to yield significant improvements. The model's results using these hyperparameters are presented in the next section.

6.2 Model Performance Evaluation

The final Support Vector Machine (SVM) model was evaluated on the test set using a range of performance metrics and evaluation tools. The comparison between predicted and observed values is summarized in the confusion matrix shown in Figure 6.2.

Figure 6.2: Confusion matrix of final trained SVM model on test set

Out of 88 events, 73 were correctly predicted: 42 from class 0 (no avalanches) and 31 from class 1 (avalanches). The model produced 5 false positives (predicted avalanches that did not occur) and 10 false negatives (missed avalanche predictions). From a forecaster’s perspective, false negatives are generally more critical, as failing to predict an actual avalanche can have serious consequences. On the other hand, a small number of false positives may actually enhance trust in the model, as it shows a conservative approach.

The confusion matrix indicates a good balance, with no major disparity between true positives and true negatives, as well as a relatively even distribution between false positives and false negatives.

From the confusion matrix, several key performance metrics were computed, including F1-score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), accuracy, precision, and recall.

In addition, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve was used to evaluate the model’s classification performance. The ROC curve plots the True Positive Rate (TPR) against the False Positive Rate (FPR) at various classification thresholds. The TPR and FPR are defined as:

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \quad \text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

The Area Under the Curve (AUC) summarizes the ROC curve as a single scalar value, representing the model’s ability to distinguish between the positive and negative classes. An AUC of 1.0 indicates a perfect model, while an AUC of 0.5 corresponds to a model performing no better than random guessing.

Figure 6.3: ROC-AUC curve of final SVM model

The ROC curve rises steeply up to a TPR of 0.8 at an FPR of approximately 0.2, after which it begins to plateau. This behavior is characteristic of a well-performing model, especially in binary classification tasks where both types of errors, false positives and false negatives, are important.

An AUC score of 0.88 indicates that the model assigns higher scores to positive instances than to negative ones 88% of the time. This demonstrates that the model has strong discriminative ability and is well-suited for applications where accurate binary classification is essential.

The performance metrics are summarized in Table 6.1.

Metric	Value
F1-score	0.827
Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)	0.659
Accuracy	0.829
Precision	0.834
Recall	0.825
ROC-AUC	0.880

Table 6.1: Performance metrics of the final SVM model on the test set

The results demonstrate that the SVM model is capable of effectively distinguishing between avalanche and non-avalanche days. The F1-score of 0.827 indicates a strong balance between precision and recall, making the model suitable for applications where both false positives and false negatives are critical. The ROC-AUC of 0.880 confirms the model's robust discriminative ability across various threshold settings, while the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) value of 0.659 suggests a solid overall correlation between predicted and actual classifications.

These performance levels highlight the effectiveness of the adopted data balancing strategy, feature selection process, and hyperparameter optimization, ultimately validating the proposed approach for operational

avalanche forecasting.

The learning curve provides valuable insight into how the model's performance evolves as a function of the training set size. It plots the model's performance on both the training and validation sets, typically using a selected metric such as F1-score. This visualization is particularly useful for diagnosing problems such as high bias, high variance, or overfitting.

Figure 6.4 presents the learning curve of the SVM classifier.

Figure 6.4: Learning curve: training and validation performance over training set

The curve displays a typical learning pattern with initial overfitting, where the training score is significantly higher than the validation score for small dataset sizes.

As the number of training examples increases, the validation F1-score steadily improves and begins to stabilize around 0.71. Simultaneously, the training score gradually decreases and converges toward 0.80. This behavior suggests that the model benefits from more data, reducing overfitting while maintaining relatively strong generalization.

Although the gap between training and validation scores narrows, it remains notable, indicating moderate variance in the model. This suggests that further improvement might be achieved through enhanced regularization, advanced resampling techniques, or hyperparameter refinement.

Near the end of the curve, the validation score begins to plateau, indicating that the model is approaching its performance ceiling given the current dataset and undersampling approach. While adding more training data could yield some improvements, these gains are expected to be incremental and relatively minor.

We use a decision threshold performance plot because binary classification models output probabilities between 0 and 1 indicating the likelihood of belonging to the positive class. To assign a final class (positive or negative), we select a threshold: predictions above it are positive, below it are negative.

Choosing this threshold is crucial as it impacts performance metrics like precision, recall, F1-score, MCC, and others. The Figure 6.5 shows how these metrics vary with the threshold, helping identify the value that maximizes the metric of interest and balances false positives and false negatives according to the problem's needs.

Figure 6.5: Threshold performance plot showing metric variation with decision threshold

From Figure 6.5, we see that very low thresholds classify almost everything as positive, causing many false positives and low performance, while very high thresholds do the opposite, leading to many false negatives and poor results. Between these extremes, metrics peak as the model better balances precision and recall.

Metrics like MCC, HK, and HSS, which consider the full confusion matrix, peak around thresholds 0.45–0.55 with values near 0.65–0.7. The F1-score, focusing on precision and recall, peaks higher (0.83–0.84) near 0.5.

At threshold extremes, all metrics drop due to poor discrimination. This plot prevents arbitrary threshold choices and offers insight into model behavior.

In summary, this plot is key to selecting the optimal threshold. Whether maximizing F1-score or more robust metrics like MCC, HK, or HSS, the ideal threshold is around 0.5, enabling better decision-making in classification tasks.

Overall, the evaluation demonstrates that the final SVM model achieves strong and balanced predictive performance, supported by multiple complementary metrics and diagnostic tools. The combination of confusion matrix analysis, ROC-AUC evaluation, learning curves, and threshold performance plots provides a comprehensive understanding of the model’s strengths and limitations. These insights confirm the robustness and practical applicability of the proposed approach for reliable avalanche forecasting.

6.3 Uncertainty of SVM final model

Bootstrapping is a statistical resampling technique used to estimate the variability and uncertainty of model performance metrics without requiring additional data. By repeatedly sampling from the original dataset with replacement, bootstrapping provides insights into how sensitive a model’s performance is to data perturbations. This is particularly valuable when assessing model robustness in settings with limited or variable data availability.

Figure 6.6 presents the standard deviation of the F1-score and the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), calculated via bootstrapping.

Figure 6.6: Standard deviation of F1-score (left) and MCC (right) from bootstrapping over C and γ combinations

Color intensity reflects the degree of variability: darker regions indicate more stable performance, while lighter areas highlight configurations with higher sensitivity to data fluctuations.

In this analysis, 50 bootstrap samples were generated. For each resample, key performance metrics F1-score and MCC were computed. This process was repeated across a hyperparameter grid surrounding the optimal configuration identified through grid search cross-validation. Specifically, the regularization parameter C ranged from 0.2 to 20 (in increments of 0.2), and the kernel coefficient γ from 0.05 to 2 (in increments of 0.05), yielding a total of 40000 (C, γ) combinations.

The region surrounding the optimal hyperparameters shows consistently low standard deviations for both metrics, suggesting that model performance is stable under resampling. This indicates robustness to sampling variability, a desirable property for real-world deployment where test conditions may vary.

In contrast, the bottom-left regions of the plots, corresponding to low C and γ values, exhibit substantially higher variability. This pattern implies that models in this regime are under-regularized and more prone to overfitting or instability, making them less reliable.

Overall, the low variance observed near the optimal configuration supports the robustness and reliability of the final model. The consistent performance across bootstrapped resamples reinforces its suitability for operational deployment in forecasting tasks where stability under uncertain conditions is critical.

6.4 Interpretability of the Model

Given the high-stakes nature of avalanche forecasting, interpretability is not just a desirable feature, it is a necessary condition for the operational use of machine learning models. While our SVM classifier offers strong predictive performance, its black-box nature requires post-hoc interpretability techniques to ensure transparency and build user trust.

To this end, we utilized the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) framework, employing the model-agnostic KernelExplainer to assign feature contributions for individual predictions. The SHAP values enabled us to interpret the SVM’s decision-making process by quantifying the influence of each feature on the predicted class probabilities.

We explored the SHAP outputs through several visualization techniques:

- **Global interpretability:** Summary plots highlighted the most influential features across the entire test set.
- **Feature interactions:** Dependence plots illustrated how specific features interact and affect the model’s output.
- **Local interpretability:** Force plots and heatmaps provided insights into the model’s reasoning on a per-instance basis.

These visualizations revealed that the model’s predictions often align with established avalanche dynamics, for example, increased snowfall and late-season conditions were associated with higher predicted risk. Such consistency between model behavior and domain knowledge strengthens confidence in the model’s internal reasoning and supports its integration into operational forecasting workflows.

SHAP effectively bridges the gap between predictive accuracy and physical interpretability by offering transparent, feature-level insights. This enables forecasters to critically evaluate, validate, and build confidence in the model’s outputs.

6.4.1 SHAP and KernelExplainer for SVMs

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are powerful classifiers but function as black-box models, making it difficult to understand the rationale behind individual predictions. This interpretability challenge is especially critical applications like avalanche forecasting, where clear explanations of model decisions are essential for building trust and guiding informed actions.

To address this, we employed SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), a model-agnostic interpretability framework grounded in cooperative game theory. SHAP assigns each feature a contribution score by evaluating its marginal effect on the prediction, averaged over all possible combinations of features. This approach ensures a fair and theoretically sound distribution of feature importance.

We employed the `KernelExplainer` implementation of SHAP, which is well-suited for interpreting black-box models such as SVMs. This approach requires two key components:

- A prediction function that returns the model’s class probabilities, here, the probability estimates generated by our trained SVM.
- A background dataset that serves as a reference for SHAP value computation. We used the scaled training set, consistent with the data used to train the SVM.

SHAP values quantify the difference between the model’s actual prediction and this baseline, decomposing it into additive feature contributions. This enables both global interpretability (understanding overall feature influence) and local interpretability (explaining individual predictions).

By applying SHAP to the test dataset, we uncover how the model “reasons” for each prediction, offering valuable insights into its decision-making process. This transparency reveals which features drive increases or decreases in predicted avalanche risk, making the model’s internal logic more accessible and actionable.

Ultimately, the SHAP-based approach facilitates a clear, interpretable attribution of each variable’s impact on the model’s predictions, effectively bridging the gap between complex machine learning outputs and domain expertise. This transparency fosters user trust and supports the practical integration of the model into operational forecasting workflows.

6.4.2 Global Interpretability

Summary Plot The first visualization presented is the summary plot, which conveys several important insights about feature importance and model behavior.

Features are ranked vertically by their overall importance, measured as the average absolute SHAP value. This metric reflects how much each feature influences the model’s predictions on average; the higher the value, the greater the impact.

Along the x-axis, SHAP values indicate the direction and magnitude of each feature’s effect on the prediction. Positive SHAP values (to the right) push the prediction toward the avalanche class, while negative values (to the left) push it toward the non-avalanche class.

The color gradient represents the actual feature values: blue tones correspond to lower values, and red tones to higher values. The violin plot shape shows the distribution and density of SHAP values for each feature across all instances, illustrating how feature influence varies within the dataset. All features are normalized while preserving their original distribution, ensuring easy interpretability.

For example, `DayOfSeason`, the most influential feature, shows that higher values (red) increase the predicted avalanche risk, while lower values (blue) reduce it. `DayOfSeason` counts days from the start of winter (December 1st), so higher values correspond to late winter and spring conditions. This aligns with observed patterns, as wet loose snow avalanches commonly occur toward the end of the season due to increased solar radiation and snow warming.

The second most important feature is snow height (`HSnum`). Lower snow heights are generally associated with reduced avalanche risk, as shallow snowpacks tend to exhibit rough, discontinuous surfaces that inhibit large-scale failure propagation. Moreover, limited snow accumulation due to low precipitation typically results in smaller, more localized avalanches. In contrast, deeper snowpacks tend to bury surface irregularities such as rocks and terrain discontinuities, thereby reducing surface roughness and creating more favorable conditions for slab sliding.

Cumulative precipitation over the past three (`Precip_3d`) days also plays a key role: higher precipitation increases snow load, thus raising avalanche risk.

Ram Penetration (`PR`), measured by a specific probe, indicates snow stability. Higher `PR` values reflect a depth soft surface layer, often caused by recent snowfall or snow melt phase. In this case the snow cohesion is low and the instability increases.

Snow temperature, particularly at 10 cm depth (and to a lesser extent at 30 cm) (`TH01G`, `TH03G`), significantly influences risk. Warmer, wetter snow near the ground, resulting from rain-on-snow, solar radiation, or rising air temperatures, reduces snow stability, consistent with higher avalanche danger in late winter.

An initially counterintuitive finding concerns the variation in snow height over the previous one and two days (`HS_delta_1d`, `HS_delta_2d`). Although snowfall causes snow height to increase, the snowpack subsequently settles due to gravity. In early winter, this settling happens slowly, leading to positive or stable snow height changes. However, in late winter, warmer temperatures accelerate snowpack settling, which can result in negative snow height changes even after fresh snowfall. This rapid settling is linked to a higher avalanche risk, especially in the days following snowfall events, when loose snow avalanches are more frequent.

Temperature variations over 2 to 5 days also follow expected patterns: larger swings correlate with increased avalanche risk. Rapid temperature changes can weaken snow cohesion or create stress within snowpack, triggering avalanches.

A more complex observation concerns `Tmin_delta_3d`, the variation in minimum temperature over three days. The plot suggests that lower variability in minimum temperature is linked to higher avalanche risk. This may relate to late-winter clear-sky conditions causing strong nighttime radiative cooling and surface refreezing, forming melt-freeze crusts. These crusts can create weak layers in the snowpack, enhancing instability and avalanche likelihood.

Other features in the plot have less influence but generally align with the mechanisms described above.

Figure 6.7 presents a violin plot of SHAP values, ordered by feature importance from top to bottom. The shape of each violin illustrates the distribution of SHAP values for that feature, indicating its contribution to the model’s prediction. The color gradient (from blue to red) represents the actual feature values, with blue corresponding to low values and red to high values. SHAP values on the x-axis reflect the influence of each feature on the prediction: positive values push the prediction toward class 1, while negative values push it toward the opposite class.

Figure 6.7: Violin plot of SHAP values for most important features

Thresholds between avalanches and no-avalanches In order to interpret the model predictions and extract actionable insights, we analyzed the distribution of the most predictive features in relation to the SHAP value sign. Specifically, we computed descriptive statistics (mean, interquartile range, and standard deviation) for each feature, conditioned on whether its SHAP value was positive (i.e., contributing to a higher predicted avalanche probability) or negative (i.e., contributing to a lower probability).

Our analysis has yielded suggested threshold values that help differentiate between typical avalanche and non-avalanche scenarios. These thresholds are not rigid decision boundaries; instead, they represent the central tendencies observed within our data for each feature.

For each feature, the suggested threshold was determined by calculating the mean value between the 75th percentile of non-avalanche days and the 25th percentile of avalanche days. The associated uncertainty (error) for each threshold is estimated as half the difference between these 25th and 75th percentiles.

In Table 6.2, we present the suggested threshold values for the most relevant features identified by the model.

Feature	Suggested Threshold	No Avalanche	Avalanche	Error
DayOfSeason	88.8	75.0	102.5	13.75
HSnum	89.6	70.8	108.5	18.875
Precip_3d	8.3	2.0	14.7	6.325
PR	28.3	21.0	35.5	7.25
TH01G	-3.5	-5.0	-2.0	1.5
HS_delta_1d	-4.6	0.0	-9.3	4.625
TminG_delta_5d	3.0	2.0	4.0	1
TminG_delta_3d	-1.0	5.0	-7.0	6
TmaxG_delta_2d	2.5	1.0	4.0	1.5
TmaxG_delta_3d	3.5	2.0	5.0	1.5
HS_delta_2d	-6.5	0.8	-13.8	7.25
TaG_delta_5d	3.1	2.0	4.3	1.125
TH03G	-1.5	-2.0	-1.0	0.5
TmaxG_delta_1d	2.5	1.8	3.3	0.75
Precip_2d	9.3	1.0	17.5	8.25
Tsnow_delta_1d	-0.9	2.0	-3.8	2.875
HS_delta_5d	-8.5	7.0	-24.0	15.5
Tsnow_delta_3d	-2.8	2.5	-8.0	5.25
TmaxG_delta_5d	6.8	4.0	9.5	2.75

Table 6.2: Suggested thresholds and uncertainty intervals for the top predictive features (based on SHAP values)

The distributions of the top 6 most important features are shown in Figure 6.8. Differences in these distributions help to identify the typical values associated with avalanches and non-avalanches. It is important to note that the final prediction is not based on any single feature alone, but rather on the complex interactions among all features.

For example, the `DayOfSeason` was estimated around value 88, which typically corresponds to the end of February, with a variance extending between mid-February and mid-March. Cumulative precipitation over the last three days (`Precip_3d`) shows a typical threshold of approximately 22 mm, with a considerable spread between the 25th and 75th quantiles, ranging from 14.7 mm to 38.9 mm. Similarly, the depth of the soft layer, measured by `PR`, was about 28 cm (with a range of 21-35 cm), which is consistent with observations.

These threshold values can support expert interpretation, serve as early indicators, or be integrated into an operational decision support framework. However, caution is warranted: the thresholds are model-dependent and data-dependent, and their use in isolation may not capture the full complexity of avalanche formation. Nevertheless, they offer a useful summary of the key meteorological and snowpack dynamics captured by the machine learning model.

Figure 6.8: Boxplot of six most important features classified by avalanche presence; classification threshold highlighted

6.4.3 Feature Relationships

Dependence Plots The insights revealed by the SHAP summary plot are further confirmed by the SHAP dependence plots (Figure 6.9), which visualize the effect of the six most influential features on the model’s prediction of avalanche risk. In each subplot, the x-axis shows the raw feature values, while the y-axis represents the corresponding SHAP values, quantifying the feature’s marginal contribution to the model output. Points are colored according to an interacting feature, selected to reveal possible dependencies, most notably `DayOfSeason`, `HSnum`, `Precip_3d`, and `TH01G`.

The alignment and slope of the points reveal the directionality and strength of each feature’s effect:

- **Positive slopes** (e.g., in `DayOfSeason`, `HSnum`, `Precip_3d`, `PR`, `TH01G`) indicate that increasing values of these features contribute to a higher predicted probability of avalanche release. This reflects intuitive physical processes such as deeper snowpack, advancing season, or greater recent snowfall.
- **Negative slopes** (e.g., in `HS_delta_1d`) means that decreasing values indicate an increasing avalanche risk. This is particularly true for snow settlement; a decrease in snow height (settlement) is linked to a higher avalanche risk. This is likely because rapid densification or melting can destabilize the snowpack, making it more prone to avalanche releasing.

Color gradients in each subplot offer further insights into seasonal dynamics and feature interactions:

- `DayOfSeason` shows a steadily increasing effect on avalanche probability, particularly during mid-to-late winter. The interacting feature (`HSnum`) reveals that avalanche risk is amplified when both snow depth and day of season are high, supporting the known increase in avalanche frequency as the snowpack matures.
- `HSnum` exhibits a nearly linear positive contribution to model output. The interaction with `DayOfSeason` confirms that deep snow in late winter corresponds to particularly elevated risk, likely due to weak layers being buried and load accumulation.
- `Precip_3d` displays a strongly nonlinear relationship, where avalanche probability rises steeply beyond 10-20 mm of accumulated precipitation. The interaction with `TH01G` (surface snow temperature) shows that these effects are exacerbated when precipitation coincides with warmer temperatures, potentially indicative of wet snow or rain-on-snow events.
- `PR` (ram penetration) also correlates positively with avalanche risk. Interaction with `DayOfSeason` shows two distinct clusters: one in early winter (weaker snow, little crust), and another in late winter (metamorphosed, possibly wet snow). Both conditions reduce snowpack resistance and align with known avalanche release mechanisms.
- `TH01G` (surface snow temperature) contributes more strongly when close to zero, especially when coinciding with recent precipitation. This highlights the importance of marginally cold or isothermal conditions that may precede wet-snow avalanche cycles.
- `HS_delta_1d` (daily snow depth change) shows a strong negative slope. Larger decreases, indicating intense snow settlement, correspond to higher model-predicted avalanche probability. These conditions, often arising in the later part of the season as shown by interaction with `HSnum`, reflect situations where rapid densification or melt-induced compaction destabilizes the snowpack and heightens slab avalanche risk.

Figure 6.9: SHAP dependence plots for six most influential features, showing feature impact on predicted avalanche probability; point colors indicate interacting features

Overall, these dependence plots support the model’s alignment with expert knowledge of snowpack behavior and avalanche release conditions. They also demonstrate how interactions between meteorological and snowpack variables shape the model’s risk estimates across different phases of the winter season.

6.4.4 Local Interpretability

Local interpretability helps us understand the specific factors driving each individual prediction made by our model, offering a detailed view of its decision-making.

Heatmap of SHAP Values Figure 6.10, a heatmap, provides a detailed visualization of the SHAP values computed for each prediction generated by our Support Vector Machine (SVM) model on the test dataset. SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values are a powerful tool from game theory that quantitatively explain how much each input feature contributes to the model’s final decision for an individual prediction.

In this context, the SVM model is tasked with predicting avalanche occurrences (the positive class). The heatmap effectively illustrates these feature contributions over time, allowing us to track how different features influence the model’s predictions on various dates. By examining the SHAP values, we can discern which features are driving the model towards predicting an avalanche, and conversely, which features are pushing it away from such a prediction, on a day-by-day basis. This provides valuable insights into the model’s decision-making process and the dynamic interplay of features in avalanche forecasting.

Each row corresponds to a model prediction for a specific date, while each column represents a feature. Cell colors indicate the SHAP value of that feature for the given prediction: red tones push the prediction toward avalanche, blue tones toward non-avalanche. Lighter shades indicate weaker influence; darker shades represent stronger effects.

The first column on the left shows the total SHAP contribution per prediction—the sum of all feature contributions. While not a direct probability, this sum indicates the model’s confidence: intense red suggests a strong avalanche prediction, deep blue indicates confidence in no avalanche.

Prediction outcomes are color-coded in the row labels: green for correctly predicted avalanches, grey for correctly predicted non-avalanches, red for missed avalanches, and orange for false alarms. This combined coding reveals not only the model’s accuracy but also the reasoning behind its decisions.

On March 27, 1996, our model missed an avalanche, and the near-zero SHAP values reflected its low confidence in that prediction. Similarly, a correct prediction on March 29, 2016, also showed low SHAP magnitudes, indicating uncertainty even when accurate. Conversely, the model was confidently incorrect on January 31, 2024; despite an avalanche occurring, the total SHAP sum was strongly negative. These examples highlight areas where the model may struggle or misinterpret data.

The heatmap also confirms expected behaviors: during heavy snowfall periods (e.g., 2010-12-26, 2014-01-07, 2018-01-09), the model assigns strong positive SHAP values to snow-related features, correctly linking these conditions to elevated avalanche risk.

Overall, this SHAP heatmap offers a transparent, interpretable view into the model’s decision process, showing how it weighs different factors over time. Such interpretability is vital in high-stakes contexts like avalanche forecasting, fostering trust and guiding improvements in predictive performance.

Figure 6.10: Heatmap of SHAP values by date and feature; red = positive impact, blue = negative impact on avalanche prediction; left bar shows total SHAP; left column shows prediction outcomes

Force Plot: a case-by-case explanation To complement the global interpretation of model behavior, we present a detailed analysis of four representative predictions using SHAP force plots. Each example corresponds to one of the four possible prediction–observation combinations: a correct avalanche prediction (true positive), a correct no-avalanche prediction (true negative), a missed avalanche (false negative), and a false alarm (false positive).

Figure 6.11 shows SHAP force plots for several individual test instances. These plots illustrate how each feature contributes to the model’s prediction. Here’s how to interpret them:

- The **base value** (0.5016), which represents the average model output over the training set, serves as a reference point. The sum of the SHAP values shifts this baseline to produce the final prediction.
- **Horizontal bars** visualize how each feature pushes the model output away from the base value:
 - *Red segments* indicate positive SHAP values, pushing the prediction toward the avalanche class.
 - *Blue segments* indicate negative SHAP values, pushing the prediction toward the no-avalanche class.
- The **length of each segment** reflects the magnitude of the feature’s contribution to the prediction.
- The **label** displays the true class and prediction outcome, alongside the most influential features and their actual values.
- The **end of the bar** shows the final model output after all SHAP contributions have been aggregated.

This format enables an intuitive understanding of how the model makes decisions at the individual instance level. It highlights the most influential features for each prediction and clarifies whether the model’s decision was driven primarily by positive or negative evidence. By comparing multiple rows, one can also observe whether the model behaves consistently across different cases or relies on different features depending on the context.

The four examples presented here in Figure ?? represent distinct types of prediction outcomes: a correct avalanche prediction (true positive), a correct no-avalanche prediction (true negative), a missed avalanche (false negative), and a false alarm (false positive).

- **Case 1: Correct Avalanche Prediction (March 6, 2009)** This instance yielded a strong avalanche prediction (SHAP sum: 0.92), well above the base value of 0.5016. Key contributing features include significant 3-day precipitation (40 cm), high snow height, and low ram resistance (high PR), all of which point to an unstable snowpack. The model also correctly downweights the stabilizing influence of a minor snow height decrease (`HS_delta_2d`), suggesting the prediction is both accurate and physically interpretable.
- **Case 2: Correct No Avalanche Prediction (January 10, 2005)** Here, the model confidently predicted no avalanche, supported by several stabilizing indicators: low snow height, no recent precipitation, and early-season conditions. The SHAP sum of 0.12 was far below the decision threshold, consistent with a low avalanche likelihood. This case exemplifies the model’s ability to recognize low-risk environments.
- **Case 3: Missed Avalanche (January 20, 2018)** This false negative highlights a limitation of the model. The SHAP sum was slightly below the threshold (0.43), leading to a no-avalanche prediction despite an actual event. While several risk indicators were present (moderate snow height, elevated PR, and mild warming), these were counterbalanced by stabilizing features such as low recent precipitation, minimal settlement, and early-season timing.
- **Case 4: False Alarm (March 29, 2016)** This example illustrates a forecast where the model predicted an avalanche, but none occurred. The SHAP sum was above the threshold (0.55), driven by strong diurnal temperature variation, late-season timing, and signs of potential snowpack destabilization. While the actual event did not materialize, this type of “false positive” is acceptable in operational forecasting, as it promotes caution. The model correctly identified a high risk, even if no avalanche occurred, reflecting the inherent complexity of predicting avalanche triggers.

Figure 6.11: SHAP force plots for four example dates

In summary, these force plots provide intuitive and granular explanations of model decisions. They not only highlight the most influential features for each prediction but also enable critical evaluation of model limitations, such as borderline scenarios. Such insights are essential for deploying machine learning models in domains like avalanche forecasting, where interpretability and reliability are essential.

6.4.5 Final remarks

Strengths

The application of SHAP to the SVM classifier demonstrates several important strengths. First, the most influential features identified by the model align well with established avalanche physics. Key predictors such as recent precipitation, snow depth, temperature variations, and seasonal timing emerge with intuitive and scientifically coherent relationships to avalanche risk.

Additionally, SHAP enables both global interpretability (through summary and dependence plots) and local explanation (via heatmaps and force plots), offering transparency at multiple levels. This duality supports both model validation and real-world applicability: operational forecasters can interpret why a specific prediction was made, improving trust in the model and its outputs.

Another notable strength is the model's ability to respond dynamically to unstable snowpack configurations, particularly during periods of heavy snowfall, rapid warming, or significant structural changes in the snowpack. This responsiveness reflects the utility of the model as a decision support tool, one that complements human expertise by providing consistent data-driven risk assessments.

Weaknesses

Despite its strengths, our approach has a few limitations. Our model sometimes struggles in ambiguous or mixed scenarios where various competing factors influence snow stability. These situations often occur near the decision boundary, where SHAP values are small or conflicting, suggesting the model might not be sensitive enough to resolve subtle interactions.

Another inherent limitation is that SHAP can only explain what the model has learned from the input data. It can't infer or correct for any missing information or biases in the training set. For instance, if certain types of avalanche events are underrepresented in the data, SHAP explanations might downplay relevant signals or overfit to more dominant patterns.

Finally, while SHAP values are theoretically sound, their interpretation isn't always intuitive for all users, particularly those unfamiliar with machine learning or game theory. Unfortunately, this can lead to misinterpretations of a feature's exact contribution.

Operational Impact and Future Outlook

Integrating SHAP-based interpretation significantly strengthens the case for using machine learning models in avalanche forecasting. It bridges the gap between statistical learning and expert reasoning, offering interpretable, traceable justifications for model predictions. This transparency is crucial for building user trust, especially when deploying models in high-stakes environments.

The SHAP analysis has made our SVM model interpretable by clearly highlighting each feature's contribution to the final prediction. This supports a more informed and reliable evaluation of the model's behavior, which is essential for deployment in high-risk operational contexts. Furthermore, the ability to identify key drivers of risk facilitates targeted data collection and model refinement. While the model shows promising accuracy, continued efforts to incorporate diverse datasets and better capture uncertainty will further enhance its robustness and user trust.

Beyond model interpretability, SHAP analysis also holds the potential to uncover valuable insights into local patterns of snowpack behavior and avalanche dynamics. By quantifying the contribution and interaction of key variables, SHAP helps identify critical factors and hidden patterns. This advances our understanding of avalanche phenomena at a local scale and informs future research directions.

In conclusion, SHAP adds considerable value to avalanche risk modeling by making complex model behavior both transparent and actionable. While challenges remain, especially concerning data availability and edge-case performance, our current framework establishes a strong foundation for future enhancements and operational deployment.

6.5 Robustness on Real-World Data

6.5.1 Data and Model setup

To assess the robustness of the trained SVM model under real-world conditions, we tested its performance on an independent dataset from the 2024-2025 winter season, which was completely unseen during the training and validation phases (covering winters from 1995-1996 to 2023-2024). The 2024-2025 dataset underwent the same feature engineering process described in the previous chapters, ensuring consistency in input preparation.

A manual quality control was performed to identify and correct any potential data errors, such as column inversions, wrong values, and inconsistencies. Missing data were gap-filled using observational insights from Panomax Peio 3000, Panomax Saroden webcams, and AWS T0372 Pejo (Crozi Taviela), relying on adjacent day weather and temperature trends. Only 3 days out of the 108-day season required imputation due to missing data collection.

The trained SVM model, along with the MinMax scaler and the feature list, were all saved using the `joblib` Python package. This setup allows for rapid and reproducible predictions on new data without needing to retrain the model. Key model parameters were: RBF kernel, regularization parameter $C = 2$, $\gamma = 0.5$, and `probability=True` for probabilistic outputs estimating avalanche likelihood.

Figure 6.12 illustrates the SVM model applied to a real case. The blue line shows the predicted probability, while grey shaded areas highlight periods when this probability exceeds 0.5 (predicted avalanches). Red dots mark days with observed medium-large avalanches, and gold dots indicate recorded small avalanches. We want to remember that the model was trained only on medium-large avalanches.

Figure 6.12: Application of SVM model on real data: comparison between predicted probabilities and observed avalanches during winter season

6.5.2 Results

Good agreement between high probabilities and avalanches:

There is a consistent and meaningful correspondence between periods of high model-predicted probability (greater than 0.5, highlighted in gray) and the occurrence of observed avalanches, particularly those of medium to large size (red circles). This suggests that the model is successfully capturing the key atmospheric, snowpack, or environmental conditions that typically precede significant avalanche events. The clustering of large avalanche observations within high-probability intervals reinforces the model’s potential as a reliable early warning tool.

This agreement is especially important in the context of operational forecasting, where anticipating hazardous conditions can support risk mitigation decisions. The model does not merely react to isolated events but appears to identify broader periods of instability, often aligning with real avalanche cycles. This temporal coherence implies that the model’s outputs could be valuable not only for pinpointing individual days of concern but also for highlighting extended windows where caution is warranted. For instance, in the last days of January and mid-March, the model indicates high probabilities that align with observed avalanches, including larger events. This demonstrates the model’s capacity to correctly predict critical situations.

False alarms:

While the model generally performs well, some false positives occur: days when the predicted probability exceeds the 0.5 threshold, but no avalanches are observed. For example, between February 2nd and 4th, the model shows a sharp probability increase peaking above 0.8, yet no avalanche events were recorded. These cases might be overpredictions or could indicate near-miss conditions where avalanches were possible but did not occur or were not reported. In practical applications, such false alarms can still be valuable, especially if they correspond to unstable snowpack conditions that justify increased vigilance. From a forecaster’s perspective, false alarms are not necessarily an error, as they promote caution and encourage consideration of multiple forecasting factors.

Moreover, the model doesn’t account for whether an avalanche has already occurred. In reality, after an avalanche releases, snow conditions in the path change significantly; the event essentially ”cleans out” unstable snow layers. Even if the nivo-meteo conditions still indicate instability according to the SVM, a second avalanche is unlikely to occur immediately in the same path because the snowpack has been altered. Since our model relies solely on risk conditions and can’t detect a prior release, it might continue to predict avalanche risk in areas where an event has just taken place. You can observe this behavior in the plot, for example, towards the end of March.

False negatives, avalanches not predicted:

On the other hand, there are a few false negatives where avalanches occurred despite low predicted probabilities. For example, on January 18, a small avalanche was observed even though the model’s output remained well below the 0.5 threshold. These missed events tend to be minor (yellow markers) and may result from localized conditions not fully captured by the model features. From a risk management standpoint, overlooking small, isolated avalanches is generally less critical than missing larger, more hazardous events.

Notable missed medium-large avalanches include one on February 14, when a medium-sized slab avalanche occurred on north-facing slopes. This event was triggered by a persistent weak layer with failure mechanics that were not represented in the training data, causing the model to miss it. Another missed event occurred on March 30, when a wind slab avalanche caused by strong northerly winds was not predicted, as wind slab avalanches were excluded from the training dataset.

Interpretation of predictions with SHAP Force Plots:

Figure 6.13 shows four SHAP force plots, each representing a different prediction case (true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative) from the real-world dataset. These plots offer insight into the model’s reasoning and can be a valuable visualization tool in operational avalanche forecasting.

In SHAP plots, red bars indicate features that push the prediction towards Avalanche, while blue bars represent features contributing to a No Avalanche prediction. The length of each bar corresponds to the

magnitude of its SHAP value, reflecting the strength of the feature's influence. Feature values are shown alongside, and the model's decision is based on whether the SHAP sum (i.e., the combined contributions) pushes the prediction above or below the baseline probability.

On January 28, a true positive case, the model correctly predicts an avalanche. The most influential features are recent snowfall variables, suggesting that fresh precipitation played a key role in the forecasted instability.

On February 4, a false positive case, the model predicted an avalanche with a SHAP sum of 0.557, slightly above the baseline of 0.5083. In this case, a rapid warming trend was interpreted as a sign of instability. However, the snowpack remained cold, and no significant precipitation are reported. Mid-winter timing also favored snowpack stability. This example illustrates how isolated warming, without accompanying loading or prior instability, may lead to overpredictions.

On February 8, the model correctly predicts no avalanche (true negative). This day was characterized by strong cooling, no precipitation, and early-season snow, conditions generally associated with greater stability.

On March 12, a false negative occurred: an avalanche was observed, but the model failed to predict it. The SHAP analysis reveals a balanced interaction of competing signals. Features promoting instability included recent precipitation, warm snow temperatures, and the late-season timing. However, other features such as low ram penetration (possibly indicating the presence of melt-freeze crusts), absence of settlement, and cooling air temperatures contributed towards stability. The near-cancellation of these opposing factors led the model to output a probability below the threshold, despite the occurrence of an avalanche.

Figure 6.13: SHAP force plots for four example real-world predictions

These examples demonstrate how SHAP force plots can aid in understanding the reasoning behind each prediction, allowing forecasters to assess which factors were most influential. This interpretability can also help evaluate the quality and reliability of the input data, especially in operational contexts where quick and transparent decisions are needed.

6.5.3 Conclusion: Validating Model Robustness for Real-World Application

This section demonstrates the critical importance of evaluating our trained SVM model on an independent, unseen dataset from the 2024-2025 winter season. Testing the model on real-world data, completely outside its training and validation periods, is essential for truly assessing its robustness and generalization capabilities.

By applying the model to current conditions and analyzing its performance against observed avalanche events, we've gained valuable insights into its strengths and limitations in an operational context. The consistent agreement between high predicted probabilities and observed medium-to-large avalanches confirms the model's potential as a reliable early warning tool. While acknowledging instances of false alarms and missed minor events, the interpretability provided by SHAP force plots offers crucial insights into the model's reasoning. This transparency is vital for forecasters, allowing them to understand the influential factors behind each prediction and build trust in the model's outputs. Ultimately, this real-world application not only validates the model's usability but also highlights areas for future refinement, paving the way for its responsible and effective integration into practical avalanche forecasting.

6.6 Final Considerations

6.6.1 Model Performance and Strengths

Our model demonstrates a strong capability in predicting medium and large avalanches, which was its primary training focus. This indicates its effectiveness in capturing the broader patterns and conditions leading to significant avalanche events. The reduced accuracy for smaller avalanches is understandable, given their dependence on highly localized and complex factors (e.g., micro-topography, subtle snowpack layering, minor weather fluctuations) not fully captured by our current dataset and features.

The use of a 0.5 probability threshold offers a reasonable balance between sensitivity and specificity, effectively distinguishing low- from high-risk periods. This aligns with observed peak performance metrics and supports actionable decision-making in forecasting and risk management. This threshold can, however, be fine-tuned based on specific operational priorities, such as minimizing false negatives in hazardous areas or reducing false alarms.

To ensure practical applicability, we conducted a real-world test with a one-day prediction shift. The model forecasts based on data from a given day, with verification against observations from the following day. This approach accurately simulates operational workflows, where the model runs in the morning for the upcoming 24-hour risk, confirming its real-time usability.

Overall, the model provides a robust and valuable tool for avalanche risk prediction. Its ability to identify key drivers and provide reliable outputs across seasons confirms the potential of data-driven tools for avalanche prediction, even with limited initial data. Current data collection practices, while improvable, appear sufficient for modeling needs.

6.6.2 Limitations and Areas for Improvement

A critical examination of our experimental approach is essential, especially when considering the deployment of the final SVM model in real-world applications. While the model shows promising predictive performance, several factors inherent to the data, modeling approach, and environmental variability may restrict its reliability and generalizability. Understanding these limitations is crucial for contextualizing the model's outputs and guiding future improvements.

Data Quality and Representativeness

One primary limitation lies in the quality and completeness of observational data. Despite quality control, accuracy relies heavily on individual operators for manual measurements, introducing potential subjectivity.

Regular collaboration and retraining with field experts could improve consistency.

Furthermore, the snow observation site of Pejo Tarlenta, at 2000 m a.s.l., is geographically distant and less representative of actual avalanche release zones. The recent establishment of a second site at 2900 m a.s.l. in Val de la Mite is a crucial step towards better data representativeness.

Reconsidering the role of Automated Weather Stations (AWS), coupled with physically based models like SNOWPACK, could offer more comprehensive monitoring of snowpack properties.

Lastly, the absence of a centralized system for managing long-term historical data limits overall data quality and usability for machine learning. Inaccurate or incomplete data can introduce bias, leading the model to learn spurious correlations.

Despite these limitations, the model’s performance highlights areas where improved data collection and management can yield the greatest impact.

Targeted Avalanche Types

Our model was exclusively trained on medium to large avalanche events, deliberately excluding smaller occurrences. Consequently, it cannot detect or predict small-scale avalanches, limiting its applicability where even minor events pose safety concerns.

Additionally, wind slab avalanches were excluded from the training set, meaning the model cannot recognize conditions leading to their formation, a critical gap given their rapid, unexpected development. These limitations reflect the defined scope of the classification task rather than inherent model flaws, which is vital for the correct interpretation of false negatives.

Dependence on Specific Features and Methods

Our approach relies on a specific subset of features and modeling choices. The feature selection process, though beneficial, might have inadvertently excluded other relevant predictive variables. Similarly, our custom-engineered features, tailored to the available dataset, may not generalize to contexts with different snowpack structures or meteorological dynamics.

Finally, while the SVM with an RBF kernel performs well, it is less interpretable and scalable than alternatives like Random Forests, XGBoost, or deep learning models. Future work could explore these methods to assess their advantages in handling larger datasets, automatic feature interaction modeling, and enhanced interpretability.

6.6.3 Operational Implications and Future Directions

The results underscore the potential of our SVM-based model as a valuable support tool in operational avalanche forecasting. It is designed to complement, not replace, expert judgment by providing data-driven insights that enhance traditional methods, particularly in interpreting complex interactions.

Its ability to consistently identify relevant predictors and provide reliable outputs across seasons suggests its utility as a first-level alert system or a component within a broader multi-criteria decision framework. The real-case application, simulating a one-day prediction shift for next-day risk, confirmed its effectiveness in an operational setting.

The integration of SHAP analysis is crucial, enhancing transparency by allowing forecasters to understand feature contributions to predictions and assess alignment with physical expectations. This interpretability, along with typical feature values, provides early indicators of evolving risk.

For full operational deployment, incorporating numerical weather forecasts would be a key next step, though this requires re-engineering the model pipeline to handle forecast uncertainty. A pragmatic intermediate solution could involve expert-driven data synthesis from forecasted values, allowing the model’s use without full automation. Both approaches, however, are subject to propagated meteorological forecast errors (data uncertainty) and model limitations (model uncertainty). Ultimately, the model serves as an aid, offering a new lens for complex avalanche dynamics, rather than a definitive replacement for expert judgment.

Integration with existing forecasting systems can be achieved through modular implementation, updating daily with real-time AWS data and embedding within operational dashboards alongside other information sources. Crucially, clear guidelines and training are essential for non-technical users to interpret results in

conjunction with their expertise, especially concerning known model limitations (e.g., exclusion of small or certain slab avalanches).

Looking forward, several avenues could enhance the model’s reliability and scope:

- Incorporation of additional variables, such as wind speed/direction, detailed snow stratigraphy, and physically modeled data.
- Moving towards multi-class classification of avalanche types (e.g., dry slab, wet loose, glide) with more diverse and labeled datasets for nuanced forecasting.
- Exploring ensemble methods (e.g., Random Forest, XGBoost) to quantify predictive uncertainty and improve robustness.

6.6.4 Summary of Key Findings

Model Performance and Validation

The model demonstrated strong performance in distinguishing avalanche from non-avalanche events, confirming its operational suitability. On an independent test set, it achieved an F1-score of 0.827, MCC of 0.659, and an AUC above 0.88, showing robust predictive power and excellent class discrimination. Critically, it maintained a low false negative rate (avoiding missed avalanches) while minimizing false positives. Overall, its performance and feature insights support its integration into avalanche risk frameworks, providing a reliable, data-driven tool. The positive outcome confirms the potential of data-driven tools for avalanche prediction, even with limited data, and suggests current data collection practices are largely sufficient.

Key Predictive Features and Physical Interpretation

The developed model enhances understanding of the main features driving avalanche risk and their typical value ranges. Seasonality, influenced by solar radiation and snowpack moistening, is critical, with risk rising from mid-February to early March. Snow depths around 90–100 cm at 2000 meters reduce surface roughness and mechanical anchoring. Precipitation exceeding 20 mm (20–40 cm of snow) combined with a deep, soft snow layer over 40 cm (identified via ram penetration) indicates both load and weak layers. Warmer snow temperatures near -2 to -3 °C and settlements greater than 5 cm reflect snowpack metamorphism and compaction. These findings align with established avalanche science and physical snowpack processes, particularly those dominated by moistening and wet snow avalanches. This multidimensional understanding reflects the non-linear, dynamic nature of avalanche systems with threshold effects and feedback loops, enabling more accurate risk predictions.

Beyond individual features, the model effectively captures complex interactions among multiple variables, such as precipitation intensity, temperature trends, and snow depth, and how they jointly influence snowpack stability.

Operational Context

The model is designed to support operational avalanche forecasting, offering timely and reliable risk assessments suitable for integration into existing decision-making frameworks. It improves warning accuracy by highlighting critical thresholds and capturing complex feature interactions more nuanced than traditional methods.

Operational use demands consistent, high-quality input data and continuous updates. Limitations include its focus on medium/large avalanches, exclusion of certain types (like wind slabs), and reliance on data quality. Site-specific temperature variability emphasizes the need for local calibration.

Integrating SHAP tools significantly enhances transparency, clarifying model decisions and boosting operator trust. Ongoing training for forecasters is essential to ensure confident and informed use of the model outputs and SHAP explanations.

Ultimately, the model serves as a decision support tool that complements forecaster expertise, combining data-driven insights with human experience to improve avalanche risk management and public safety. This work advances prior studies by quantitatively capturing complex environmental interactions at a local

scale with limited data, and by enhancing transparency through SHAP, a focus not extensively addressed previously.

6.6.5 Future Research and Practice

Insights from this study can guide the design of more focused monitoring systems, prioritizing critical variables like snow depth, temperature, and precipitation in real time. The success of combining machine learning with explainability tools like SHAP encourages further exploration of hybrid models that integrate physical snowpack knowledge with data-driven methods. Future studies could include additional environmental factors such as wind or snow crystal structure to capture more complex drivers.

Despite promising results, data limitations remain. Our model currently focuses on medium/large avalanches, excluding smaller but relevant events, and its accuracy depends on the quality and availability of historical data, which varies regionally. Improved spatial and temporal data coverage, with more automated sensors and snow observation sites closer to avalanche-prone areas, would significantly enhance model accuracy and generalizability. Methodologically, future work can refine feature engineering, explore alternative machine learning architectures, and develop dynamic models adaptable to changing climate conditions. Systematic validation across diverse mountain regions is crucial for assessing robustness and supporting adaptation.

Practically, our model should complement, not replace, expert judgment. Integrating model outputs with forecaster experience and local knowledge ensures more reliable risk assessments. Training users on interpreting SHAP and similar explanations will foster trust and facilitate wider adoption. Overall, this study lays a strong foundation for advancing avalanche forecasting through data-driven approaches, emphasizing ongoing data enhancement, methodological innovation, and thoughtful operational integration.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Work

7.1 Novel Contributions

This thesis demonstrates the practical feasibility and effectiveness of applying machine learning techniques, specifically Support Vector Machines (SVM), for local-scale avalanche forecasting within an operational context. Unlike many studies that focus on broad regional predictions, this work addresses the specific challenges of developing accurate, interpretable models tailored to a localized environment where data availability is limited and site-specific conditions strongly influence avalanche dynamics.

Working at a local scale introduces several unique complexities. The availability of high-quality, comprehensive datasets is often limited both at local and regional scales, as automated weather stations and snowpack sensors may be sparse or inconsistently maintained. However, at the local scale, these issues are exacerbated due to the limited number of available stations. Moreover, the influence of microclimates, small-scale climatic variations driven by topography, altitude, and exposure, creates highly heterogeneous snow conditions even within short distances. This local variability poses challenges for accurately modelling avalanche occurrences, requiring carefully engineered features and preprocessing steps to effectively capture relevant patterns without overfitting to noise or very specific local conditions.

A central contribution of this research is the balanced approach to enhancing predictive accuracy while preserving model interpretability. By leveraging tools such as SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), the study moves beyond treating machine learning as a “black box” and offers clear, actionable explanations of how meteorological, snowpack, and terrain factors contribute to avalanche risk. For example, SHAP analysis revealed that variables such as recent snowfall amount and seasonality consistently had the highest impact on model predictions, aligning with expert intuition. This transparency fosters trust and facilitates the practical use of the model by forecasters, enabling data-driven insights to complement expert knowledge.

Importantly, the proposed model is designed as a decision support system that integrates naturally with existing expert-based forecasting workflows. For instance, during a typical forecasting day, the model provides quantitative risk scores based on the latest meteorological inputs, which forecasters review alongside observational data and their experiential judgment. This integration helps highlight borderline cases where expert intervention is critical or flags unusual patterns that might be overlooked, thereby enhancing consistency and situational awareness without supplanting human expertise.

Throughout the development process, particular attention was given to ensuring that the model addresses real-world operational challenges and fits within practical forecasting workflows. This evaluation was conducted using data from the most recent winter season. To simulate realistic usage conditions, the avalanche observations were temporally shifted by one day, allowing the model output to be evaluated as if it were part of a real-time decision-making process. This approach ensured that the system was tested under operational constraints, reinforcing its practical relevance and supporting its potential integration into day-to-day forecasting activities.

Methodologically, the thesis addresses common issues in avalanche data, such as severe class imbalance and feature relevance, through tailored preprocessing, feature selection, and model tuning. The resulting SVM models demonstrate improved robustness and predictive performance compared to traditional empirical methods, confirming the value of machine learning as a complementary approach to enhance avalanche

forecasting.

Finally, the case study conducted in the Pejo Ski Area confirms the model’s effectiveness at a local scale, demonstrating its potential to support daily avalanche risk assessments, enhance the safety of winter sports enthusiasts, and minimize economic losses associated with slope closures. This tangible operational relevance represents a significant step forward in bridging the gap between advanced machine learning techniques and their practical application in real-world mountain safety management.

7.2 Limitations and Issues

Despite the promising results achieved in this study, several important limitations and challenges remain.

The dataset used to train and validate the models is limited to only two avalanche types: new snow and wet snow avalanches. Slab avalanches were excluded due to a lack of continuous wind data and their limited occurrence in the dataset. This restriction represents a significant limitation on the model’s applicability, as it only captures a subset of avalanche dynamics. Users should be aware that the model does not account for other important avalanche types, such as wind-driven slab avalanches, which may behave differently and require separate consideration.

Avalanche formation in the area is strongly influenced by localized climatic and topographic conditions. For example, the prevalence of loose snow avalanches suggests that specific meteorological triggers, such as solar radiation and rapid temperature increases following significant snowfall, play an important role. These local conditions shape the features identified as most predictive during model training, emphasizing physical processes like melt-driven instability.

As a result, the model is finely tuned to the avalanche mechanisms most relevant to these local conditions. However, other important processes, such as wind-related slab formation, are underrepresented or absent in the model. Consequently, its predictive behavior is biased toward a narrow subset of avalanche processes, which limits the model’s comprehensiveness.

Second, the issue of class imbalance, where avalanche events are much rarer than non-events, poses a fundamental challenge for model training and evaluation. While techniques such as resampling were applied to mitigate this, the rarity of positive examples can still lead to models that are overly conservative or insensitive to borderline cases. This is particularly problematic for low-frequency, high-impact events, where missing a rare but dangerous avalanche could have serious consequences for safety and decision-making.

Third, the overall quality and nature of the input data represent another important limitation. In this study, manual observations were used as the primary data source, while automated weather station (AWS) data were deliberately excluded. Although AWS data can provide high-frequency and more precise measurements, it often suffers from issues such as sensor malfunctions during snowstorms or extreme cold, communication outages, calibration drift, or inconsistent data continuity. These problems make post-processing and quality control more complex and can introduce unreliable signals into the model.

In contrast, manually collected data, despite being less frequent (typically once per day) and geographically more distant from avalanche release zones, were chosen for their longer historical continuity and higher overall reliability. Manual observations tend to undergo basic quality checks at the time of collection and are less susceptible to the types of technical failures common in automated systems. However, this approach introduces its own set of limitations: the lower temporal resolution reduces the model’s ability to capture rapidly evolving conditions, and the set of available parameters is narrower compared to what AWS could provide.

Moreover, manual data collection inherently carries the risk of human error and lacks the systematic post-processing quality control found in more structured sensor networks. Such inaccuracies, even if occasional, can propagate through the model pipeline and degrade the accuracy of predictions. These limitations highlight a key trade-off between data quality, quantity, and relevance in operational avalanche forecasting. Future efforts might explore hybrid solutions that combine the reliability of manual data with the richness and temporal resolution of AWS data, provided adequate validation and error-handling frameworks are in place.

Furthermore, although interpretability tools like SHAP improve the transparency of the predictions, the underlying complexity of machine learning models may still represent a barrier to their adoption in operational forecasting. In practice, the introduction of data-driven tools often encounters resistance from practitioners who are accustomed to heuristic or experience-based decision-making. Full integration requires not only

technical trust in the model’s performance but also institutional acceptance, which may depend on targeted training, familiarity with the tool, and gradual demonstration of added value in real-world scenarios.

Finally, this study did not implement or test the integration of the models into a real-time operational forecasting workflow. Transitioning from an offline research environment to real-time use requires a set of technical and organizational capabilities, including a reliable data communication infrastructure to ensure timely input delivery, automated model retraining pipelines to incorporate the latest data, and intuitive user interfaces that present outputs in a clear and actionable format. Without these components, the model remains a promising prototype rather than a fully operational tool.

Recognizing and understanding these limitations is essential for guiding future developments. Addressing them will be critical for improving model robustness, enhancing usability in the field, and supporting the broader goal of integrating machine learning into traditional avalanche forecasting practices in a way that respects and augments human expertise.

7.3 Future Developments

Building on the findings and limitations identified in this thesis, several promising directions for future research and development are proposed to enhance the accuracy, robustness, and practical utility of machine learning models in avalanche forecasting.

First, it is essential to test and validate the entire modeling procedure, including class imbalance handling, feature selection, and hyperparameter tuning, on datasets from other alpine regions with diverse climatic and topographic conditions. While the model itself is designed to remain site-specific for local-scale forecasting, applying the methodology elsewhere will assess its robustness and adaptability. Additionally, testing the model’s performance under extreme conditions and rare avalanche events is critical to ensure reliability in the most challenging and high-risk scenarios.

Second, expanding and diversifying data sources has the potential to significantly enhance model inputs and improve prediction accuracy. Valuable additions could include data from Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) equipped with advanced sensors and standardized quality control protocols, as well as IoT-based sensor networks strategically deployed in known avalanche release zones. Remote sensing products, particularly satellite imagery, useful for identifying indicators such as wet snow or surface melt, can provide spatially extensive insights. Furthermore, integrating outputs from physically based snowpack models and high-resolution numerical weather predictions can offer deeper context on snow stability and weather-driven avalanche triggers. By combining these heterogeneous inputs within a multimodal machine learning framework, it becomes possible to generate more detailed, dynamic, and context-aware avalanche risk assessments.

Third, exploring advanced machine learning techniques, such as ensemble methods, deep learning architectures, hybrid physical-data-driven models, and continual learning frameworks, could better capture complex, nonlinear relationships and enable the models to adapt over time as new data becomes available.

Fourth, further development of interpretability and explainability methods tailored to avalanche forecasting is essential. Increasing transparency will foster greater trust and acceptance among forecasters and stakeholders, facilitating the integration of these tools into daily operational workflows.

Fifth, practical implementation considerations are vital. This includes establishing real-time data pipelines, automating model retraining, and creating user-friendly interfaces that deliver actionable insights promptly. Additionally, involving forecasters and end-users in the development process through iterative feedback loops can improve usability and ensure that the tools meet operational needs effectively.

Finally, standardizing data collection protocols across different monitoring sites will facilitate broader adoption and interoperability, enabling more seamless integration of machine learning tools in diverse alpine environments. Collaboration among researchers, operational forecasters, and technology providers will be key to transforming these advances into tangible safety improvements and economic benefits in mountain regions. Looking ahead, presenting future developments at professional gatherings such as snow science workshops and technical meetings would provide valuable opportunities to share results and collect feedback on which future directions to pursue. Engaging with forecasters and researchers in these settings helps ensure that new tools evolve in ways that meet real operational needs and priorities.

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Appendix A: Technical Data

Data Description

This work utilizes data from Mod.1 AINEVA, collected at Pejo Tarlenta (2000 m a.s.l.) within the Pejo ski area. The dataset spans winter seasons from 1995–1996 through 2023–2024 and is used for model training and testing. Data from the 2024–2025 winter season serve for real-world application and validation.

The data are publicly available through the MeteoTrentino website: <https://www.meteotrentino.it> where CSV files for each winter season can be downloaded.

Additionally, the internal avalanche database of Pejo Funivie was used for validating avalanche occurrences during the 2024–2025 season.

Mod.1 data include both predictor features and avalanche observations, which serve as the target labels for our supervised machine learning model.

Further details on data characteristics and preprocessing are provided in the subsequent chapter.

Model Source Code

All source code and implementation scripts are publicly available on my personal page on Github: https://github.com/bridachristian/avalanches_forecast/

This repository contains scripts for data preprocessing, feature engineering, and model development. While the code is functional, full documentation and detailed usage instructions are still in progress and will be completed soon.

Technical Implementation

The entire modeling pipeline was implemented in Python, leveraging open-source libraries to ensure reproducibility. Key packages and versions used include:

- numpy==1.26.4
- pandas==2.2.3
- matplotlib==3.10.1
- seaborn==0.13.2
- scikit-learn==1.5.1
- mlxtend==0.23.4
- imbalanced-learn==0.13.0
- optuna==3.6.1
- scipy==1.14.1
- shap==0.47.2
- IPython==8.36.0
- joblib==1.4.2

The code was run on a Windows 11 Home environment (Version 24H2, Build 26100.4061) with Python 3.10.17. Hardware specifications include an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8750H CPU @ 2.20 GHz (6 cores, 12 threads) and 16 GB RAM.

To guarantee consistent results, a fixed random seed (42) was set for all stochastic processes, including data splitting, resampling (under- and oversampling), and model training.

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